

Design Optimization and Realization Of Interband Cascade Lasers Beyond The Sweet-Spot Operation Wavelength

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Borislav Petrović

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1. Gutachter: Prof. Dr. Sven Höfling

2. Gutachter: Prof. Dr. Karl Brunner

3. Gutachter: _____

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1. Prüfer: Prof. Dr. Sven Höfling

2. Prüfer: Prof. Dr. Karl Brunner

3. Prüfer: Prof. Dr. Thorsten Ohl

4. Prüfer: _____

5. Prüfer: _____

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
AFM	Atomic force microscopy
AR	Active region
BA	Broad area
BFM	Beam flux monitoring
CBO	Conduction band offset
cw	Continuous wave
EDQE	External differential quantum efficiency
FCA	Free carrier absorption
FGR	Fractional growth rate
FTIR	Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy
FTS	Fourier transform spectrometry
FWHM	Full-width-half-maximum
HR-XRD	High-resolution X-ray diffraction
ICL	Interband cascade laser
IQE	Internal quantum efficiency
LDG	Linear digital grating
LMIG	Liquid metal ion gun
MBE	Molecular beam epitaxy
MCT	HgCdTe
MQW	Multi quantum well
NRL	Naval Research Laboratory
OPD	Optical path difference
P/A	Perimeter-to-area ratio
PL	Photoluminescence
PR	Photoreflectance
QCL	Quantum cascade laser
QW	Quantum well
RGA	Residual gas analyzer
RT	Room temperature
RWG	(Narrow) ridge waveguide
SCL	Separate confinement layers
SEM	Scanning electron microscopy
SIMS	Secondary-ion mass spectroscopy
SL	Superlattice
SMI	Semi-metallic interface
SNR	Signal-to-noise ratio
SRH	Shockley-Read-Hall
STEM	Scanning transmission electron microscopy
TDLAS	Tunable diode laser absorption spectroscopy
TE	Transversional electric (field)
TEM	Transmission electron microscopy
TL	Transition layer
TM	Transversional magnetic (field)
TOF	Time of flight
UHV	Ultra-high vacuum
VBO	Valence band offset

VCSEL	Vertical-cavity surface-emitting laser
VISA	Valence intersubband absorption

Summary

The main objective of the work was to optimize designs of epitaxially grown mid-infrared interband cascade lasers (ICLs) of different wavelengths based on GaSb and InAs substrates. This implies design, growth and characterisation of low threshold current lasers as well as the theoretical and experimental comparisons of lasers with different claddings and/or growths on different substrates.

ICLs are portable photonic devices emitting in mid-infrared region, featuring low threshold current and threshold power densities and high voltage efficiencies. The light emission is based on interband recombination. The active region of an ICL is cascaded, thus it exhibits multiple photon generation for a recombination of a single electron and hole. A high number of stages contributes to lower threshold carrier density to obtain lasing; however, it also increases the overall voltage, hence there is a trade-off between threshold current and threshold power density. A single stage of the active region is composed of InAs/GaSb/InAs recombination region, hole injector and electron injector. The detailed principle of an ICL is explained in section 3.3. In addition to active region, waveguides of the ICLs play an important role in the performance of the ICL. The main purpose of waveguides is to optically confine the mode to the active region and to separate the mode from the highly doped substrate to avoid the optical losses. In addition, it is important that waveguides provide a sufficient heat dissipation from the active region for a stable laser operation. For these reasons, materials of low refractive index and high thermal conductivity are desirable when designing the waveguides of an ICL. Plasmon-enhanced InAs(Sb) claddings are particularly interested materials as with higher doping, their refractive index can substantially reduce, however on expense of higher optical absorption losses due to high doping. The optical absorption losses are limiting the wavelength range of ICL operation at room temperature. The influences of different waveguide designs on performance of ICLs are discussed in the first three published works listed in the end of this dissertation.

In the first work, the two 6-stages GaSb-based ICLs emitting at 5.0 μm of the same active region and geometry, but different cladding species were grown. One ICL was featuring quaternary bulk $\text{Al}_{0.85}\text{Ga}_{0.15}\text{As}_{0.07}\text{Sb}_{0.93}$ of lower refractive index of $n_r = 3.30$ and the other, the commonly used AlSb/InAs superlattice (SL) claddings of $n_r = 3.39$. The lower refractive index provided 14.4 % higher optical mode confinement factor in the active region. The ICL with bulk claddings has shown the superior performance, as its room temperature (RT) threshold current density was 24 % lower than the ICL with SL claddings. The measured threshold power densities of the two ICLs were however comparable due to wider transition layers and insufficient doping of the cap layer of the ICL with bulk claddings, that resulted in its higher series resistance.

Plasmon-enhanced claddings have gained attention in recent years as they gradually extended the operation window of ICLs to beyond 14 μm at cryogenic temperatures. In the second work, a similar concept, but for shorter wavelengths, was applied to GaSb-based ICLs and plasmon-enhanced $\text{InAs}_{0.915}\text{Sb}_{0.085}$ lattice-matched to GaSb. The device parameters were optimized in terms of maximizing the optical confinement in the active region and minimizing the overall absorption losses. Furthermore, two ICLs emitting at 4.6 μm with the same 12-stages active region and hybrid SL plasmon-enhanced claddings were grown on InAs and GaSb substrates. It is shown that due to lower refractive index of outer $n^+\text{-InAs}_{0.915}\text{As}_{0.085}$ layer ($n_r = 2.88$) than of $n^+\text{-InAs}$ ($n_r = 3.10$) and due to higher refractive index of GaSb separate confinement layers (SCLs) than of InAs SCLs, the ICL grown on GaSb substrate has 3.8 % higher optical confinement factor in the active region. Experimentally, the GaSb-based ICL has performed with 15.3 % lower threshold current density, but also 12.8 % higher threshold voltage, resulting in

comparable threshold power densities. The measured absorption losses in GaSb-based and InAs-based ICLs of 5.8 cm^{-1} and 4.6 cm^{-1} are reasonably matching with the calculated values of 6.4 cm^{-1} and 4.9 cm^{-1} . Despite the lower optical mode confinement in highly doped plasmon-enhanced claddings in GaSb-based ICL, the lower mobility in the GaSb than in InAs SCLs resulted in higher total free carrier absorption (FCA) in GaSb-based ICL. It is shown that the calculated threshold gains of the two ICLs are equal due to compensation of higher optical confinement in the active region with the higher absorption losses, and vice-versa.

Finally, in the third work a high performance 8-stages ICL emitting at $5.2 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ and featuring the hybrid cladding design, was realized. Due to the low refractive index of n^+ -InAs_{0.915}As_{0.085} ($n_r = 2.70$), the cladding design projected 11.2 % higher optical mode overlap with the active region than the ICL of the same active region and SL claddings. The measured RT threshold current density of $J_{th} = 242 \text{ A/cm}^2$ is the lowest reported value in pulsed mode for wavelengths longer than $5 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$. The threshold power density of $P_{th} = 840 \text{ W/cm}^2$ was matching the lowest reported values at similar wavelengths. The threshold current density of continuous wave (cw) operation at RT was higher than pulsed operation was suggesting, $J_{th} = 861 \text{ A/cm}^2$. The maximum measured output power was 6.1 mW, with the wallplug efficiency of 1.4 %, which is in the range of reported values in literature.

In addition to variations and optimizations of cladding designs, an alternative active region is discussed for long wavelength emission. A design composed of **AlSb/InAs/GaInSb/InAs_{1-x}Sb_x/GaInSb/InAs/AlSb** was proposed for a recombination region of long wavelength ICL with a focus on wavelength of $7.5 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$. The symmetrical triple V-shaped well design has shown 18.9 % higher wavefunction overlap than the standard W-shaped well of the same wavelength. For this comparison, both W-shaped and triple V-shaped designs were optimized for every layer thickness and arsenic fraction ratio of the middle well (x). In addition, the calculated valence intersubband absorption (VISA) loss of the V-shaped structure was notably lower than for W-shaped QW regardless of bias applied. However, it is shown that despite the higher wavefunction overlap and lower absorption, application of triple V-shaped wells in ICLs can be challenging due to high bias sensitivity of the coupling of ground states of electron InAs(Sb) and hole GaInSb QWs.

Zusammenfassung

Das Hauptziel dieser Arbeit war die Optimierung von Designs epitaktisch gewachsener Interband-Kaskadenlaser (ICLs) im mittleren Infrarotbereich mit unterschiedlichen Wellenlängen auf GaSb- und InAs-Substraten. Dies umfasst das Design, das Wachstum und die Charakterisierung von Lasern mit niedriger Schwellstromdichte sowie theoretische und experimentelle Vergleiche von Lasern mit verschiedenen Claddings und/oder auf unterschiedlichen Substraten.

ICLs sind tragbare photonische Bauelemente, die im mittleren Infrarotbereich emittieren und sich durch niedrige Schwellstrom- und Schwelleistungsdichten sowie hohe Spannungseffizienzen auszeichnen. Die Lichtemission basiert auf Interbandrekombination. Die aktive Region eines ICL ist kaskadiert, wodurch bei der Rekombination eines einzelnen Elektrons und Lochs mehrere Photonen erzeugt werden. Eine hohe Anzahl an Stufen trägt zu einer geringeren benötigten Trägerdichte zur Laseroszillation bei; sie erhöht jedoch gleichzeitig die Gesamtspannung. Es besteht somit ein Zielkonflikt zwischen Schwellstrom und Schwelleistungsdichte. Eine einzelne aktive Stufe besteht aus einer InAs/GaInSb/InAs-Rekombinationsregion sowie einem Loch- und einem Elektroneninjektor. Das Funktionsprinzip eines ICL wird detailliert in Abschnitt 3.3 erläutert. Neben der aktiven Region spielen die Wellenleiter eine wichtige Rolle für die Leistung des Lasers. Die Hauptfunktion der Wellenleiter besteht darin, die optische Mode in der aktiven Region zu halten und von dem hochdotierten Substrat fernzuhalten, um optische Verluste zu vermeiden. Außerdem ist eine ausreichende Wärmeableitung aus der aktiven Region für einen stabilen Laserbetrieb entscheidend. Daher sind Materialien mit niedrigem Brechungsindex und hoher Wärmeleitfähigkeit beim Design der Wellenleiter vorteilhaft. Besonders interessant sind plasmonisch verbesserte InAs(Sb)-Claddings, da ihr Brechungsindex durch hohe Dotierung stark gesenkt werden kann – jedoch auf Kosten höherer optischer Absorptionsverluste. Diese Verluste begrenzen den Wellenlängenbereich des ICL-Betriebs bei Raumtemperatur. Die Auswirkungen verschiedener Wellenleiterdesigns auf die Leistung von ICLs werden in den ersten drei veröffentlichten Arbeiten, die am Ende dieser Dissertation aufgeführt sind, diskutiert.

In der ersten Arbeit wurden zwei 6-stufige GaSb-basierte ICLs mit Emission bei $5,0\ \mu\text{m}$ und identischer aktiver Region und Geometrie, aber unterschiedlichen Claddings, hergestellt. Ein Laser besaß quaternäres $\text{Al}_{0.85}\text{Ga}_{0.15}\text{As}_{0.07}\text{Sb}_{0.93}$ -Bulk-Claddings mit einem niedrigeren Brechungsindex von $n_r = 3,30$, der andere verfügte über die üblichen AlSb/InAs-Superlattice(SL)-Claddings mit $n_r = 3,39$. Der niedrigere Brechungsindex ermöglichte eine um 14,4 % höhere optische Modenkonfinierung in der aktiven Region. Der Laser mit Bulk-Claddings zeigte eine überlegene Leistung: Die Schwellstromdichte bei Raumtemperatur war 24 % niedriger als beim Laser mit SL-Claddings. Die gemessenen Schwelleistungsdichten waren jedoch vergleichbar, was auf breitere Übergangsschichten und eine unzureichende Dotierung der Kappschicht beim Bulk-Design zurückzuführen ist, was wiederum zu einem höheren Serienwiderstand führte.

Plasmonisch verbesserte Claddings haben in den letzten Jahren an Bedeutung gewonnen, da sie den Betriebsbereich von ICLs bei kryogenen Temperaturen auf über $14\ \mu\text{m}$ erweitert haben. In der zweiten Arbeit wurde ein ähnliches Konzept auf kürzere Wellenlängen übertragen, wobei plasmonisch verstärktes $\text{InAs}_{0.915}\text{Sb}_{0.085}$, gitterangepasst zu GaSb, verwendet wurde. Die Geräteparameter wurden optimiert, um die optische Konfinierung in der aktiven Region zu maximieren und gleichzeitig die gesamten Absorptionsverluste zu minimieren. Darüber hinaus wurden zwei ICLs mit Emission bei $4,6\ \mu\text{m}$ und identischer 12-stufiger aktiver Region sowie hybriden SL-plasmonisch verstärkten Claddings auf InAs- und GaSb-Substraten

hergestellt. Es konnte gezeigt werden, dass aufgrund des niedrigeren Brechungsindex der äußeren n^+ -InAs_{0.915}Sb_{0.085}-Schicht ($n_r = 2,88$) im Vergleich zu n^+ -InAs ($n_r = 3.10$) sowie des höheren Brechungsindex der GaSb-SCLs gegenüber InAs-SCLs der auf GaSb gewachsene ICL eine 3,8 % höhere optische Konfinierung in der aktiven Region aufweist. Experimentell zeigte sich der GaSb-basierte ICL mit 15,3 % niedrigerer Schwellstromdichte, jedoch auch mit 12,8 % höherer Schwellspannung, was in vergleichbaren Schwelleistungsdichten resultierte. Die gemessenen Absorptionsverluste der GaSb- und InAs-basierten ICLs lagen bei $5,8 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ und $4,6 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, was gut mit den berechneten Werten von $6,4 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ bzw. $4,9 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ übereinstimmt. Trotz der geringeren Modenkönfinierung in den hochdotierten Claddings beim GaSb-basierten ICL führten die geringere Ladungsträgermobilität in GaSb-SCLs gegenüber InAs zu einer insgesamt höheren freien Trägerabsorption (FCA) im GaSb-basierten ICL. Es konnte gezeigt werden, dass die berechneten Schwellverstärkungen beider ICLs gleich sind, da sich höhere optische Konfinierung und höhere Verluste gegenseitig kompensieren.

In der dritten Arbeit wurde schließlich ein leistungsstarker 8-stufiger ICL mit Emission bei $5,2 \mu\text{m}$ und einem hybriden Cladding-Design realisiert. Aufgrund des niedrigen Brechungsindex von n^+ -InAs_{0.915}Sb_{0.085} ($n_r = 2.70$) wurde eine 11,2 % höhere Modenüberlappung mit der aktiven Region projiziert als bei einem ICL mit gleicher aktiver Region und SL-Claddings. Die gemessene Schwellstromdichte bei Raumtemperatur von $J_{\text{th}} = 242 \text{ A/cm}^2$ stellt den niedrigsten bisher berichteten Wert im Pulsmoden für Wellenlängen $>5 \mu\text{m}$ dar. Die Schwelleistungsdichte von $P_{\text{th}} = 840 \text{ W/cm}^2$ entspricht den niedrigsten in der Literatur berichteten Werten in diesem Wellenlängenbereich. Die Schwellstromdichte im Dauerstrichbetrieb (cw) bei Raumtemperatur war erwartungsgemäß höher und betrug $J_{\text{th}} = 861 \text{ A/cm}^2$. Die maximal gemessene Ausgangsleistung lag bei $6,1 \text{ mW}$ mit einem Wandsteckerwirkungsgrad (wallplug efficiency) von 1.4 %, was im Bereich der Literaturwerte liegt.

Neben der Variation und Optimierung der Cladding-Designs wurde eine alternative aktive Region für langwellige Emissionen diskutiert. Ein Design bestehend aus AlSb/InAs/GaInSb/InAs_{1-x}Sb_x/GaInSb/InAs/AlSb wurde für die Rekombinationsregion eines langwelligen ICL mit Fokus auf $7,5 \mu\text{m}$ vorgeschlagen. Das symmetrische Triple-V-Well-Design zeigte eine 18,9 % höhere Wellenfunktionsüberlappung als das Standard-W-Well-Design für dieselbe Wellenlänge. Für diesen Vergleich wurden beide Designs hinsichtlich Schichtdicken und Arsenanteil im mittleren Well (x) optimiert. Zusätzlich wurde festgestellt, dass die berechnete Valenzband-Intersubband-Absorption (VISA) des Triple-V-Designs unabhängig von der angelegten Vorspannung deutlich geringer ist als beim W-Well. Dennoch zeigt sich, dass die Anwendung der Triple-V-Struktur in ICLs herausfordernd ist, da die Kopplung der Grundzustände von Elektronen (InAs(Sb)) und Löchern (GaInSb) sehr empfindlich gegenüber der Vorspannung ist.

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1. Introduction

Detection of gasses and measuring their concentration has been of high importance in numerous applications, such as regulation in industrial process control [1], [2], [3], medical analysis [4], [5], [6], [7], [8], [9], atmosphere exploration [10], [11] environmental protection [12], [13], [14] and military, for detection of explosives [15] and for heat-seeking missiles [16]. Absorption lines of numerous organic and inorganic molecules lie in mid-infrared spectral range as depicted in Figure 1.1, similar to spectrum presented in [17]. Spectral fingerprints of most gasses relevant for environmental monitoring are in the 3-6 μm wavelength range. Measuring the concentration of water vapor (H_2O), methane (CH_4) and carbon-dioxide (CO_2) in atmosphere is used for weather forecasting [18], [19], while detection of carbon-monoxide (CO) is also substantial due to its poisonous, flammable and odourless properties. Secondly, industrial processes are commonly monitored in the wavelength range of 6-11 μm . Production lines for plastics and polyethylene in petrochemical industry, require detection of organic molecules such as methane, acetylene (C_2H_2), ethene (C_2H_4) and hydrogen sulphide (H_2S) [1]. Furthermore, fuel processes in engines produce highly toxic nitrous oxides (NO , NO_2), that are not only dangerous for health but are also greenhouse gasses mostly responsible for acid rain [20]. Finally, molecules of significance for medical applications lay in approximately the 8-12 μm wavelength range. For example, tracking amount of ammonia (NH_3) in blood, gives information about protein metabolism and potential liver diseases [4], [9], whereas presence of ethane (C_2H_6) in exhaled breath can indicate a lung disease [6].

Figure 1.1. Absorption lines of gas molecules in mid-infrared range. The data was taken from HITRAN data base.

Tunable diode laser absorption spectroscopy (TDLAS) [21] implies use of stable emission of light that resonates with vibrational or rotational modes of the molecules. In addition to conventional diode lasers, ICLs with their narrow linewidth and mid-infrared tunability, are increasingly employed in TDLAS systems for trace gas detection. Moreover, photoacoustic detection [22] and Fourier transform spectrometry (FTS) [23] is commonly used for detection of greenhouse gasses. A common and simplified setup for TDLAS is sketched in Figure 1.2. The intensity of the detected light, transmitted through the absorber region with wavelength-dependent coefficient α and molecule concentration N is given by Lambert-Beer law:

$$I(x) = I_0 e^{-\alpha(\lambda)Nx} \quad (1)$$

Figure 1.2. Schematic principle of TDLAS. The incident light resonant to vibrational/rotational modes of the molecules get absorbed and the attenuated light intensity is measured at the output.

The plotted absorption lines are based on HITRAN line strengths [24], but the values have been normalized (scaled between 0 and 1) for visualization. As such, the y-axis does not represent the absolute absorption coefficient $\alpha(\lambda)$ but rather the relative positions and intensities of the spectral features. To compute the actual absorption coefficient, the unscaled (absolute) HITRAN line strengths $S(T)$ would need to be used in combination with gas concentration and the line shape function as per:

$$\alpha(\lambda) = N \cdot S(T) \cdot g(\lambda - \lambda_0) \quad (1.1)$$

where $g(\lambda)$ is the line shape function of an absorption line. With the increasing demand for gas-sensing devices in the mid-infrared spectral range, the need for low threshold, highly efficient, portable devices has been increasing as well. ICLs emerged as a promising solution as they are tunable, coherent light sources with low threshold currents and power densities in the spectral window of 3-7 μm . In the mid-infrared range, quantum cascade lasers (QCLs) and lead-salt lasers (based on group IV-VI materials) have traditionally been used for gas sensing applications [25], [26]. However, QCLs typically require higher threshold currents and power consumption, while lead-salt lasers suffer from cryogenic cooling requirements and limited tunability. Interband cascade lasers (ICLs) offer a unique combination of low threshold currents, high tunability, high wall-plug efficiency, and room-temperature operation, making them especially suitable for portable and battery-powered sensing systems [3], [11], [14], [27], [28], [29]. A majority of ICLs are realized at the “sweet spot” operation wavelength of 3-4 μm [30], [31], [32]. ICL owe their low threshold current to its cascading scheme similar to QCLs [33]. However, ICLs operate based on interband transitions, hence due to three orders of magnitude higher upper laser lifetime, the number of cascade stages is significantly lower (usually 5-10). The first ICL design was proposed in 1994 by Rui Yang, then at University of Toronto. The paper was published the following year [34]. The design highlighted the recombination region of the electron and hole well in the broken band alignment, as the core of the laser. Nevertheless, the design was not including the hole injector, as there were no suggestions that it was needed [31]. The idea of tunnelling through the semi-metallic broken band alignment of neighbouring InAs and GaInSb layers originates from the previously established resonant interband tunnelling diodes realized at Caltech in 1989 [35]. Subsequently, the group from the Naval Research Laboratory (NRL) estimated the threshold

current densities of ICLs in the range of 100-200 A/cm² and predicted possible RT emission due to low Auger coefficients [36]. Such threshold is nowadays commonly obtainable in laboratory. The first experimental realization of ICL was made in 1997 by Li et al [37]. The laser contained 20 cascade stages and emitted at 3.8 μm in pulsed mode at temperatures up to 170 K. The threshold current density was reported at a few kA/cm². A few improvements in terms of output power were made the same year [38], [39]. The following year, I. Vurgaftman et al. demonstrated an ICL fabricated in form of vertical-cavity surface-emitting laser (VCSEL) [40] featuring **AlSb/InAs/GaInSb/InAs/AlSb** “W-shaped” QW that was already introduced in 1995 [41]. This recombination region design contains an additional InAs electron well to the previously proposed single electron-hole well pair **AlSb/InAs/GaSb/AlSb**. The idea was to increase the optical matrix element, and the “W-shaped” recombination region remains the state-of-the-art ever since. With this realization, the maximum operational temperature of ICL in pulsed mode got extended to 255 K. In subsequent years, the improvements were made by reducing number of wells in the electron injector to below 10. Furthermore, an extra well was added to hole injector design to prevent leakage of electrons from the recombination region to electron injector. This enabled operation temperature of 286 K [42]. A remarkable progress was made when the first pulsed operation at RT was demonstrated in 2002 [43], and the reported threshold current density was 6.9 kA/cm². At this point, cw operation was possible for temperatures up to 150 K. Further experimental work on ICLs with “W-shaped” recombination region led to reduction of threshold current density to ≈1.2 kA/cm² for a 15-stages device [44]. The cw operation was still limited to temperature of 200 K. An additional reduction to 630 A/cm² was achieved when the thick bottom cladding was introduced to prevent leakage of the optical mode into the GaSb substrate [45]. Thinning the first electron injector well enabled lasing at lower electric field, which reduced the threshold current density of cw operation from over 2 kA/cm² to 1.15 kA/cm². Additionally, it increased the maximum operation temperature to 261 K [46]. A major milestone was made in 2008 [47], by heavily doping the electron injector wells and by introducing SCLs to the cladding design. This improvement further reduced the threshold current density to ≈ 400 A/cm², which was the lowest value achieved up to then. In the same work, a narrow ridge variant of the laser performed the first cw operation at RT.

The state-of-the-art claddings are based on InAs/AlSb SLs due to lower refractive index than the recombination region and possibility of strain-compensated growth on GaSb and InAs substrates. However, materials with lower refractive indices and higher thermal conductivity are desirable, especially at longer wavelengths, due to need for a high confinement of the optical mode in the active region and a better heat dissipation.

The aim of this work is to investigate various cladding and active region structures of ICLs at wavelengths longer than the “sweet-spot” of 3-4 μm range. The work involves a theoretical optimization of their design and realization. In the publication [48], the superiority of Al_{0.85}Ga_{0.15}As_{0.07}Sb_{0.93} claddings over SL claddings was demonstrated for 5.0 μm ICLs, in terms of the threshold current density and the optical confinement. In the publication [49], the optimization of a GaSb-based ICL with a hybrid superlattice plasmon-enhanced cladding design was optimized in terms of the optical confinement in the active region and the FCA. In addition, it was shown that GaSb-based ICLs are superior to InAs-based ICLs with the same cladding structure and for emission wavelength of 4.6 μm. In the publication [50], a similar cladding structure was applied to GaSb-based ICL with emission wavelength of 5.2 μm. The obtained RT threshold current density was the lowest reported for the ICLs with wavelengths longer than 5 μm.

Despite the remarkable progress in development of ICLs, several key challenges remain. Extending efficient operation to longer wavelengths requires improved optical confinement and thermal management, especially as FCA and threshold currents tend to increase with wavelength. The trade-off between optical mode confinement and minimizing losses in highly doped claddings also remains an open issue. Furthermore, the influence of different substrate materials on device performance and the optimization of active region designs for maximizing wavefunction overlap and reducing absorption losses are ongoing research topics. This thesis addresses these challenges by investigating alternative cladding designs—including bulk and hybrid superlattice-plasmon-enhanced structures—and analyzing their impact on optical confinement, losses, and threshold characteristics. Additionally, it explores advanced active region designs, such as triple V-shaped quantum wells, aiming to extend efficient ICL operation towards longer wavelengths.

This dissertation is organized in the following chapters. In the second chapter, the crystal and band structure of semiconductors are introduced, and the calculation procedure of band structure is discussed. The third chapter is devoted to fundamentals of laser operation and to the theoretical discussion of the working principle of ICLs. The loss mechanisms are classified and described. The fourth chapter focusses on the epitaxial growth of the lasers and the laser device processing, as well as on growth calibration procedures and characterization tools and techniques.

The fifth chapter discusses benefits of alternative cladding designs to optimize the optical mode confinement and potentially improve the thermal management in ICLs of wavelengths longer than sweet-spot range 3-4 μm . Bulk $\text{Al}_x\text{Ga}_{1-x}\text{As}_y\text{Sb}_{1-y}$ and hybrid superlattice plasmon-enhanced claddings are discussed, grown and characterized as an alternative to state-of-the-art SL claddings. Optimization of hybrid cladding design is particularly addressed along with advantages and drawbacks of their growth on different substrates: InAs and GaSb.

The sixth chapter proposes a triple electron well design in the recombination region of GaSb-based ICLs as a means for increasing the oscillator strength and potentially extending the wavelength range of pulsed operation at RT to beyond 7 μm . The design optimization in terms of the wavefunction overlap was elaborated in detail. The range of RT operation of InAs-based ICLs has recently been extended to 7.7 μm , however by means of additional phosphorus-based layers [51].

2. III-V Semiconductor materials

ICLs are commonly composed of III-V materials. In the section 2.1. the crystal structure and band structure are described. Later, in 2.2. iterative procedure of solving Schrödinger-Poisson equation will be summarized as a method for determining band structures of the active region of the laser.

2.1. Crystal and band structure

The compound semiconductors from group III-V elements typically have a Zinc-blende crystal structure. It is composed of two face-centered cubic lattices of group III and group V elements, mutually shifted along $\langle 111 \rangle$ direction and for a quarter of spatial diagonal. Every group III atom is in the center of tetrahedron formed by group V atoms surrounding it. The lattice structure is depicted in Figure 2.1.1. Semiconductor materials are characterized by a bandgap energy between the allowed states of electrons occupying valence band and free electrons occupying the conduction band. Fermi level of semiconductors lays in the range of bandgap, whereas its position depends on the doping.

Figure 2.1.1. Unit cell of Zinc-blende lattice of GaSb. Zinc-blende lattice is composed of two face-centered lattices mutually shifted for a quarter of the space diagonal.

Materials of similar lattice constant can be grown with high crystal quality on top of each other forming a heterostructure. In terms of energy, different band gaps and offsets between the band edges of adjacent materials shape the electric potential. With quantization effect involved in a few nanometers' thick semiconductor layers, the electric potential forms QWs and barriers. Figure 2.1.2 presents the band gaps corresponding to lattice constants of the binaries of III-V elements [52]. In general, materials with smaller lattice constants exhibit larger band gap energies. The reason behind this is that energetic orbitals of the covalent bonds are split more if the atoms of the lattice are closer. As displayed in the figure, in terms of lattice constant, there are three sets of materials: 5.65 Å, 6.1 Å and 6.45 Å family. The binaries of 5.65 Å family have similar lattice constants to Ge and ZnSe, whereas the family of 6.45 Å also include CdTe and HgTe [53]. Unlike these two, 6.1 Å family has three binaries of III-V materials and hence provide more variability in design of laser diodes and photodetectors, thus GaSb and InAs substrates are

commonly used for growth of such devices. Ternary, quaternary, and even quinary materials are often required to meet the needs of optoelectronic devices [31], [54], [55]. The lattice constant of a ternary material is obtained from the Vegard's law [52]:

$$a_{A_xB_{1-x}C} = x \cdot a_{AC} + (1 - x) \cdot a_{BC} \quad (2.1.1)$$

The exact calculation of bandgaps of ternary alloys must include experimentally verified bowing coefficients ($K(x)$) which can be dependent on the molar fraction ratio:

$$E_g(A_xB_{1-x}C) = x \cdot E_g(AC) + (1 - x) \cdot E_g(BC) - x \cdot (1 - x) \cdot K(x) \quad (2.1.2)$$

Figure 2.1.2. Band gaps and lattice constants of III-V binaries. The 6.1 Å binaries are marked by the red contour.

The temperature dependence of the semiconductor band gap is determined by material-dependent Varshni parameters α and β as [52]:

$$E_g(T) = E_g(T = 0 \text{ K}) - \frac{\alpha T^2}{\beta + T} \quad (2.1.3)$$

Temperature dependences of the band gap energies of the III-V binaries are displayed in Figure 2.1.3. The relative changes of bandgaps between RT and $T = 0 \text{ K}$ are summarized in Table 2.1. The calculation shows that temperature sensitivities of indium-based binaries are highest, while that of aluminium-based are lowest. Knowing these temperature dependencies is desirable when the operational temperature of a device is known.

Figure 2.1.3. Temperature dependences of the bandgaps of III-V binary materials.

	AlAs	AlSb	GaAs	GaSb	InAs	InSb
$\Delta E_g/E_g(0K)$	0.031	0.036	0.063	0.085	0.153	0.261

Table 2.1. Relative changes of the bandgap from $T = 0$ K to $T = 300$ K of the III-V binaries.

Similarly, the valence band offsets (VBOs) of ternaries are calculated as:

$$VBO(A_xB_{1-x}C) = x \cdot VBO(AC) + (1 - x) \cdot VBO(BC) - x \cdot (1 - x) \cdot B(x) \quad (2.1.4)$$

where $VBO(AC)$ and $VBO(BC)$ are known VBOs for binary compounds relative to a common reference (vacuum level), and $B(x)$ is a VBO bowing parameter. Conduction band offsets (CBOs) of all the compounds are determined as:

$$CBO = VBO + E_g \quad (2.1.5)$$

In Figure 2.1.4, the conduction and valence band edges of the III-V binaries at RT are depicted. The band gaps of AlAs, AlSb, GaAs and GaSb are all higher than 350 meV, hence type-I QW structures employing these materials are not capable of reaching mid-infrared wavelengths. Although the bandgap of InAs would be suitable, the wavelength range of its type-I structures would be limited to wavelengths shorter than 3.5 μm . The band gap of InSb is about 174 meV and therefore also meets this criterion, nevertheless as it is the only III-V material of such long lattice constant, a tensile strain in other materials involved would be significant. In order to obtain longer wavelengths in mid-infrared range or to improve electron transport, the type-II band alignment between the adjacent materials needs to be introduced so that the optical transition is spatially indirect. This way, the wavelength of interest is not purely dependent on the bandgap of a single material, but it can be easily tuned by the right combination of layer thicknesses. The examples of structures of type-II alignment are 2.3 nm AlSb/2.43 nm InAs

and 2.14 nm GaSb/3.03 nm InAs SLs commonly employed in interband lasers [56], [57] and photodetectors, respectively [58].

Figure 2.1.4. Conduction and valence band edges of III-V binaries at $T = 300$ K. The material parameters are taken from Ref. [52].

Due to a few of nanometres thick barriers, the ground states in conduction and valence band of the SLs form minibands, as displayed in Figure 2.1.5.

Figure 2.1.5. Band structures of (a) GaSb/InAs SL used as absorber in interband photodetectors (b) AlSb/InAs SL commonly used as claddings in interband lasers, both grown on GaSb substrates.

The band structure was simulated by single band calculation performed by software nextnano³ [59]. The energy difference between the coupled states in conduction and valence band is defined as an effective bandgap of the SL. The effective bandgap of GaSb/InAs SL of $E_{\text{GaSb/InAs}} = 218$ meV (≈ 5.7 μm) which is a wavelength longer than type-I band structures can provide.

2.2. Schrödinger-Poisson equation

The band structure of semiconductor heterostructure under bias is modelled by Schrödinger-Poisson self-consistent model [60], [61], [62], [63], [64]. Firstly, the initial electron and hole densities $n^{(0)}$ and $p^{(0)}$ are assumed. Taking into account the space charges and free carriers, the Poisson equation reads:

$$\nabla_x \cdot [\varepsilon_0 \varepsilon_r(x) \nabla \varphi(x)] = -\rho(x). \quad (2.2.1)$$

The charge density distribution ρ is given by:

$$\rho^{(k)}(x) = e[-n^{(k-1)}(x) + p^{(k-1)}(x) + N_D^+(x) - N_A^-(x)] \quad (2.2.2)$$

where $n^{(k)}$ and $p^{(k)}$ are densities of electrons and holes of k -th iteration, while $N_D^+(x)$ and $N_A^-(x)$ are concentrations of ionized donors and acceptors.

From solving the Poisson equation, the electrostatic potential $\varphi^k(x)$ is obtained, and subsequently the energetic potential $V^k(x)$, based on potential of the material structure, ($V_0(x)$), carrier densities ($-e\varphi^k(x)$) and external field F ($-eFx$). The potential is then plugged into the Schrödinger equation:

$$\left[-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m^*} \nabla_x^2 + V_0(x) - e\varphi^k(x) - eFx \right] \psi_i^{(k)} = E_{n,i}^{(k)} \psi_i^{(k)} \quad (2.2.3)$$

The calculated wavefunction $\psi_i^{(k)}$ along with eigenenergy is used for determining the new carrier densities:

$$n^{(k)}(x) = \int_{E_{n,0}}^{E_{\infty,0}} \sum_{\nu} g_{\nu} \frac{m_{n,\nu}}{\hbar^2 \pi} \sum_i |\psi_{n,i}^{(k)}(x)|^2 \frac{1}{1 + e^{\frac{E-E_F}{k_B T}}} h(E - E_{n,i}) dE$$

$$p^{(k)}(x) = \int_{E_{-\infty,0}}^{E_{p,0}} \sum_{\nu} g_{\nu} \frac{m_{p,\nu}}{\hbar^2 \pi} \sum_i |\psi_{p,i}^{(k)}(x)|^2 \frac{1}{1 + e^{\frac{E_F-E}{k_B T}}} h(E - E_{p,i}) dE \quad (2.2.4)$$

where g_{ν} is a degeneracy factor of valley and spin index ν . Finally, the obtained carrier densities are compared to the values of previous iteration:

$$|n^{(k)}(x) - n^{(k-1)}(x)| < \varepsilon$$

$$|p^{(k)}(x) - p^{(k-1)}(x)| < \varepsilon. \quad (2.2.5)$$

If the difference is below the tolerance margin, the band structure is calculated. If it is not the case, the process re-starts in the next iteration. The self-consistent equations are solved

numerically, by finite difference method implemented in the nextnano³ software. The calculation of band structure is carried out for single band model due to better matching with experimentally measured wavelengths than 8 k·p, as the 8 k·p model involves more material parameters and hence more uncertainties. In addition, the single band model is less time and resource consuming when high number (tens of thousands) of data points is obtained, like in sweeps in chapters 5 and 6. The effective masses of compounds are taken from [52]. The nextnano³ solver solves stationary Schrödinger-Poisson equation and considers the Stark's shift and doping charge. However, the exact charge distribution under laser operation might be different from the calculated in Schrödinger-Poisson equation, as it would consider carriers in non-equilibrium state. The effects of non-equilibrium state and the effects from the subchapters 3.1.2 and 3.2. are not taken to account.

3. Semiconductor lasers

In this chapter, fundamental processes for laser operation are explained. The section 3.1. is dedicated to radiative and non-radiative recombination mechanisms present in the semiconductor lasers. Subsequently, in the section 3.2, working principle and the structure of an ICL is elaborated.

3.1. Light matter interaction

In this section, interband and intersubband transitions in the semiconductor lasers are discussed. The negative interband absorption (gain) is a result of an inverse population of the active region in the lasers based on interband transitions. The intersubband absorptions are positive and parasitic.

3.1.1. Interband absorption

Emission of photons in semiconductors is induced by energy transition of carriers between a high to a low state [65]. An electron occupying a higher state (b) can relax to a lower state (a) spontaneously by emitting a photon of energy equal to the difference:

$$E_b - E_a = \hbar\omega = \frac{hc}{\lambda} \quad (3.1.1.1)$$

This mechanism is called spontaneous emission. An emitted photon can be absorbed by another electron if the photon energy is sufficient to excite it to the higher state. In stimulated emission, an incident photon of energy $\hbar\omega$ interacts with an excited electron, causing it to transition to a lower energy state and emit a second photon that is coherent with the incident photon. Stimulated emission can continuously maintain electrons in a higher state by a presence of gain medium, based on two possible mechanisms: optical or electrical pumping. Acceleration of electrons by an external bias and absorption of photons of sufficient energy, provide continuous excitation of electrons to the upper laser level. The emitted light becomes amplified if the concentration of electrons in the higher state is higher than in the lower state, which is called "population inversion". To quantify the gain in a semiconductor laser based on interband transitions, the interband absorption should be derived. A semiconductor illuminated by light is considered and described by the k·p model. The Hamiltonian describing electron-photon interaction can be described as follows [65]:

$$H = \frac{(\mathbf{p} - e\mathbf{A})^2}{2m_0} + V(r). \quad (3.1.1.2)$$

The Hamiltonian can be expanded to

$$H = \frac{p^2}{2m_0} + V(r) - \frac{e}{2m_0} (\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{A} + \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{p}) + \frac{e^2 A^2}{2m_0} \approx \frac{p^2}{2m_0} + V(r) - \frac{e}{m_0} \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{p} \quad (3.1.1.3)$$

assuming $|e\mathbf{A}| \ll |\mathbf{p}|$ common for optical field intensities. The Hamiltonian can therefore be split into its unperturbed (H_0) and light-perturbed part ($H'(\mathbf{r})$):

$$H_0 = \frac{p^2}{2m_0} + V(r)$$

$$H'(\mathbf{r}) = -\frac{e}{m_0}\mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{p} = -\frac{eA_0 e^{-ikr}}{2m_0}\hat{\mathbf{e}} \cdot \mathbf{p}. \quad (3.1.1.4)$$

Assuming the transition from the lower energy state “a” to the higher energy level “b”, the absorption rate is given by Fermi’s golden rule:

$$W_{abs} = \frac{2\pi}{\hbar} |H'_{ba}|^2 \delta(E_b - E_a) = \frac{2\pi}{\hbar} |\langle b|H'(\mathbf{r})|a\rangle|^2 \delta(E_b - E_a) =$$

$$= \frac{2\pi}{\hbar} \left| \int \psi_b^*(r) H'(\mathbf{r}) \psi_a(r) d^3r \right|^2 \delta(E_b - E_a). \quad (3.1.1.5)$$

The transition rate per unit volume from energy level $E_a + \frac{\hbar^2 k_a^2}{2m^*}$ to energy level $E_b + \frac{\hbar^2 k_b^2}{2m^*}$ is dependent on the probabilities that the state “a” is occupied by an electron and that state “b” is empty, hence:

$$R_{a \rightarrow b} = \frac{2}{V} \sum_{k_a} \sum_{k_b} \frac{2\pi}{\hbar} |H'_{ba}|^2 \delta(E_b - E_a - \hbar\omega) f_a (1 - f_b). \quad (3.1.1.6)$$

Similarly, the emission rate from state “b” to state “a” is calculated as

$$R_{b \rightarrow a} = \frac{2}{V} \sum_{k_a} \sum_{k_b} \frac{2\pi}{\hbar} |H'_{ab}|^2 \delta(E_a - E_b + \hbar\omega) f_b (1 - f_a) \quad (3.1.1.7)$$

The absolute transition rates for absorption and stimulated emission are proportional to the photon density, which governs the interaction probability.

The absorption and emission processes are sketched in Figure 3.1.1.1.

Figure 3.1.1. Schematic illustration of absorption (R_{ab}) and stimulated emission (R_{ba}). Absorption occurs when a photon excites an electron from level a to b. In stimulated emission, an incident photon

induces the excited electron to relax from level b to a, emitting a second photon that propagates in the same direction and phase as the incident photon.

The net transition rate is therefore

$$R = R_{a \rightarrow b} - R_{b \rightarrow a} = \frac{2}{V} \sum_{k_a} \sum_{k_b} \frac{2\pi}{\hbar} [|H'_{ba}|^2 \delta(E_b - E_a - \hbar\omega) f_a (1 - f_b) - |H'_{ab}|^2 \delta(E_a - E_b + \hbar\omega) f_b (1 - f_a)] \quad (3.1.1.8)$$

which after some arrangement of terms leads to

$$R = \frac{2}{V} \sum_{k_a} \sum_{k_b} \frac{2\pi}{\hbar} |H'_{ba}|^2 \delta(E_b - E_a - \hbar\omega) (f_a - f_b) \quad (3.1.1.9)$$

Equation (3.1.1.8) represents the net stimulated transition rate and does not include spontaneous emission, which is independent of photon density.

Taking into account the intensity of the Poynting vector of the emitted electromagnetic field

$$|\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{r}, t)| = |\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}, t) \times \mathbf{H}(\mathbf{r}, t)| = \frac{n_r c \varepsilon_0 \omega^2 A_0^2}{2} \quad (3.1.1.10)$$

the optical absorption coefficient can be obtained as ratio of number of photons absorbed per unit volume and injected photons per unit area

$$\alpha(\hbar\omega) = \frac{R}{\frac{P}{\hbar\omega}} = \frac{R\hbar\omega}{\left(\frac{n_r c \varepsilon_0 \omega^2 A_0^2}{2}\right)} = \frac{2\pi e^2}{V n_r c \varepsilon_0 m_0^2 \omega} \sum_{k_a} \sum_{k_b} |\hat{\mathbf{e}} \cdot \mathbf{p}_{ba}|^2 \delta(E_b - E_a - \hbar\omega) (f_a - f_b) \quad (3.1.1.11)$$

If the previous expression is applied on the bulk semiconductor by implementing $k = k_b - k_a$, the absorption coefficient featuring states in conduction (c) and valence (v) band is

$$\alpha(\hbar\omega) = \frac{2\pi e^2}{V n_r c \varepsilon_0 m_0^2 \omega} \sum_{\mathbf{k}} |\hat{\mathbf{e}} \cdot \mathbf{p}_{cv}|^2 \delta(E_c - E_v - \hbar\omega) (f_v - f_c) \quad (3.1.1.12)$$

where Fermi distributions are defined as functions of the Fermi levels E_{fc} and E_{fv} as

$$f_v(\mathbf{k}) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{(E_v(\mathbf{k}) - E_{fv})/k_B T}}, \quad f_c(\mathbf{k}) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{(E_c(\mathbf{k}) - E_{fc})/k_B T}} \quad (3.1.1.13)$$

for energies of the initial and final state in bulk semiconductor given as:

$$E_c = E_g + \frac{\hbar^2 k^2}{2m_e^*}, \quad E_v = -\frac{\hbar^2 k^2}{2m_h^*}. \quad (3.1.1.14)$$

The initial (v) and final (c) state of the transition fulfil Bernard-Duraffourg inversion condition [66] that is needed for a presence of gain:

$$E_{Fc} - E_{Fv} > E_c - E_v = \hbar\omega > E_g \quad (3.1.1.15)$$

Active regions of majority of semiconductor lasers are composed of QWs, therefore it is necessary to derive the absorption coefficient for quantized energies, defined as:

$$E_c = E_g + E_{en} + \frac{\hbar^2 k_t^2}{2m_e^*}, \quad E_v = E_{hm} - \frac{\hbar^2 k_t^2}{2m_h^*}. \quad (3.1.1.16)$$

The energy transitions in both bulk and QW structures are depicted in Figure 3.1.1.2.

The momentum matrix \mathbf{p}_{cv} for the quantized states is then given by

$$\mathbf{p}_{cv} = \langle \psi_c | \mathbf{p} | \psi_v \rangle = \langle u_c | \mathbf{p} | u_v \rangle \delta_{\mathbf{k}_t, \mathbf{k}_t'} I_{hm}^{en} \quad (3.1.1.17)$$

where I_{hm}^{en} is the overlap integral of envelope wavefunctions of discrete states, n-th of the conduction and m-th of the valence band:

$$I_{hm}^{en} = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} dz \psi_n^*(z) \psi_m(z) \quad (3.1.1.18)$$

Figure 3.1.1.2. (a) Energy transition in bulk semiconductor (b) Energy transition between electron and hole state of a semiconductor QW.

Following the same quantization, the energy difference between the states in conduction and valence band is

$$\begin{aligned} E_c - E_v &= E_g + E_{en} + \frac{\hbar^2 k_t^2}{2m_e^*} - \left(E_{hm} - \frac{\hbar^2 k_t^2}{2m_h^*} \right) = E_g + E_{en} - E_{hm} + \frac{\hbar^2 k_t^2}{2} \left(\frac{1}{m_e^*} + \frac{1}{m_h^*} \right) \\ &= E_g + E_{en} - E_{hm} + E_t = E_{hm}^{en} + E_t \end{aligned} \quad (3.1.1.19)$$

whereas the absorption coefficient is

$$\alpha(\hbar\omega) = \frac{2\pi e^2}{Vn_r c \epsilon_0 m_0^2 \omega} \sum_{n,m} |I_{hm}^{en}|^2 \sum_{\mathbf{k}_t} |\hat{\mathbf{e}} \cdot \mathbf{p}_{cv}|^2 \delta(E_c - E_v - \hbar\omega) (f_v^m - f_c^n). \quad (3.1.1.20)$$

Considering the density of states in the QW

$$\rho_{2D} = \frac{m_e^* m_h^*}{m_e^* + m_h^*} \frac{1}{\pi \hbar^2} h(\hbar\omega - E_{hm}^{en}) = \frac{m_r^*}{\pi \hbar^2} h(\hbar\omega - E_{hm}^{en}) \quad (3.1.1.21)$$

and the definition of gain g as

$$g(\hbar\omega) = -\alpha(\hbar\omega) \quad (3.1.1.22)$$

the gain spectrum is obtained:

$$g(\hbar\omega) = \frac{2\pi e^2}{Vn_r c \epsilon_0 m_0^2 \omega} \sum_{n,m} |I_{hm}^{en}|^2 \frac{m_r^*}{\pi \hbar^2 L_z} |\hat{\mathbf{e}} \cdot \mathbf{p}_{cv}|^2 \delta(E_c - E_v - \hbar\omega) (f_c^n(E_t) - f_v^m(E_t)) h(\hbar\omega - E_{hm}^{en}). \quad (3.1.1.23)$$

Finally, if the broadening of linewidth (γ) is taken into account, the gain spectrum is obtained from:

$$g(\hbar\omega) = \frac{2\pi e^2}{Vn_r c \epsilon_0 m_0^2 \omega} \sum_{n,m} |I_{hm}^{en}|^2 \int_0^\infty \frac{m_r^*}{\pi \hbar^2 L_z} |\hat{\mathbf{e}} \cdot \mathbf{p}_{cv}|^2 \delta(E_c - E_v - \hbar\omega) (f_c^n(E_t) - f_v^m(E_t)) h(\hbar\omega - E_{hm}^{en}) \frac{\gamma/\pi}{[E_{hm}^{en} + E_t - \hbar\omega]^2 + \gamma^2} dE_t. \quad (3.1.1.24)$$

Apart from the population inversion, the necessary condition for lasing emission is a presence of the laser cavity in between two facets. The sketch of the cavity is presented in Figure 3.1.1.3. From the boundary condition for resonance of electromagnetic field in the cavity with medium of the average refractive index n_r it holds:

$$z\lambda = 2n_r L, \quad z \in \mathbb{N} \quad (3.1.1.25)$$

Figure 3.1.1.3. Fabry-Pérot cavity of a semiconductor laser.

The modal gain compensates the external (mirror) and internal absorption losses inside the active region (α_{AR}) and the waveguides (α_{WG}). Despite Lorentzian profile, the gain does not necessarily reach its maximum, but it is clamped at the value of the total losses, as sketched in

Figure 3.1.1.4. Considering the confinement factors of the optical mode in the active region (Γ_{AR}) and waveguides (Γ_{WG}) the equation follows:

$$\Gamma_{AR}g_{th} = \alpha_{mirror} + \Gamma_{AR}\alpha_{AR} + \Gamma_{WG}\alpha_{WG} \quad (3.1.1.26)$$

where the mirror losses for the cavity of length L and reflectivity of facets R_1 and R_2 is

$$\alpha_{mirror} = \frac{1}{2L} \ln\left(\frac{1}{R_1 R_2}\right) \quad (3.1.1.27)$$

Figure 3.1.1.4. The laser gain as a function of energy. The gain is positive for energies higher than bandgap and lower than difference between quasi-Fermi levels (Bernard-Durauffourg condition). Its real maximum is clamped at the threshold value determined by the total (internal and external) optical losses.

3.1.2. Intersubband absorption

In contrast to interband recombination as a driving mechanism of the lasing operation of the ICL, the absorption of photons occurs also between the subbands of the conduction and valence band. In this section, the two mechanisms of intersubband absorption are explained: principles of FCA absorption in the conduction band and the VISA.

3.1.2.1. Free carrier absorption (FCA)

Free charges can be excited to unoccupied states within the same band, higher than the ground state. Photon exciting the already excited carrier, instead of the carrier in the bound state, manifests as a loss. The absorption of photons participating in this process is FCA. Following the excitation, carriers thermally relax to the ground state by phonon scattering, increasing the temperature of the crystal lattice. In addition to intersubband absorption, FCA occurs also within the same subband between the two states with the same ground energy level but different kinetic energies. Such absorption is called intrasubband absorption.

The FCA losses can be derived from the Lorentz-Drude model [67] [68], assuming that an electron in the external electromagnetic field behaves as a damped oscillator:

$$m \frac{d^2}{dt^2} \overline{r(t)} + m\gamma \frac{d}{dt} \overline{r(t)} + m\omega_0^2 \overline{r(t)} = -e\overline{E(t)} \quad (3.1.2.1.1)$$

The electric permittivity can be derived from the equation as

$$\varepsilon_r = \frac{\varepsilon}{\varepsilon_0} = 1 - \frac{Ne^2}{m^* \varepsilon_0} \frac{1}{\omega^2 - \omega_0^2 - \frac{i\omega}{\tau}}. \quad (3.1.2.1.2)$$

As the electrons are free, the restoration force is zero, hence

$$\varepsilon_r = \frac{\varepsilon}{\varepsilon_0} = 1 - \frac{Ne^2}{m^* \varepsilon_0} \frac{1}{\omega^2 - \frac{i\omega}{\tau}}. \quad (3.1.2.1.3)$$

Expressing electric permittivity as a square of the complex refractive index gives

$$\varepsilon_r = (n + ik)^2 = \varepsilon_\infty \left[1 - \frac{\omega_p^2}{\omega^2 - \frac{i\omega}{\tau}} \right] \quad (3.1.2.1.4)$$

where plasma frequency ω_p and electron scattering time are determined by

$$\omega_p^2 = \frac{Ne^2}{m^* \varepsilon_\infty \varepsilon_0}, \quad \tau = \frac{\mu_e m_e^*}{e}. \quad (3.1.2.1.5)$$

The real and imaginary part of the electric permittivity can be extracted from equation (3.1.2.1.4) as:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Re}(\varepsilon_r) &= \varepsilon_\infty \left(1 - \frac{\omega_p^2}{\omega^2 + \frac{\omega}{\tau}} \right) \approx \varepsilon_\infty \left(1 - \frac{\omega_p^2}{\omega^2} \right) = n^2 - k^2 \approx n^2 \\ \text{Im}(\varepsilon_r) &= \varepsilon_\infty \frac{\omega_p^2}{\omega^3 \tau + \frac{\omega}{\tau}} \approx \varepsilon_\infty \frac{\omega_p^2}{\omega^3 \tau} = 2nk \end{aligned} \quad (3.1.2.1.6)$$

considering that the magnitude of imaginary part of the refractive index is much smaller than the real part.

Finally, the classical expression for FCA can be obtained from the imaginary part of the electric permittivity as [68], [69]:

$$\alpha_{FC} = \frac{4\pi k}{\lambda} = \frac{4\pi \text{Im}(\varepsilon_r)}{\lambda} \frac{1}{2n} \approx \frac{2\pi}{\lambda n} \varepsilon_\infty \frac{\omega_p^2}{\omega^3 \tau} = \frac{e^3}{4\pi^2 c^3 \varepsilon_0} \frac{N \lambda^2}{n \mu_e m_e^{*2}} \quad (3.1.2.1.7)$$

The FCA losses are therefore proportional to square of wavelength of the absorbed light.

3.1.2.2. Valence intersubband absorption (VISA)

When the energy of emitted light is higher than the energy difference between energies of the two eigenstates of the different parity, an absorption can occur. The VISA is heavily dependent on the light polarization. Light polarized parallel to the growth direction z (TM) is dominantly absorbed in intrasubband transition (hh2-hh1). Conversely, light polarized in x - y plane, perpendicular to growth direction (TE), is absorbed in intersubband transition (lh2-hh1, lh4-hh1, etc) [70]. The emitted light of the state-of-the-art ICL is dominantly TE polarized [32], [71]. Figure

3.1.2.2. presents the VISA for vertical energy transition (zero change in momentum) between the valence band states in a QW.

Figure 3.1.2.2. VISA between the light hole and heavy hole eigenstates.

Intensity of VISA is significantly stronger than intersubband absorption in conduction band [72]. As it is proportional to hole density, it increases with gain. However, the absorption can be attenuated by using strained layers in QW [73].

The absorption coefficient is given [74] by:

$$\alpha_{VISA} = \frac{4\pi^2 N e^2 \hbar}{3\omega m_0^2 c \sqrt{\epsilon}} \sum_{\mathbf{k}} |\langle \psi_{h1} | \mathbf{p} | \psi_{h2} \rangle|^2 \frac{(f_{h1} - f_{h2}) / \pi \tau_{h1h2}(\mathbf{k})}{[E_{h1}(\mathbf{k}) - E_{h2}(\mathbf{k}) - \hbar\omega]^2 + [1/\tau_{h1h2}(\mathbf{k})]^2} \quad (3.1.2.2)$$

where f_{h1} and f_{h2} are probabilities of occupation of the hole state with wave vector \mathbf{k} and $\tau_{h1h2}(\mathbf{k})$ is the average scattering time for holes in states $(h1, \mathbf{k})$ and $(h2, \mathbf{k})$. VISA has a strong influence on temperature dependence of the threshold current density; hence it is important to suppress it for obtaining the cw operation [75], [76], [77].

3.2. Non-radiative recombination

When the electron-hole recombination does not result in emission of a photon, the non-radiative process occurs. In this section, mechanisms of non-radiative losses are discussed: Auger and Shockley-Read-Hall recombination.

3.2.1. Auger recombination

The most prominent non-radiative mechanism limiting the threshold current of the ICLs is Auger recombination. There are four different occurrences in which Auger recombination can manifest in their corresponding rates [65]:

1. An electron in conduction band recombines with the hole from the valence band and transfers its energy to an adjacent electron (R_n)
2. An electron in conduction band recombines with the hole from the valence band and transfers its energy to an adjacent hole (R_p)
3. An electron does not recombine, but coincides with the lattice, breaks the bond and releases another electron from the valence band to the conduction band (G_n)
4. A hole collides with an electron in the valence band and breaks its bond by impact ionization, so electron jumps to the conduction band (G_p).

The four mechanisms are displayed in Figure 3.2.1. The horizontal lines indicate ground states and the parabolas indicate presence of kinetic energy.

The rate R_n is proportional to the electron concentration but also to concentrations of electron-hole pairs it destroys. Similarly, the rate R_p is proportional to the hole concentration and to the concentrations of destroyed electron-hole pairs

$$R_n = C_n n^2 p, \quad R_p = C_p n p^2. \quad (3.2.1.1)$$

The rates G_n and G_p are proportional to electron and hole concentrations:

$$\begin{aligned} G_n &= e_n n_0 = C_n n_0^2 p_0 = C_n n_i^2 n_0, \\ G_p &= e_p p = C_p n_0 p_0^2 = C_p n_i^2 p_0. \end{aligned} \quad (3.2.1.2)$$

Figure 3.2.1. (a) An electron in the conduction band transfer the energy to the nearby free electron (b) An electron in the conduction band transfers the energy to a nearby hole (c) Electron emission: a high energy free electron collides with electron in the valence band and excites it to the conduction band (d) Hole emission: a high energy hole excites bound electron to the conduction band resulting in generation of hole. The processes are labelled by "1" and "2" according to time sequence.

The net recombination rate is then calculated as

$$R_{AUGER} = R_n + R_p - G_n - G_p. \quad (3.2.1.3)$$

Considering that $n, p \gg n_i$, the total Auger recombine rate is

$$R_{AUGER} = R_n + R_p = C_n n^2 p + C_p p^2 n \quad (3.2.1.4)$$

3.2.2. Other non-radiative losses

In addition to Auger recombination, there are scattering losses that can occur at lattice defects and layer interfaces.

Shockley-Read-Hall (SRH) recombination [65] is a recombination mechanism based on trap states; hence its rate is dependent on the crystal quality of the material. The recombination processes labelled with corresponding rates (R) are presented in Figure 3.2.2. The trap state captures an electron (R_a) or release already captured electron (R_b) to the conduction band. Alternatively, it can capture (R_c) or release previously captured electron (R_d) to the valence band. The net SRH recombination rate is determined as difference of the rates delivering electrons to the trap state and the rates of emptying the trap state:

$$R_{SRH} = R_a + R_c - (R_b + R_d) \quad (3.2.2.1)$$

After derivation, the obtained net recombination rate is then:

$$R_{SRH} = \frac{np - n_i^2}{\tau_p(n + n_0) + \tau_n(p + p_0)} \quad (3.2.2.2)$$

Figure 3.2.2. (a) Rate of capturing electrons from the conduction band (b) Rate of releasing electrons to the conduction band (c) Rate of capturing electrons from the valence band (d) Rate of releasing electrons to the valence band.

Where n and p represent concentrations of injected electrons and holes, while τ_n and τ_p are their respective lifetimes. Concentration n_i is the intrinsic carrier density and n_0 and p_0 denote the carrier concentrations at Fermi level coinciding with the trap level E_t

$$n_0 = n_i \exp\left(\frac{E_t - E_i}{k_B T}\right), \quad p_0 = n_i \exp\left(\frac{E_i - E_t}{k_B T}\right). \quad (3.2.2.3)$$

As the τ_{SRH} is two orders of magnitude longer than Auger lifetime (≈ 0.5 ns), SRH recombination is not relevant for the ICL performance.

3.3. Interband cascade lasers (ICLs)

In this subchapter, the principle of operation of ICL is explained. The structure and roles of different parts of the ICL are discussed in detail.

3.3.1. Working principle of ICL

ICLs are bipolar optoelectronic devices that operate based on interband transitions and carrier recycling through a series of cascade stages. The active region typically includes 5–10 such stages. Unlike the parallel configuration of multi-quantum well (MQW) lasers—where the injected current is distributed among all wells, reducing carrier density per well—ICLs feature cascade stages connected in series [31], [78]. In ICLs, the same current sequentially traverses each stage. At each stage, electrons in the conduction band recombine with holes in the valence band, emitting photons. The resulting holes and electrons are then interband-tunneled through a semimetallic interface (SMI) back into the conduction band of the next stage, enabling carrier recycling and maintaining approximately uniform carrier densities across all stages. The band structure of 1.5 stages of its active region is depicted in Figure 3.3.1.1. The active region consists of the hole injector composed of AISb/GaSb, electron injector, composed of AISb/GaSb and the recombination region in a form of a W-shaped QW composed of **AISb/InAs/GaInSb /InAs/AISb** layers. The broken band alignment between the second hole injector well and the first electron injector well under bias enables transport of electrons from the top of the valence band in GaSb to conduction band of InAs. Without electric field, the ground state in the GaSb QW is higher than the ground state in InAs QW. With increasing external electric field, this energy gap is closing. Once the eigenstate energy of GaSb is higher than in InAs, the system forms a SMI, and the electron transport is enabled as labelled in Figure 3.3.1.1. The carriers are supplied from the SMI to the recombination regions via electron and hole injector. The quasi-Fermi levels are assumed to be equal on both sides of the SMI. Electrons tunnel through electron wells of the electron injector to the recombination region of the next cascade stage. The widths of QWs of the electron injector are increasing from the SMI to the recombination region, so that the ground states of the QWs couple at applied bias. The transport of holes is carried via the hole injector towards the recombination region. Holes injected to the GaInSb well of the recombination region effectively manifest as a transport of electrons from the GaInSb to lower energies in GaSb of the hole injector, further tunnelling through the SMI and the electron

injector to the next recombination region. The relation between the quasi-Fermi levels of the adjacent cascade stages has to satisfy the following:

$$E_{F_i} - E_{F_{i+1}} \geq \hbar\omega \geq E_g \quad (3.2.1)$$

where E_g is the energy separation between electron and hole ground states in the recombination region. It is necessary in order to generate sufficient gain to compensate the photon loss. This waterfall configuration of band structure enables multiple photon generation for a single electron-hole pair. The number of photons is multiplied by the number of cascade stages of the active region.

Figure 3.3.1.1. Band structure of the active region of a state-of-the-art ICL. The recombination of carriers occurs in the W-shaped QW region. The semi-metallic interface (SMI) enables tunnelling of electrons from the top of the valence band in GaSb to the conduction band of InAs. The transports of electrons and holes through the respective injectors are labelled.

Even though, with more stages, the threshold for lasing in terms of carrier concentration and hence current density would be reduced, this also has a major drawback. The excessive cascading results in a significant increase of the open circuit voltage, and consequently the threshold voltage and threshold power. This further leads to high Joule losses limiting the laser performance, especially in cw operation. The optimal number of cascade stages though, is determined by a “rule of thumb” based on the emission wavelength. The rule states that

expected open-circuit voltage should be below 2 V based on state-of-the-art devices [31], [79], [80], [81], [82]. As mentioned before, ICLs have the lowest threshold current densities in the wavelength range 3-7 μm . The lowest threshold current densities are measured around the “sweet spot” of $\lambda \approx 3.5 \mu\text{m}$ [31], [56]. At shorter wavelength, the InAs layers of electron injectors are potentially not transparent and could lead to absorption losses, increasing the threshold current. Conversely at longer wavelengths, thicker layers of the recombination region are needed, leading to reduction of the wavefunction overlap. In addition, the FCA quadratically increases with wavelength. Both effects cause an increase of the threshold current. Figure 3.3.1.2 [83] presents an overview of state-of-the-art threshold current densities of the three laser species: common laser diodes, ICLs and QCLs. It is shown that in the wavelengths of the range 3-7 μm ICLs outperform the other two.

Figure 3.3.1.2. State-of-the-art threshold current densities of different lasers in mid-infrared wavelength range. The data is taken from the reference [83].

3.3.2. W-shaped recombination region

Commonly used laser diodes with an active region based on type-I QW are limited by the band gap material of the well where the recombination occurs. Unlike standard laser diodes, recombination region of an ICL is composed of a hole GaInSb QW sandwiched between electron InAs QW, assembling a W-shaped form of the band edges. The broken band alignment between InAs and GaInSb enables a tuning of the emission wavelength dominated by confinement via the design of different QW thicknesses [84]. Nevertheless, InAs layers are significantly narrower than equivalent type I QW of the same emission wavelength. This increases sensitivity of the wavelength on the fluctuation of layer thicknesses in experimental realization, especially if the layer interfaces are not abrupt. The recombination region employs two InAs layers instead of just one, for the sake of higher wavefunction overlap. In a single pair of InAs/GaInSb, the electron and hole wavefunction would be spatially delocalized and the wavefunction overlap is significantly lower. A symmetrical W-shaped QW designed to emit at 3.5 μm is displayed in Figure 3.3.2. The structure is composed of **AlSb/InAs/Ga_{0.6}In_{0.4}Sb/InAs/AlSb** of thicknesses

(2.5/1.5/3.0/1.5/1.5) nm. The mole fraction ratio (x) of $\text{Ga}_{1-x}\text{In}_x\text{Sb}$ is commonly under 50 % [31], [41], due to high compressive strain. Symmetrical wells are desirable for unbiased measurements, for example when optimizing the intensity of photoluminescence (PL). However, in a recombination region of ICL, one InAs well is designed to be slightly thinner to compensate for the Stark-shift and hence prevent a potential decoupling of the electron wavefunctions of the two InAs QWs.

Figure 3.3.2. Band structure of the optical recombination region of the ICL emitting at the “sweet spot” wavelength of 3.5 μm . The GaInSb QW is stacked in between two electron InAs QWs forming a W-shaped region. The first electron and hole states are labeled as E1 and HH1, respectively. The wavefunction overlap is 0.640.

3.3.3. Injector regions

Electron and hole injector regions are implemented in the active region of ICLs to enable spatial localization of carriers and to enable their conduction throughout the structure. The high conduction band edge of GaSb of the hole injector prevents tunnelling through AISb barrier from the W-shaped QW to the adjacent wells and hence it forces the electron transport through the semi-metallic interface (SMI) between the hole and electron injector, after the optical transition and electron tunnelling from the hole QW of the W-shaped QW to GaSb QW of hole injector. Thicknesses of GaSb QW of the hole injector are designed so that their ground states couple under bias. To concentrate holes in the GaInSb well of the W-shaped QW region, hole energy in the hole injector is approximately 100 meV below the energy in the recombination region [31].

Analogously, low valence band edge of InAs layers of the electron injector act as a barrier for holes from the recombination region. For the sake of preventing the diagonal recombination, at SMI, the AISb barrier is thicker (2.5 nm) than elsewhere (1.2 nm). From the gain point of view,

short injector region is desirable for minimizing the optical absorption losses [31], [85]. However, the first injector well should be reasonably thick so that sufficient charge accumulates from the SMI. The band structure in Figure 3.3.1.1. is shown for the case where the energy corresponding to a voltage drop of one stage is equal to the transition energy of the emission ($E_{e1}-E_{e2}= hc/\lambda$). The first InAs well is sufficiently thick so that its ground state is below the state in the hole injector. The last well is thin enough so that its ground state is significantly (~ 100 meV) above the upper laser level of the next recombination region (E_{e2}). Thicknesses of remaining wells are gradually decreasing to create an energy staircase from the SMI to the state e_2 .

However, threshold of lasing operation is met at a higher electrical field, so that the electron state of the next recombination region is not aligned, but below the hole state of the previous recombination region ($E_{e2} < E_{h1}$). A higher electrical field aligns the ground states in the InAs QW of the electron injector by forming a miniband by bending their band edges, which enables the electron transport. Valence band edges of the hole injectors are energetically lower than the band edge of the GaInSb in the W-shaped QW region, even at zero bias. This alignment favors hole population of the recombination region over the hole injector. On the opposite, the band edges of electron injector bend if the sufficient bias is provided, leading to that most electrons occupy states in the electron injector, rather than in the next W-shaped QW recombination region. Disbalance of carrier densities in the W-shaped QW region leads to increase of Auger recombination rate. This problem was successfully addressed by increasing doping electron wells of the electron injector from $\sim 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ to $\sim 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ [86]. By doping of electron injector wells, electron concentration in the recombination region increases, while the hole concentration slightly decreases. The carrier rebalancing is met when the concentrations are equal. The QW at the SMI is left undoped for avoiding any potential recombination with the hole injector QW. It was noted that the threshold current densities substantially improved when the electron and hole densities became approximately equal, and the electron injector doping has become a standard in the ICL designs ever since.

3.3.4. Claddings

State-of-the-art ICL waveguides are 1.5-3.3 μm thick and are composed of InAs/AlSb SLs [31], [56], [87]. The waveguide ensures confinement of the optical mode to the active region and separates the active region from the (lossy) metallic contacts and highly doped substrate. The high refractive index of the substrate ($n_{r-\text{GaSb}} = 3.71$) further requires a low refractive index of the waveguide [30], [31], [45]. In addition to the optical properties, efficient dissipation of heat away from the active region is needed for the waveguide. Therefore, the necessary requirements for cladding material are a refractive index lower than the average of the active region ($n_r \approx 3.45$) [30], high carrier mobility, high thermal conductivity, and lattice-matched or strain compensated growth on the GaSb substrate. The refractive index of the AlSb/InAs SL is $n_r = 3.39$ [32], [88], which is just slightly lower than the refractive index of the active region. The AlSb and InAs layers can be grown strain compensated as their lattice constants are slightly longer and slightly shorter than the lattice of GaSb substrate (6.1 Å family). To make carrier transport possible, InAs layers of the claddings are n-type doped, but to minimize optical losses

the doping levels are gradually decreasing from the buffer and cap ($\sim 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) towards the vicinity of the active region ($\sim 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$). In addition to claddings, in 2005 a pair of bulk SCLs was introduced to improve the optical confinement in the active region [89]. Since then, it has been commonly used as it contributes to a substantial increase of the optical confinement in the active region [90]. In addition, a portion of the optical mode shifts from the claddings of high loss to SCLs. In that regard, SCLs are moderately doped ($\sim 5 \cdot 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) to mitigate the optical losses. However, as suggested in reference [30], with further increase of SCLs thickness, confinement in the active region reduces on the expense of confinement in SCLs. NRL [31] reports used thicknesses for SCLs of 500 nm for 5 stages ICL and 700 nm for 7 stages SCL, whereas an earlier report [91] implies the optimal SCL thickness should linearly scale with emission wavelength. The layout of an ICL structure is presented in Figure 3.2.4. (a). The five stages active region is designed to emit at $3.5 \mu\text{m}$. The thicknesses of the bottom and top cladding are 3.3 and $2.0 \mu\text{m}$ respectively. The thickness of SCLs is 350 nm . Figure 3.2.4 (b) depicts profiles of the refractive indices and the simulated optical mode along the growth direction (x) of the ICL. In addition, it also presents the distribution of the optical confinement throughout the layer species. Confinement factor of layer “ i ” can be quantified as:

$$\Gamma_i = \frac{\int_{x_{i-MIN}}^{x_{i-MAX}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |E(x, y, z)|^2 dx dy dz}{\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |E(x, y, z)|^2 dx dy dz} \quad (3.3.4)$$

where $E(y, z)$ is electrical field of the emitted light in the lateral, in-plane directions y and z .

Figure 3.3.4. (a) The structure layout of the state-of-the-art ICL of 5 cascade stages emitting at $3.5 \mu\text{m}$. (b) The profiles of refractive indices and optical mode in the ICL structure with respective confinement factors of the different layers.

Although the bottom tail of the optical mode is not visible below $x = -2.5 \mu\text{m}$, as a “rule of thumb” it was shown that mode intensity ratio of tail and the maximum needs to be below 10^{-}

⁶, to prevent absorption from the substrate. The optical mode simulation was carried out by university-made software LASIM featuring a Helmholtz equation solver.

3.3.5. Transition layers

In order to enable efficient carrier transport through the layers with a significant offset in band edge energies, transition layers (TLs) are necessary to be implemented [31], [56]. TLs are a kind of SL composed of AlSb barriers and InAs QWs. Thicknesses of the InAs QW in the TLs are designed so that their ground states are gradually varying between the two energies that the TLs are connecting. Figure 3.3.5.1. displays the band structure profiles of the GaSb-based ICL for transitions from the bottom SCL to the active region (in panel (a)) and from the active region to the top SCL (in panel (b)). In the first TL, the thickness of InAs layers gradually increase from 1.2 nm to 1.6 nm to mitigate the 330 meV band offset, whereas in the second TL, thicknesses gradually reduce from 2.0 to 1.1 nm to mitigate the band offset of -30 meV. The InAs QW of TLs are n-type doped with Si to the same level as the adjacent active regions, $N = 5 \cdot 10^{18} \text{cm}^{-3}$. Figure 3.3.5.2. presents the band structures of the transition from the bottom cladding to the bottom SCL (in panel (a)) and from the top cladding to the top SCL (in panel (b)). The InAs QW of TLs are n-type doped with Si to the same level as the adjacent cladding layers, $N = 1 \cdot 10^{17} \text{cm}^{-3}$. The bridged band offset in the first case is 180 meV, while in the second, it is 460 meV. The overall offset at the field $E = 62 \text{ V/cm}$ is therefore

$$\Delta E_{TL} = (330 - 30 + 180 + 440) \text{ meV} = 940 \text{ meV} \quad (3.3.5.1)$$

Considering the emission energy of 340 meV, the open circuit voltage can be estimated as

$$V_{oc} = 5 \cdot 0.34 \frac{\text{eV}}{e} + 0.94 \frac{\text{eV}}{e} = 2.64 \text{ V} \quad (3.3.5.2)$$

Figure 3.3.5.1. (a) Band structure of TL between the bottom SCL and the active region (AR) (b) Band structure of the TL between the active region and the top SCL.

Figure 3.3.5.2. (a) Band structure of TL between the bottom SL cladding and the bottom SCL (b) Band structure of the TL between the top SCL and the top SL cladding.

4. Growth and characterization of ICLs

State-of-the-art ICLs are based on III-V materials that are commonly epitaxially grown. In this chapter, the epitaxial growth, characterization and processing of ICLs as well as structures for the necessary calibrations will be discussed.

4.1. Molecular Beam Epitaxy

In this section, the principles of molecular beam epitaxy will be elaborated. Additionally, a detailed description of the epitaxial system used in this work will be provided.

4.1.1. Epitaxial growth of III-V structures

All samples in this work were grown by molecular beam epitaxy (MBE) [92], [93]. This technique enables deposition of layers with atomic resolution. One of the main constraints for the semiconductor growth is the material of the substrate. Commonly used substrates for III-V ICL structures are GaSb and InAs. If the lattice constant of the substrate is larger than the lattice constant of the grown material (see Figure 4.1.1), the material stretches laterally and therefore

Figure 4.1.1. (a) Schematic of a tensile strained crystal grown on the substrate of a larger lattice constant. The grown material gets compressed along the vertical direction to keep the constant volume. (b) Schematic of a compressively strained crystal grown on the substrate of a smaller lattice constant. The grown crystal gets stretched along the vertical direction.

compresses vertically maintaining the same volume. Similarly, if the substrate material has a smaller lattice constant than the grown material, the material gets compressed laterally and it stretches in the vertical direction. Tensile and compressive strain effectively reduce and increase the material bandgap [52], respectively, but also contribute to degradation of the quality of the material through linear defects and hence downgrade the electro-optical properties. This is the reason why the lattice-matched or strain-compensated growth is of great importance for the exclusions of dislocations. During growth, processes such as interdiffusion, migration and desorption can also occur. Apart from strain, the quality of the growth is largely determined by the substrate temperature and the ratio between fluxes of group III and group V materials. Low temperature can shrink the migration length of the atoms, leading to local growth of islands instead of uniform layers. Too high temperature can cause too many atoms to desorb from the surface, disabling the crystalline growth. Due to high adhesion coefficient and since the group III materials are provided less than group V materials, the group III materials mostly determine the rate of growth of III-V compounds. The flux of group V though determines the quality of the growth. If the group V is too low, the binary can be grown unsaturated with group V which can lead to high defect “metallic” surface. Too high flux of group V material can potentially shorten the migration length and consequently contribute to roughness of the surface.

4.1.2. Eiko system

The *Eiko EV 100S* MBE was used for the epitaxial growth of heterostructures of this work and a schematic of the system is presented in figure 4.1.2.1. The system is composed of two chambers: main chamber and loadlock chamber. In one growth run, up to three samples can be grown, as the manipulator in the loadlock chamber supports three slots for sample holders and one slot for the dummy-holder during growth. One of the three holders is equipped with a heater for outgassing water and oxides. Sample that is next in line for growth gets outgassed in the loadlock chamber for approximately two hours at 300 °C, prior to transfer to the main chamber. The pressure in the loadlock is maintained low by a combination of turbomolecular and a roughing pump attached to it. The roughing pump enables pressure of $5 \cdot 10^{-3}$ mbar, whereas turbomolecular pump reduces it further to $1 \cdot 10^{-8}$ Torr (mbar). The pressure is monitored by ultra-high vacuum (UHV) pressure gauge. When the samples are transferred to the loadlock after the growth, in order to open the loadlock window for the unloading, the pumps need to be turned off and the atmospheric pressure needs to be established. For this purpose, a valve to an external nitrogen line attached to the loadlock is opened. Nitrogen is used, since it is a non-reactive gas.

The main chamber is evacuated by ion getter pumps, hence during growth the pressure becomes as low as $1 \cdot 10^{-9}$ mbar. The shrouds of the main chamber are cooled down by liquid nitrogen to maintain the UHV during growth, as the gases stick to the coldest surfaces and provide a sufficient mean free path to the molecules from effusion cells. The manipulator in the main chamber consists of one sample holder that is rotated around vertical axis during growth, for uniform epitaxy of the material over the wafer. An additional UHV pressure gauge is mounted beside the sample holder for the purpose of beam flux monitoring (BFM). The BFM stands for measurement of fluxes coming out of every effusion cell, prior to growth. In this way, the

fractional ratios of group III and group V elements in ternary and quaternary compounds can be estimated prior to calibration. The manipulator can also be rotated around its horizontal axis to reach three specific positions: the transfer position, aligned with the load-lock chamber; the growth position, directed downward toward the effusion cells; and the BFM (beam flux monitoring) position, where the fluxes are aligned to produce the maximum signal on the BFM gauge.

Figure 4.1.2.1. Schematic of the used Eiko EV 100 S MBE system. The main chamber is equipped with two In cells, one Ga, one Al, one Be, one dual Si-GaTe cell, and two cracker cells – As and Sb.

The MBE system is equipped with effusion cells with group III elements (Al, Ga, In), two cells of group V materials with valved crackers (As, Sb) and Be, Si and GaTe-cells used as dopants. Materials of the cells are heated up by filaments around the containing crucibles and the temperatures are controlled by the thermocouples. Cells are opened and closed by shutters controlled by pneumatic air lines. Fluxes of group V are additionally controlled by needle valves attached to electromotors. During growth, the substrate temperature is monitored using both a thermocouple and a pyrometer mounted at the viewport directly beneath the substrate holder. As a non-contact method, the pyrometer measurement accounts not only for the thermal radiation from the substrate holder itself but also for contributions from surrounding effusion cells, which can influence both the substrate temperature and the pyrometer reading. Since there is no universally accepted method for accurately determining the substrate temperature, either the pyrometer or the thermocouple can be used, however it is important to consistently use the selected method—either the pyrometer or the thermocouple—to ensure fair and reliable comparison across growth conditions. Once the samples are grown in the main chamber, they

are transferred to the loadlock chamber by a rod with a magnetic core, to be unloaded from the system and replaced with new wafers for the next growth run.

Outside of the growth campaign, the MBE system can be opened for maintenance; either for refilling materials or fixing an inner part of the system externally. After the opening, the temperatures of the cells are then brought down to the ambient temperature. If the system was exposed to the atmospheric conditions during the opening, the chamber needs to be thermally isolated and then gradually heated up to 200 °C (“baked”).

The goal is to desorb the unwanted gasses, such as water vapour and oxides inside the chamber, to reestablish the UHV conditions that existed prior to the opening. The pressure of individual gasses inside the system is monitored by a residual gas analyser (RGA), attached to the chamber externally. It is a quadrupole mass analyser whose structure will be discussed later in this chapter. The output is the background pressure of a particular gas identified by its atomic (molecular) mass. Figure 4.1.2.2 depicts an example of distribution of background pressure of the gasses present in the main chamber after the bakeout. Once the overall pressure in the chamber is in the range of 10^{-12} - 10^{-10} Torr and the pressures can no longer be reduced by pumping, the baking is finished, and the heat isolation (aluminium box and foil) is removed. The cell filaments are then heated up to the usual (standby) temperatures. When the temperatures are raised up and stable, some material is coming out of the cells and the pressure in the chamber is increased to the operational 10^{-8} Torr, which reduces to 10^{-9} Torr, during growth, once the chamber walls are cooled down by liquid nitrogen. The first growth campaigns after the opening are used for calibration of the growth rates, doping concentrations and flux ratios of group V elements.

Figure 4.1.2.2. Background pressures of gasses present in the MBE chamber with respect to their corresponding molecular masses.

4.2. Calibration of growth parameters for growth of an ICL

Prior to the growth of an ICL, a calibration of different growth parameters is crucial for the respective purposes: growth rates (layer thicknesses), fluxes of group V elements (minimizing

strain) and doping concentrations (doping). In this section, these calibrations will be clarified separately.

4.2.1. Calibration of growth rates and strain

To grow high performance ICLs, the accuracy of optimized design parameters such as layer thicknesses and doping levels is necessary. Additionally, it is important to have a high crystal quality, hence, to minimize the strain and to provide sufficient flux of group V elements to the crystal lattice. In the state-of-the-art ICLs, there are three species of binaries present in its structure: InAs, AlSb and GaSb. The most common way to calibrate growth rates and strain is via measurement of high-resolution X-ray diffraction (HR-XRD) spectra of periodic structures. X-rays of the $Cu_{K\alpha 1}$ –line ($\lambda = 0.1506$ nm) are diffracted by the crystal planes of the grown material and scanned by a detector. A diffraction rocking curve is produced by simultaneously varying the incident angle (ω) of X-rays on crystal planes of spacing d , and the angular position of the detector towards the direction of incident ray (2θ). A constructive interference of X-rays occurs at incident angle ω that satisfies the Bragg equation:

$$d \cdot \sin(\omega - 2\theta) = n\lambda \quad (4.2.1.1)$$

where n is a diffraction order (integer number). The full-width-half-maximum (FWHM) of the fringe indicating a bulk layer gets narrower with thicker layer. As the substrate is by far the thickest layer of the structure (600 μm), its peak is the narrowest and with the most prominent intensity. Commonly employed cladding material in GaSb-based ICLs is InAs/AlSb SL. The thickness of InAs is 2.43 nm (8 ML), whereas the thickness of 2.3 nm of AlSb is chosen to compensate the lattice mismatch of one SL period:

$$d_{InAs} \cdot \frac{a_{GaSb} - a_{InAs}}{a_{GaSb}} = d_{AlSb} \cdot \frac{a_{AlSb} - a_{GaSb}}{a_{GaSb}} \quad (4.2.1.2)$$

where a_{InAs} , a_{GaSb} and a_{AlSb} are corresponding lattice constants. Cladding layers are a few micrometers thick; therefore, it is crucial to grow them strain-compensated on GaSb substrate. The major role in determining the strain in SLs is the balance of binary species at interfaces [94]. At the interface of InAs and AlSb layers, some arsenic atoms will diffuse to AlSb while some antimony atoms will diffuse to InAs, forming monolayers of AlAs/InSb in between, as depicted in Figure 4.2.1.1.

Figure 4.2.1.1. Interface layers between InAs and AlSb layers. If AlAs is a dominant kind of interface, the strain is gauged to tensile, whereas if InSb type is dominant, the strain is gauged to compressive.

With higher ratio of arsenic to antimony flux, applied in growth of InAs layers, the interfacial layers gauge towards AIAs kind of interface, involving tensile strain, whereas with lower ratio, it gauges to InSb, leading to compressive strain. To calibrate both layer thicknesses and the strain, the sample displayed in Figure 4.2.1.2 (a) is grown. It consists of two SLs of 30 periods, composed of 2.43 nm InAs/2.3 nm AISb and 3.43 nm InAs/2.3 nm and bulk layer of GaSb spaced in between to separate the SLs and to enable extracting growth rate of GaSb from the scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image of the sample. Both SLs are grown at substrate temperature of 450 °C. In Figure 4.2.1.2 (b), a diffractogram of such calibration sample is presented. Two SL patterns are overlaying with the shift corresponding to different period. The constructive interference of X-rays produces high intensity reflex peaks of different orders; zeroth closest to the substrate peaks ($\omega=2\theta$) and higher order peaks distributed symmetrically to the zeroth order according to eq 5.2.1.1. Period of a SL is calculated by

$$P = \frac{\lambda}{2\Delta\omega \cdot \cos(\omega_{AVG})} \quad (4.2.1.3)$$

where $\Delta\omega$ is the spacing between two adjacent SL reflexes and ω_{AVG} their average position.

Figure 4.2.1.2. (a) Structure layout of the sample for calibration of growth rates and strain in claddings (b) X-ray diffractogram of 2.43 nm InAs/2.3 nm AISb and 3.43 nm InAs/2.3 nm AISb SLs. The reflexes of 0th to 3rd order are labelled.

The grown periods of SLs are obtained from periods of SLs averaged over all detectable XRD reflexes. Fractional growth rate (FGR) is the percentage of the desired growth rate (< 1 for undergrown and >1 for overgrown layers). The FGRs of InAs and AISb are then extracted as follows:

$$FGR_{InAs} = \frac{d_{SL2-GROWN} - d_{SL1-GROWN}}{d_{SL2-PLANNED} - d_{SL1-PLANNED}} = \frac{d_{SL2-GROWN} - d_{SL1-GROWN}}{5.73 \text{ nm} - 4.73 \text{ nm}} \quad (4.2.1.4)$$

$$FGR_{AISb} = \frac{d_{SL1-GROWN} - FGR_{InAs} \cdot d_{InAs-PLANNED}}{d_{AISb-PLANNED}} = \frac{d_{SL1-GROWN} - FGR_{InAs} \cdot 2.43 \text{ nm}}{2.3 \text{ nm}} \quad (4.2.1.5)$$

where d_{InAs} and d_{AISb} are thicknesses of the InAs, AISb layers and d_{SL1} and d_{SL2} are periods of shorter and longer SLs, respectively.

The zeroth order peak of the SL of shorter period is overlaying with the GaSb substrate peak, while the longer SL has its zeroth order on the side, indicating tensile strain coming from the longer InAs layer in its structure. If the zeroth order peak of the shorter SL was shifted towards “tensile side” (right) of the substrate peak, it would be a consequence of too high arsenic to antimony flux ratio; if it was on the “compressive side” (left), it would imply the ratio is too low.

4.2.2. Calibration of composition ratios of group V elements

For the growth of ternary and quaternary compounds, it is important to have correct layer thicknesses but also the right mole fraction ratios. In ternaries with two group III elements, the fraction ratio is set by choosing growth rates of the containing binaries in such proportion. However, for compounds containing two group V elements, calibration of growth rates is not sufficient. Calibration of $\text{InAs}_{0.915}\text{Sb}_{0.085}$ ternary lattice-matched to GaSb is needed for growth of hybrid-based claddings that will be introduced in the next chapters. In Figure 4.2.2.1. (a) the layout of the sample for calibration is depicted. To calibrate arsenic to antimony ratio, a sample composed of two 200 nm thick layers of InAsSb with the same arsenic flux, but different antimony fluxes is grown. In Figure 4.2.2.1. (b) the X-ray diffraction spectrum of the sample is presented. The arsenic to antimony composition is determined by the position of the corresponding fringe peaks to the GaSb-substrate peak. In the subplot, the fraction ratio of Sb is presented for two applied antimony fluxes at valve openings of 14 and 18 milinch. The obtained lattice mismatches are 910 ppm and 2680 ppm corresponding to Sb fraction ratios of 9.9 % and 12.0 %. From the linear fitting, the valve opening for lattice matching to GaSb substrate was 11.3 milinch.

Figure 4.2.2.1. (a) Structure layout of the sample for calibration of group V fraction ratios in a ternary compound. (b) X-ray diffractogram of two InAsSb layers with the same arsenic, but different antimony fluxes applied. The layer with smaller antimony flux is less compressively strained on GaSb-substrate.

In the next calibration run, and the lattice matching to GaSb was obtained. In the Figure 4.2.2.2, the structure layout and the diffractogram of the final calibration sample are depicted.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.2.2.2. (a) Structure layout of the final calibration sample for group V fraction ratios in a ternary compound. (b) X-ray diffractogram of final calibration sample featuring one InAsSb layer with the ratio of group V elements corresponding to lattice matching to the GaSb-substrate.

Similarly to ternaries, quaternary layers are also employed in cladding design of ICLs. For calibration of $\text{Al}_{0,85}\text{Ga}_{0,15}\text{As}_{0,07}\text{Sb}_{0,93}$ lattice-matched to GaSb-substrate, a slightly different approach is used.

In Figure 4.2.2.3 (a) a layout of calibration sample for quaternary layers is shown. A bulk layer of AlGaSb is grown to distinguish influences on strain coming from ratio of fluxes of group III elements from the ratio of fluxes of group V elements. In other words, AlGaSb layer is present to confirm accuracy of the previously calibrated growth rates of the two constituting binaries, so that their ratio is split 85 % - 15 %. In the remaining two AlGaAsSb layers, antimony flux is kept the same, and arsenic flux is different, to ensure at least two calibration points necessary for the fitting. In Figure 4.2.2.3 (b) the X-ray diffractogram of the sample is presented with labeled ternary AlGaSb and quaternary AlGaAsSb fringe peaks. The complete absence of arsenic involves a high compressive strain showing lattice mismatch of 6125 ppm, hence AlGaSb layer was grown thinner than AlGaAsSb layers. The two quaternary layers were grown tensile strained with arsenic fluxes corresponding to valve openings of 20 and 25 milinch that resulted in lattice mismatch of 180 ppm and 785 ppm respectively. With smaller fraction ratio of arsenic, the tensile strain reduces. The obtained fraction ratios of As in AlGaAsSb extracted from the lattice mismatches are 7.4 % and 8.2 %. The linear fit depicted in the subplot shows that the lattice matching, which is met for the arsenic fraction ratio of 7 %, corresponds to arsenic valve opening of 17.5 milinch.

Although the valve opening (commonly referred to as valve diameter) is not a direct measure of flux, it still serves as a practical reference for comparing group V flux ratios when the BFM

system is not operational.

Figure 4.2.2.3. (a) Structure layout of the sample for calibration of group V fraction ratios in a quaternary compound. (b) X-ray diffractogram of one AlGaSb layer and two AlGaAsSb layers with the same antimony, but different arsenic fluxes applied. The layer with smaller arsenic flux is less tensile strained on GaSb-substrate.

In the next calibration run, the lattice matching was obtained. The layer structure and the corresponding diffractogram of the sample for the final calibration run are presented in Figure 4.2.2.4 (a) and (b).

Figure 4.2.2.4. (a) Structure layout of the sample for calibration of group V fraction ratios in a quaternary compound. (b) X-ray diffractogram of one AlGaSb layer with the desired flux ratio of group III elements and one AlGaAsSb layer with the flux ratios of group V elements corresponding to lattice matching to GaSb-substrate.

4.2.3. Calibration of doping and carrier concentrations

To enable conduction of carriers through the active region of ICL, claddings are n-type doped, whereas active region is n-type doped for the sake of suppression of Auger recombination as explained in the chapter 3.3.3. State-of-the-art doping level in InAs layers of SL-based claddings gradually varies from $1 \cdot 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ to $1 \cdot 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ whereas of plasmon-enhanced claddings are in the range of 10^{19} cm^{-3} . Injector wells in the active region are typically n-type doped with $4 \cdot 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ [31], [80]. To successfully estimate the doping levels, Secondary Ion Mass Spectrometry (SIMS) technique is used. The output is concentration of atoms along the growth direction.

SIMS is a destructive technique in which a beam of primary ions is sputtering the surface of the specimen, whereas the beam of ejected, secondary ions get detected and analysed at the output. Figure 4.2.3.1. presents a schematic of the structure of the spectrometer. It is composed of primary ion source, mass analyser and a detector in a high vacuum environment with pressures below 10^{-6} Torr. The high vacuum is needed to prevent collisions of secondary ions with the gases on the path to the detector. There are three species of ion guns used. In gaseous source ions are generated from ionization of noble gasses (Ar^+ , Xe^+), oxygen (O_2^+) or fullerene (C_{60}^+) [95]. A second type is the surface ionization source, where ions are created by caesium evaporation through tungsten plug. Its ion beam is of a high purity and low energy spread ($<50 \text{ meV}$). The third type, the liquid metal ion gun (LMIG) is the source used for the doping calibration of ICLs. The ions are emitted from a liquid metal covering the tungsten tip under a strong electric field. The metals commonly employed are Ga, In, Au and Bi [95].

Figure 4.2.3.1. Schematic of structure of SIMS. It is composed of the ion source, mass analyser and a detector.

LMIG source features moderate intensity but a highly focused beam (5 nm spot). The mass analyser is the central part of the spectrometer that separates the secondary ions by their mass-to-charge ratio. There are three species of mass analysers. Depending on the type, analysers can employ electric or magnetic field for classification of ions. The first type is a sector field mass spectrometer which uses a combination of the two fields. Its geometry is displayed in Figure 4.2.3.1. Ions, accelerated and focused by electrical field, are directed to a circular tube under orthogonal magnetic field. At the entrance to mass analyser, all ions have the same energies, but different masses correspond to different velocities. From the

equilibrium of Lorentz and centripetal force (eq. 4.2.3.1), and from the energy conservation law (eq. 4.2.3.2), the mass to charge ratio relates to the corresponding combination of electric and magnetic field (eq. 4.2.3.3) as it follows:

$$F_{Lorentz} = ZevB = F_{centripetal} = \frac{mv^2}{r} \quad (4.2.3.1)$$

$$ZeV = \frac{mv^2}{2} \quad (4.2.3.2)$$

$$\frac{m}{Z} = \frac{eB^2r^2}{2V} \quad (4.2.3.3)$$

The second type, quadruple analyser uses four rods with RF and DC voltages creating a dynamic electric field. The m/Z ratio is filtered based on stability of the trajectory determined by tuning the RF and DC voltages [95]. Other ions oscillate out of phase and become lost.

The third type of the analyser, time of flight (TOF) mass analyser, where ions are accelerated by electrical field, prior to entering a straight flight tube. By measuring time ion reaches the detector at the end of the tube, the mass to charge ratio can be obtained:

$$T_f = \frac{L}{v} = L \sqrt{\frac{1}{2V}} \sqrt{\frac{m}{Z}} \quad (4.2.3.4)$$

Since the tube length is fixed, not all the ions can be detected. To the back of the tube, a series of ring electrodes is attached, forming a reflection that reflects ions of different velocities at different positions in the opposite direction. In addition, resolution of the measurement of the ions with the same m/Z ratio is also increased.

Finally, the detector of the spectrometer is basically a Faraday cup, that discharges the collected ions on its inner shell and transfers them to the outer walls. Usually, it is combined with a dynode to create an avalanche effect, as a multiplier of the signal. The used type of analyser is TOF.

In Figure 4.2.3.2 (a) the structure layout of the calibration sample grown on InAs-substrate is displayed. Four 200 nm thick InAs layers n-type doped with silicon atoms of different fluxes are grown. The target concentrations are $1 \cdot 10^{17} - 1 \cdot 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ (in SL claddings), $4 \cdot 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ (in active region) and $1 \cdot 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ (in plasmon-enhanced claddings). First and the last 10 nm of each layer is grown undoped to provide enough time to dopant cell to heat up to every consecutive temperature corresponding to desired target values of doping concentrations, without introducing a growth interruption. The InAs layers are separated by 10 nm AlSb barriers to provide additional time for the dopant cell to ramp up, and to form an interface contrast in the SEM image so that growth rate of InAs could be checked. It is important to point out that when calibrating temperature of effusion cells with dopant materials, it is crucial to take to account the correct growth rate. At the same cell temperature, the doping concentration will be higher at lower growth rates, as more dopant atoms manage to incorporate in the lattice per unit time.

Figure 4.2.3.2. (a) Layout structure of the sample consisting of four n-type doped 200 nm thick layers, for calibration of doping concentration of doped InAs-layers of the ICL. (b) Doping concentration of the calibration sample measured by SIMS.

In Figure 4.2.3.2. (b) the SIMS profile of the sample is depicted. The obtained averaged doping concentrations indicated in the figure are merely diverging from the target values for the middle two temperatures, 840.4 °C and 887.2 °C. At the temperature of 762.2 °C, the concentration was higher than expected, hence the cell temperature was to be reduced as indicated by the arrow. Conversely, at the temperature of 918.2 °C, the concentration was lower than targeted, thus the temperature was to be increased. In Figure 4.2.3.3. dependences of measured and targeted Si concentrations on the temperature of the Si cell are shown. In practice, the measured concentrations are scaled to growth rate of 1000 nm/h. Then, the slope and y-axis cut are extracted from the linear fit of the concentration dependence on the temperature of Si cell. This way, for every growth rate and target doping concentration, the corresponding cell temperature can be obtained. Unlike silicon, which can replace either of group III (p-type doping) or group V atoms (n-type doping), Te strictly replaces the group V element. Similarly to the calibration of Si-doping of InAs layers, for calibration of Te-doping of GaSb layers is carried out by growing three GaSb layers with different doping concentrations.

Figure 4.2.3.3. Measured and targeted Si doping concentrations obtained for the respective temperatures of the Si cell. The calibrated temperatures of the cells corresponding to the desired

concentrations are indicated by ends of the arrows. For the middle two cell temperatures, discrepancy from the targeted concentrations is negligible.

A relative calibration based on comparison to the dominant group V concentration in the host semiconductor (as advised by our technician) was applied. Although this method provides only an approximate estimation of the absolute dopant concentration, the SIMS measurements were referenced against known doping concentrations previously established by an independent photoreflectance characterisation. For $\text{InAs}_{0.915}\text{Sb}_{0.085}$ - based plasmon-enhanced claddings in ICLs grown on GaSb substrates, an additional calibration step is needed to cross-check the obtained carrier density of $9.6 \cdot 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ in InAs layer. The additional calibration sample, presented in Figure 4.2.3.4 (a), consists of 500 nm highly doped $\text{InAs}_{0.915}\text{Sb}_{0.085}$ layer on an undoped GaSb substrate. In Figure 4.2.3.4. (b), its ion mass spectrum shows slightly higher concentration of $1.16 \cdot 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. The higher concentration suggests a higher diffusivity of antimony in comparison to arsenic, as more silicon atoms substitute atoms of the lattice. However, this difference is insignificant in terms of resulting refractive index as it will be shown in the following chapter.

Figure 4.2.3.4. (a) Layout of highly doped 500 nm bulk $\text{InAs}_{0.915}\text{Sb}_{0.085}$ for calibration of doping density in plasmon-enhanced claddings. (b) Density of dopant silicon atoms in highly doped bulk $\text{InAs}_{0.915}\text{Sb}_{0.085}$ sample.

Finally, to measure the carrier density instead of concentration of donor atoms, a photoreflectance measurement is carried out by using Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR). The sample with 500 nm thick film of $\text{InAs}_{0.915}\text{Sb}_{0.085}$ is illuminated by infrared source. The photoreflectance spectra is presented in Figure 4.2.3.5. Plasmon resonance peak is localized around 34.12 THz, hence measured plasmonic cut-off wavelength is $\lambda_p = 8.785 \mu\text{m}$. To extract the carrier density, energy dispersion of the material is needed to be known, hence it is calculated by $8 \cdot k \cdot p$ and depicted in Figure 4.2.3.6. A schematic of an iterative method for obtaining the carrier density presented in Figure 4.2.3.7. In the first step, the carrier density is assumed, around the expected value. Subsequently, from the k-vector corresponding to Fermi energy in bulk (eq. 1), and the slope of energy dispersion, the corresponding effective mass at such k-vector is determined (eq. 2). From the obtained effective mass and measured plasmonic cut-off frequency, carrier density is calculated according to eq. 3. If the result is equal to assumed value, the carrier density is determined, otherwise, a new assumption of carrier density is made and the procedure repeats.

Figure 4.2.3.5. Photoreflectance spectra of bulk $\text{InAs}_{0.915}\text{Sb}_{0.085}$ in mid-infrared region. The plasmonic resonant frequency of $8.785 \mu\text{m}$ corresponds to carrier density of $1.05 \cdot 10^{19} \text{cm}^{-3}$.

The carrier density obtained is $1.05 \cdot 10^{19} \text{cm}^{-3}$, which is slightly lower than concentration of silicon atoms measured by SIMS, suggesting that 90 % of dopant atoms were ionized. The carrier concentration in outer cladding layer will be significant for determining the refractive index and FCA losses.

Figure 4.2.3.6. Energy dispersion of bulk $\text{InAs}_{0.915}\text{Sb}_{0.085}$ in reciprocal space. The effective mass reaches minimum $m_e^* = 0.025 m_0$ at $k_{||} = 0$ (no doping).

Figure 4.2.3.7. Scheme of iterative procedure for extracting charge carrier density from photoreflectance measurement of doped InAsSb sample.

4.3. Growth, fabrication and characterization of interband cascade laser

In this subchapter, the growth, processing and characterization of an ICL is described. The respective characterization tools and measurements are explained for primary characterization (optical microscopy, SEM, STEM, HR-XRD, SIMS) and secondary (electro-optical) characterization. The post-growth processing was specified for broad area and narrow ridge waveguide devices.

4.3.1. Epitaxial growth

Once the calibration of growth parameters is completed, an ICL can be grown. ICLs are commonly grown on GaSb or InAs substrates. The 3.7 μm ICL is grown on n-type Te-doped GaSb substrate ($1 \cdot 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$). The growth rates of GaSb and InSb in the active region (AR) are calibrated to 480 nm/h and 320 nm/h, respectively, to form 60/40 ratio in the hole $\text{Ga}_{0.6}\text{In}_{0.4}\text{Sb}$ QW, whereas in claddings, AlSb and InAs are grown at 500 nm/h. The last four InAs wells of the electron injector of the 3.7 μm design described in the third chapter are n-type doped with Si ($5 \cdot 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$). The Figure 4.3.1.1. displays a sketch of the doping profile of the ICL structure. The GaSb-based SCLs were lightly n-type doped with Te ($6 \cdot 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) to mitigate absorption losses in vicinity of the active region, where the optical mode reaches its maximum intensity. The first and the last 10 nm of the SCLs were doped higher ($5 \cdot 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) to alleviate the doping concentration offsets with the adjacent TLs to claddings and to the active region. The InAs QWs

of the cladding layers are n-type doped with Si to $2 \cdot 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ in vicinity of the SCLs, linearly increasing to $8 \cdot 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ towards the outside. The cap InAs layer is heavily n-type doped with Si ($2 \cdot 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) for a good ohmic contact. An important parameter left to be gauged towards optimal growth is the substrate temperature.

Figure 4.3.1.1. Doping density profiles of InAs and GaSb layers doped with Si (blue) and Te (purple), respectively.

In Figure 4.3.1.2, the profile of substrate temperature throughout duration of growth of GaSb-based ICL is depicted. Prior to growth, the substrate temperature was raised to $560 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to outgas the unwanted oxides from the substrate. During this process the sample was exposed to an overpressure of Sb to prevent Sb-desorption from the substrate. As for the calibration samples, the temperature was ramped down to $500 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The growth begins with 200 nm n-type Te-doped GaSb buffer ($1 \cdot 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) to separate the structure from impurities of the substrate. The temperature was then decreased to $450 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for the growth of the bottom SL InAs/AlSb cladding. The bottom bulk GaSb SCL was grown with $500 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The active region of the ICL is dominantly composed of InAs/AlSb layers, suggesting the same optimal temperature as used for the cladding layers. As the emission wavelength and gain depend on a proper growth of the active region, it is important to match the desired temperature and to maintain it. Therefore, once the active region is grown, the temperature remains at $450 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ throughout the growth of the rest of the structure. Increasing temperature would lead to smearing out of the interfaces in the active region, leading to red shift of emission wavelength and poorer performance in terms of threshold current, as shown in Ref. [96]. The growth of InAs-based ICLs is slightly different. Since InAs buffer and SCLs are InAs-based, these layers are grown at $\sim 450 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The growth of the SLs is though more complex in terms of strain compensation. The value of lattice constant of GaSb is between InAs and AlSb, hence with the right ratio of thicknesses, the strain can be compensated. However, for growth on InAs substrates, some growth interruptions with applied arsenic (soaking) must be applied to tackle the accumulation of compressive strain introduced by AlSb barriers.

Figure 4.3.1.2. The substrate temperature profile throughout the growth of a GaSb-based ICL with SL InAs/AlSb claddings.

4.3.2. Optical microscopy

Surface image of the ICL can reflect non-ideal growth conditions. We are considering $3.7\ \mu\text{m}$ emitting laser with state-of-the-art active region and cladding design. Figure 4.3.2 presents the low (a) and high (b) density of oval defects. Higher density of defects is a consequence of lower flux of group V materials. Arsenic and antimony fluxes for ICL depicted at (a) were $1.81 \cdot 10^{-6}$ Torr and $2.10 \cdot 10^{-6}$ Torr, respectively. Surface of the sample (b) was not saturated with group V elements; thus, oval defects appeared. The arsenic and antimony fluxes for ICL presented on Figure 4.3.2 (b) were $1.55 \cdot 10^{-6}$ Torr and $1.95 \cdot 10^{-6}$ Torr. As there were no linear defects (parallel defect lines), the surface did not indicate any residual strain.

Figure 4.3.2. Surface images of the $3.7\ \mu\text{m}$ ICLs grown at the same temperatures, but group V (As, Sb) fluxes used in the active region: (a) ($1.81\text{E-}6$, $2.10\text{E-}6$) Torr (b) ($1.55\text{E-}6$, $1.95\text{E-}6$) Torr. The defects at the sample with lower flux indicate the unsaturated surface.

4.3.3. High Resolution X-ray Diffraction (HR-XRD)

HR-XRD spectra of the 3.7 μm ICL is depicted at Figure 4.3.3. Satellite peaks of the active region and of the cladding layers, as well as the peak corresponding to the InAs cap layer are labelled. Active region peak show good growth quality as indicated by visible peaks up to 18th order (low-angle side) and up to 14th order (high-angle side) . The peaks indicate accuracy of 97.1 % since the measured cascade length was 38.0 nm whereas the length of the designed cascade was 39.14 nm.

Figure 4.3.3. X-ray diffractogram of the 3.7 μm ICL indicating strain-compensated growth.

The cladding layers peaks are showing period length of 4.70 nm, reflecting accuracy of 99.4 %, as the desired period length was 4.73 nm (2.43 nm InAs/2.30 nm AlSb). The cladding layer peaks are doubled due to abrupt increase of ambient temperature caused by the shutdown of cleanroom ventilation system. The overlap between GaSb substrate peak and zeroth order SL reflex labelled in the figure show a good strain compensation, as the lattice mismatch was only 230 ppm.

4.3.4. Scanning/Transmission Electron Microscopy (SEM/STEM)

In Figure 4.3.4.1. SEM images of the grown 3.7 μm ICL show smooth layer interfaces and a good contrast between materials. The accuracy of thicknesses of the top and bottom SCL was 95.3 %. Thicknesses of the claddings are also matching well with the design values. Recombination regions and electron injectors of the active region are presented in light gray, while hole injectors are indicated in dark gray as it is predominantly composed of GaSb. Figure 4.3.4.2. (a) depicts image of the active region composed of 5 cascade stages and transition layers to top and bottom SCL. In Figure 5.3.4.2 (b) the layers of a single cascade stages are aligned to its band structure, where AlSb barrier layers are labeled by arrows. Due to a limited resolution, SEM technique is suitable for layers thicker than ~ 20 nm. To have an insight to

thicknesses and interface abruptness of the thin layers of a few nanometers, scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) is used.

Figure 4.3.4.1. SEM images of 3.7 μm ICL: (a) active region (b) whole structure.

Figure 4.3.4.2. (a) SEM image of the active region of 3.7 μm ICL with labelled cascade stages and transition layers (b) SEM image of a single cascade stage of the active region of 3.7 μm ICL, aligned to layers of its band structure profile. The green arrows point to AlSb barrier layers.

STEM is a technique related to transmission electron microscopy (TEM), but with a key difference in the observation geometry relative to the direction of the incoming electron beam. In TEM, image formation depends on changing the aperture position to detect electrons, whereas STEM uses various detectors positioned at different collection angles to capture electrons scattered along specific trajectories. The electron beam in STEM is deflected electrostatically by scanning coils toward an electron-counting detector, typically structured as a Faraday cup. Unlike TEM, where electrons pass through the entire cross-section of the specimen, STEM focuses the beam to a fine probe—typically 0.05–0.2 nm in diameter—at each point on the sample, resulting in higher spatial resolution. The sample is then raster-scanned so that each point is illuminated perpendicularly to the incoming beam. This high-resolution capability allows for imaging of individual atoms along the sample’s growth

direction. In Figure 4.3.4.3 a band structure of the active region of 3.7 μm ICL is depicted. Aligned with the band structure and presented by the black curve, is a profile of ratio

Figure 4.3.4.3. Band structure of the active region of 3.7 μm ICL. Factor F reflecting presence of group III/group V atoms shows non-abrupt interfaces that may lead to longer emission wavelength.

$$F = \frac{I_{III} - I_{III}}{I_{III} + I_V} \quad (4.3.4)$$

where I_{III} and I_V are intensities of atomic columns corresponding to numbers of group III (Al, Ga, In) and group V (As, Sb) atoms present in the corresponding monolayer. The curve indicates smeared out interfaces influenced by interdiffusion of group V elements between adjacent layers. Oval profiles of factor F could reflect on slight red shift of emission wavelength due to effective shrinkage of thicknesses of QWs in the recombination region.

4.3.5. Secondary Ion Mass Spectrometry (SIMS)

Similarly to calibration of doping, doping densities of layers of an ICL are measured by SIMS. Insufficient doping can reduce the voltage efficiency due to downgrading ohmic contact at the cap. Additionally it would increase the series resistance and hence the threshold power density. Figure 4.3.5 displays doping densities of the grown ICL. The buffer layer is n-type doped to $1 \cdot 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. Doping density of the InAs layers of the claddings reduce from outside ($8 \cdot 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) to the SCL layers ($2 \cdot 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$). Edge peaks of the doping density of SCL layers reach $2 \cdot 5 \cdot 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. Doping density of the rest of SCLs also match the designed value ($6 \cdot 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}$). However, doping density in the active region does not show the constant value as it is a result of averaging doping of the InAs-wells of electron injector. The doping in the cap layer is in the range of desired 10^{19} cm^{-3} range, however it was not possible to readout the exact value at such short thickness.

Figure 4.3.5. Densities of Si (blue curve) and Te (red curve) ions in the growth direction of an ICL. Doping density of InAs wells in claddings are linearly increasing from SCLs towards outside. First and the last 10 nm of each SCL is doped higher than the middle of SCL. The doping density in the electron injector QWs is averaged over the active region.

4.3.6. Broad area and narrow ridge waveguide processing

After the growth, ICLs were processed to either broad area (BA) or narrow ridge waveguides (RWG) by optical lithography (photolithography). Heat dissipation from the active medium plays an important role in laser operation as the heat is limiting the laser performance. With wider ridges, Joule heating increases due to increase of current, hence BA devices are commonly non-operational in continuous-wave (cw) mode. However, for the simplicity of the process, they are used for electro-optical characterization in pulsed mode operation. Complementary, a RWG laser can be driven in cw mode, however its process involves more time and complexity.

BA devices are processed in 50 μm , 75 μm and 100 μm wide ridges. The etch depth of the process is sufficiently large to etch through the active region (AR). If the etch depth is shallower, the portion of current driven through the ridge is reduced due to effect of current spreading as presented in Figure 4.3.6.1. The current spreads laterally through the bulk, thus it is a parasitic effect similar to current leakage from surface conduction of unpassivated side walls. The processing of BA devices is presented in Figure 4.3.6.2. Surface of the grown ICL, depicted in (a) is cleaned with acetone and isopropanol, 2 min each and then baked at 150 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 15 min, to outgas any organic residuals. Subsequently, 1.7 μm thick layer of the positive

resist is deposited on the cleaned surface as shown in (b). For the sake of uniformity of the thickness in the radial direction, the resist is spin-coated at 3500 rpm at 95 °C for 40 min.

Figure 4.3.6.1. (a) Sketch of the current spreading in an ICL with unpassivated side walls, processed by shallow etching. (b) Sketch of the current spreading in an ICL with unpassivated side walls, processed by deep etching through the active region.

After the resist deposition, as subfigure (c) suggests, the sample is covered with a lithography mask with 50 μm , 75 μm and 100 μm wide slits and then illuminated for exposure time of 20 s. The exposed areas of the resist get developed by the suitable developer for 20 s (d). Then eventually, surface is ashed with 50 % content of O_2 for 2 min, to remove any resist residuals. In addition, any leftover oxide residuals are treated with a mixture of 0.8 ml of NH_4OH and 15 ml of water for 15 s (e). On the sample surface are then evaporated metal layers in sequence of 10 nm of Ti, 30 nm of Pt, 185 nm of Au as a top contact, at evaporation rate of 0.05 nm/s (f). Afterwards, the lift-off process is carried out by ultrasonic bath at 80 °C to remove the remaining resist along with metal on top (g). The sample is then wet etched by the mixture of 25 ml water/2.5 ml H_3PO_4 /3.5 ml H_2O_2 at 30 °C, for 6-7 min, so that the ridges are etched through the active region (h). Then same way as in the step (e), the oxide residuals are treated after the wet etching (i). Finally, the back contact is evaporated in a sequence of 55 nm of AuGe, 22.5 nm of Ni, 150 nm of Au at evaporation rate of 0.05 nm/s (j), after what the sample is annealed at 300 °C for 30 s (k). For processing of RWG lasers instead of optical lithography, e-beam lithography is used. Unlike optical lithography, e-beam uses a field electron emission source such as heated W/ ZrO_2 for acceleration electrons to kinetic energies of up to 100 keV. Their corresponding wavelength is shorter than of the light used for optical lithography, enabling sub-10-nm resolution, which is the main advantage of e-beam. In addition, its lithography is maskless, as the metal contacts are used as a mask instead. This is however limiting the throughput of the process. The ICL grown on 2" wafer is cleaved to quarters, each containing three 11 mm x 10 mm pieces for processing. On every process piece of the grown sample ~20 ICL ridges are fabricated. The ridges are etched down to the interface between

active region and the bottom SCL. The ICL structures are 5-7 μm wide and the cavity length is ~ 1 mm. The passivation layers are deposited on the ridges to prevent the oxidation on the side walls.

Figure 4.3.6.2. (a) Cleaning with acetone, isopropanol and baking. (b) Deposition of a positive resist and spin coating. (c) Exposure to illumination. (d) Resist development. (e) Ashing of resist residuals and oxide treatment. (f) Evaporation of Ti/Pt/Au contact. (g) Lift-off under ultrasonic bath. (h) Wet etching. (i) Oxide treatment. (j) Evaporation of AuGe/Ni/Au (back) contact. (k) Thermal annealing.

However, at top of the ridge, it is etched by reactive ion etching for electrical contacting. The contacts are the same as for BA process, although, an additional ~ 10 μm of Au is electroplated on the top contact. Before the evaporation of the back contact, the substrate is thinned from 600 μm to ~ 150 nm. Shorter distance from the active region to the cooled copper heat sink enables better heat dissipation if the laser is mounted epi-side up. This step is not necessary if the device is mounted epi-side down. The facets are coated with high-reflective (HR) metal layers, on the back side insulated by anti-reflective (AR) SiO_2 and Al_2O_3 .

4.3.7. Electro-optical characterisation of an ICL

In Figure 4.3.7.1. the setup for electro-optical characterisation of an ICL is presented. A laser ridge is placed on a heat sink (chuck) attached to the stage movable along all three axes. The position of the sample is adjusted by micrometer screws, and the electrical contact is made by tungsten needle attached to a micropositioner. Temperature of the heat sink is controlled by a water-cooled Peltier element via digital temperature controller. The laser can be operated in both pulsed and continuous-wave mode by the laser drive power supply by selecting the duty cycle based on the pulse length and repetition rate. The emitted light is collimated by two 2-inch anti-reflective coated ZnSe lenses on the HgCdTe (MCT) detector. The input current, voltage and the output power from the detector are read on three channels of the oscilloscope. The power-current-voltage characteristics are traced and monitored by Labview software. On the path from the laser to the MCT detector, a gold flippable mirror is used to reflect the beam of emitted light towards the FTIR spectrometer (Bruker IFS 66v/S) to measure the spectra. Additionally, a lock-in amplifier is used to improve a signal-to-noise ratio (SNR).

A major part of the FTIR, Michelson interferometer is depicted in Figure 4.3.7.2. The emitted light is divided by a KBr beam splitter and directed to two optical paths: towards the stationary mirror and towards the movable mirror.

Figure 4.3.7.1. Schematic of the setup for electro-optical characterisation of an ICL. The flippable mirror is used for switching the setup from the power-current-voltage characterisation to measurement of the emission spectrum.

The moving mirror is periodically transmitting and blocking each wavelength as result of varying the optical path difference (OPD). The resolution of the measurement is however, limited by the maximum path length the mirror can make. The output signal of the light is scanned by a detector. Based on the wavelength range of the input light, the used detectors are Ge (1.5 – 3.8 μm), MCT (1 – 24 μm) and InSb (1.5 – 8.0 μm), where InSb has the highest detectivity. The wavelength-dependent emission spectrum is obtained in software OPUS from interference of the light from optical paths split by KBr beamsplitter of the FTIR. The grown

ICL of state-of-the-art design, processed to 2 mm long and 50, 75 and 100 μm wide BA ridges is characterized at the described setup. The ridges were etched through the active region. Pulsed measurements were carried out under a repetition rate of 1 kHz and pulse width of 500 ns, to mitigate Joule heating.

Figure 4.3.7.2. Schematic of a Michelson interferometer configured to FTIR. The incident beam is split into beams towards stationary and moving mirror. Backreflected beams are interfering at the detector.

Figure 5.3.7.3 (a) displays electro-optical characteristics of the BA ICL operated at 20 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The maximum temperature the emission was obtained was 125 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The measured threshold current density was $J_{th} = 146 \text{ A/cm}^2$ is comparable to the lowest reported values [56], [97]. The lowest reported threshold current density of an ICL, $J_{th} = 98 \text{ A/cm}^2$ [56] was obtained for the same active region design, however for 12 cascade stages, on expense of the threshold power. The measured differential resistance was $R_{diff} = 2.52 \Omega$ which is slightly higher than state-of-the-art, most probably due to lower-than-expected doping in the capping layer. Slightly higher differential resistance and open circuit voltage of $V_0 = 2.57 \text{ V}$ resulted in threshold power density of $P_{th} = 417 \text{ W/cm}^2$, higher than reported [87], [88]. The voltage efficiency of $\eta_v = 58.6 \%$ could be improved by lowering the differential resistance. It can be noted that the open-circuit voltage is reasonably matching with the estimated value in chapter 3 ($V_0 = 2.64 \text{ V}$). In comparison to deeply etched BA, the obtained threshold current density and differential resistance of shallowly etched BA were $J_{th} = 236 \text{ A/cm}^2$ and $R_{diff} = 1.64 \Omega$. The leakage current through the bulk contributed to a higher threshold current density. As the leakage and the main component of the current driven through the ridge along the growth direction form a parallel junction, the series resistance is lower than for the deeply etched device.

In Figure 4.3.7.3. (b), the temperature dependence of threshold current densities was presented. An important figure of merit for lasers is a characteristic temperature (T_0) defined implicitly as

$$J_{th} = J_{th0} e^{T/T_0}. \quad (4.3.7)$$

Figure 4.3.7.3. (a) Pulsed voltage-current and light-current curves at 20 °C for a 2 mm long and 50 μm wide BA device. (b) Temperature dependence of the threshold current density and extracted characteristic temperature $T_0 = 41$ K.

High characteristic temperature is an indicator of high temperature stability of the laser, as the temperature change of threshold current density changes reduces with higher T_0 . The extracted characteristic temperature was $T_0 = 41$ K which was slightly lower than reported (45 – 60 K) for similar wavelengths [30], however it is important to note that the characteristic temperature mathematically reduces at larger temperature range. A high T_0 can also be an indicator of a possible operation of a RWG device in cw at RT. Figure 4.3.7.4. (a) depicts spectra of the ICL at six different temperatures.

Figure 4.3.7.4. (a) Spectra at different temperatures of a BA (2 mm X 50 μm) device. Central wavelengths of parabolic fits of spectra are labelled. (b) Temperature dependence of the central wavelengths of the spectra. The extracted wavelength shift is $\Delta\lambda/\Delta T = 2.1$ nm/°C.

The narrow spectral spikes visible in the emission spectra originate from longitudinal Fabry–Pérot modes of the 2 mm-long cavity. Their regular spacing and persistence across temperatures confirm they are not measurement noise, but intrinsic modal features of the uncoated laser cavity. The red shift is a consequence of band gap reduction of constituting electron InAs and hole Ga_{0.6}In_{0.4}Sb QW according to Varshni dependence. As presented in Figure 4.3.7.4. (b), the temperature-induced wavelength shift was 2.1 nm/°C.

5. ICL claddings for advanced optical confinement

At wavelengths longer than “sweet-spot” wavelength range of 3-4 μm , a high optical confinement in the active region is crucial for laser operation due to low wavefunction overlap and high FCA losses. In this chapter, the ICLs with various cladding materials of lower refractive index and higher thermal confinement than state-of-the-art AlSb/InAs SLs are designed and realized.

In the first section, a theoretical and experimental comparison between GaSb-based ICLs with AlSb/InAs and bulk $\text{Al}_{0.85}\text{Ga}_{0.15}\text{As}_{0.07}\text{Sb}_{0.93}$ claddings was made, at an emission wavelength of 5.0 μm . In the second section, the comparison was made between the GaSb and InAs-based ICLs with hybrid superlattice plasmon-enhanced claddings at emission wavelength of 4.6 μm . In addition, the optimization of the cladding design for the GaSb-based ICL was shown. In the third section, design and realization of a GaSb-based ICL with emission wavelength of 5.2 μm and hybrid cladding design is discussed.

5.1. GaSb-based interband cascade lasers with AlGaAsSb claddings

In this subchapter, influence of bulk AlGaAsSb claddings on performance of the ICLs is discussed. The first section, a theoretical comparison to the ICL with state-of-the-art SL claddings was made in terms of the optical confinement. In the second section, the performances of the two ICLs with analog structures and different cladding materials is compared. The results from figure 5.1.1.3 are simulated and obtained from Helmholtz wave equations.

5.1.1. ICLs with bulk and superlattice claddings

When the first cw operation at RT was demonstrated in 2008 [47], SL claddings with doping levels gradually decreasing towards the active region were introduced and are commonly used ever since. As state-of-the-art ICLs are based on III-V materials, they are usually grown on GaSb and InAs substrates. Due to the lattice constant of AlSb (InAs) slightly longer (shorter) than the lattice constant of GaSb, $a = 0.60959 \text{ nm}$ [52], the strain compensation in AlSb/InAs SL is simply achievable by the right ratio of layer thicknesses and fluxes of group V elements, as described before. Aside from defect-free growth, a low refractive index and a high thermal conductivity are desirable material properties for cladding layers. This is particularly important for a high confinement of the optical mode in the gain medium (active region) and for a better heat dissipation. Additionally, a high carrier mobility plays an important role in lowering series resistance and FCA losses according to equation 3.1.2.1.7. In Figure 5.1.1.1. an overview of refractive indices for III-V binaries is presented, for wavelengths in the 3.5-5.0 μm spectral window, significant for majority of ICLs. The 6.1 \AA family, labelled in Figure 5.1.1.1. indicate InAs and AlSb as state-of-the-art cladding materials, on the opposite sides of the GaSb regarding the lattice constant. From all the shown binaries, AlSb and AlAs have the lowest refractive indices, hence $\text{AlAs}_{0.08}\text{Sb}_{0.92}$ lattice-matched to GaSb would be a suitable candidate for cladding layers. However, Al-rich layers have been proven to be susceptible to oxidation

both at high temperatures during growth and later over time [81], [98]. This leads to the segregation and accumulation of the metallic elemental Sb in the layer [99]. Defect-free AlAsSb was successfully grown in the past, but on InAs substrates as demonstrated in Reference [100]. The oxidation process of bulk AlAsSb grown on GaSb was later studied under various conditions [98]. The AlAsSb layer capped with GaSb was oxidized at 340 °C by carrier gas N₂ that was flown into the furnace with a bubbler containing deionized water. Dendrite-shaped defects were formed at the surface due to oxidation. It was observed that the defects spread through the sample with the oxidation time. It was reported that for AlAsSb of a higher As-content, AlAs_{0.56}Sb_{0.44} the oxidation stops at temperatures higher than 340 °C due to “self-limiting effect” caused by abrupt drop of the diffusion constant.

Figure 5.1.1.1. Refractive indices of III-V binaries in the wavelength range 3.5-5.0 μm. The binaries of lattice constant ≈6.1 Å are labelled.

However, since it is not possible to grow tensile strained layer defect-free on GaSb substrate, a different approach is needed. For the sake of higher oxidation stability, a fraction of Ga is introduced to the alloy, thus Al_{0.85}Ga_{0.15}As_{0.07}Sb_{0.93}, lattice-matched to GaSb is used instead of AlAs_{0.08}Sb_{0.92}, despite slightly increasing the refractive index [88]. As stated in the same reference, bulk AlGaAsSb claddings are promising and potentially can outperform ICLs with AlSb/InAs SL claddings, which was confirmed by RT threshold current density as low as J_{th} = 220 A/cm² for emission wavelength of 3.5 μm. A similar value was later obtained in reference [96] at 3.33 μm, where the optimal growth temperature was studied. The W-shaped QW and the electron injectors both contain InAs layers commonly grown at substrate temperatures T ≈ 430 – 450 °C [90], [101], [102]. Conversely, aluminium-rich layers are grown optimally at higher temperatures, T ≈ 500 – 520 °C [103], [104].

In this chapter, the comparison and realization of the ICLs with AlSb/InAs SL and AlGaAsSb bulk claddings emitting at 5 μm is made. Going towards longer wavelengths, i.e. above the sweet spot operation (~3.5 μm), obtaining low threshold current density becomes more technologically challenging due to decrease of the wavefunction overlap in the recombination region and parabolic increase of the FCA losses according to equation 3.1.2.1.7 from

subchapter 3.1.2.1. In Table 5.1.1.1. an overview of refractive indices n_r [32], [88], [105], [106], [107] and thermal conductivities κ of both cladding designs are presented [86], [108], [109].

	AlSb/InAs	AlGaAsSb
n_r	3.39	3.30
κ (W/m·K)	≈ 7	≈ 3

Table 5.1.1.1. Refractive indices and thermal conductivities of AlSb/InAs SL claddings and bulk $\text{Al}_{0.85}\text{Ga}_{0.15}\text{As}_{0.07}\text{Sb}_{0.93}$ claddings.

There are two main advantages of the bulk cladding compared to SL claddings: a lower refractive index $n_{r\text{AlGaAsSb}} = 3.30$ compared to $n_{r\text{AlSb/InAs}} = 3.39$ and a higher thermal conductivity of $\kappa_{\text{AlGaAsSb}} \approx 7 \text{ W/m}\cdot\text{K}$ compared to $\kappa_{\text{AlSb/InAs}} \approx 3 \text{ W/m}\cdot\text{K}$. An additional advantage is the reduced complex growth with its excessive number of shutter cycles (~ 2000 per grown sample) for SL claddings, that contributes to weariness of the MBE system. Two ICL structures with the same six-stage active region and geometry but different cladding designs are displayed in Figure 5.1.1.2. Similarly to the ICL with SL claddings, TLs in the ICL with AlGaAsSb claddings were employed to bridge the band offset between the GaSb SCL and $\text{Al}_{0.85}\text{Ga}_{0.15}\text{As}_{0.07}\text{Sb}_{0.93}$ claddings. The TLs are 50 nm thick linear digital gratings (LDGs) composed of 11 periods of GaSb/ $\text{Al}_{0.85}\text{Ga}_{0.15}\text{As}_{0.07}\text{Sb}_{0.93}$ with thicknesses gradually decreasing from 4 nm down to 0.5 nm (GaSb) and increasing from 0.5 nm to 4 nm ($\text{Al}_{0.85}\text{Ga}_{0.15}\text{As}_{0.07}\text{Sb}_{0.93}$).

Figure 5.1.1.2. Schematic layout of the ICLs with SL cladding in (a) and with AlGaAsSb bulk cladding in (b).

The profiles of refractive indices and optical mode profiles along the growth direction are depicted for both ICL structures in Figure 5.1.1.3 (a). It is shown that the mode confinement in the active region is enhanced for the bulk cladding because of the lower refractive index. The confinement factors of the two ICLs were calculated by a Helmholtz wave equation solver. Distribution of optical mode intensity with the corresponding confinement factors in ICL with SL and AlGaAsSb claddings are presented in Figures 5.1.1.3 (b) and (c), respectively. Optical confinement in the active region of the ICL with AlGaAsSb claddings is 14.4 % higher in comparison to ICL with SL claddings. Conversely, confinement in claddings is reduced by 17.8 %. Taking doping levels (N), effective masses (m_e^*) [52] and mobilities (μ_e) [110], [111], [112], [113],

[114], [115] to account, FCA losses in different layer species can be calculated from equation 3.1.2.1.7.

The respective figures of merit along with obtained FCA losses are listed in Table 5.1.1.2. The doping of the cladding layers linearly increases from $1 \cdot 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ to $1 \cdot 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ with distance from the active region, hence the FCA is also linearly dependent on the coordinate along the growth direction (x). Considering confinement factors, overall FCA losses can be calculated in both ICL structures from

$$FCA = FCA(\text{cladd}, SCL, AR) = \int \alpha_{\text{cladd}}(x) d\Gamma_{\text{cladd}}(x) + \alpha_{SCL} \Gamma_{SCL} + \alpha_{AR} \Gamma_{AR} \quad (5.1.1)$$

For the simplicity and lack of accessibility to the calculation of the intervalence band absorption at the time of writing the corresponding manuscripts ([48], [49], [50]), in this chapter the losses in AR taken to account were FCA losses averaged over different containing layer species.

Figure 5.1.1.3. (a) Refractive index profiles and relative mode intensities along the growth direction of two ICLs with the same active region design but different cladding designs: SL InAs/AlSb claddings (dark green) and bulk AlGaAsSb claddings (light green). (b) Optical mode confinement distribution along the growth direction of the ICL with SL claddings. (c) Optical mode confinement distribution along the growth direction of the ICL with bulk AlGaAsSb claddings.

	SCL	SL cladd.	Bulk cladd.	AR
$N(\text{cm}^{-3})$	$6 \cdot 10^{16}$	$1 \cdot 10^{17} - 1 \cdot 10^{18}$	$1 \cdot 10^{17} - 1 \cdot 10^{18}$	$4 \cdot 10^{18}$
$m_e^*(m_0)$	0.039	0.081	0.126	0.067
$\mu_e(\text{cm}^2/\text{V} \cdot \text{s})$	2800	10.000	640	4500
$FCA_{SL}(\text{cm}^{-1})$	2.4	0.5	/	2.7
$FCA_{Bulk}(\text{cm}^{-1})$	2.6	/	2.3	3.1

Table 5.1.1.2. Doping levels, effective masses, mobilities and FCA losses in GaSb SCLs, AlSb/InAs SL, bulk $\text{Al}_{0.85}\text{Ga}_{0.15}\text{As}_{0.07}\text{Sb}_{0.93}$ claddings and the active region (AR).

The evaluated overall FCA losses in the ICL with bulk claddings, $\alpha = 8.0 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is significantly higher than in ICL with the SL claddings, $\alpha = 5.6 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The two analog designs imply that there is a trade-off between the improvement of the optical confinement in the active region and reduction of FCA loss. The active region is composed of 6 cascade stages. The recombination region composed of **AlSb/InAs/Ga_{0.6}In_{0.4}Sb/InAs/AlSb** with thicknesses of **(2.5/2.23/2.55/1.75/1.0)** nm was designed to emit at $5.0 \mu\text{m}$ by the software nextnano³.

5.1.2. Growth and characterisation

The ICLs with SL and bulk claddings were grown by MBE on 2-inch GaSb substrates n-type doped with Te ($1 \cdot 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$). The growth procedure of the two ICLs is described in detail in Appendix A of this dissertation.

In Figure 5.1.2.1 (a), a HR-XRD of the ICL with SL claddings is displayed. The GaSb substrate and zeroth order SL reflex are labelled in the figure and show a reasonable strain compensation with a mismatch of only 560 ppm.

Figure 5.1.2.1. (a) X-ray diffractogram of the ICL with SL claddings indicating strain-compensated growth. (b) X-ray diffractogram of the ICL with AlGaAsSb bulk claddings indicating lattice-matched growth.

Higher order peaks of the SL claddings, peaks of the active region (AR) and the peak of the InAs cap are presented as well. The HR-XRD scan of the ICL with AlGaAsSb claddings is shown in Figure 5.1.2.1. (b). The mismatch of 340 ppm indicates almost ideal lattice matching of the claddings to the GaSb substrate. The peaks of the active region of the ICL with superlattice claddings are visible up to 17th (low-angle side) and 13th order (high-angle side), whereas the peaks of the active region of the ICL with bulk claddings are visible up to 19th (low-angle side) and 11th order (high-angle side), implying a good crystal quality of both ICLs. Period thicknesses of the active region and claddings of both ICLs show high precision of up to 2 % error margin. It is worth pointing out that the displayed scan of the ICL with bulk claddings is presenting the grown sample structure after the rinsing the sample surface with water. After the growth of the sample is finished, the surface stays exposed to Sb to prevent its desorption from the surface. However, by accident, Sb shutter did not close at the end of the growth run, when the substrate temperature was low, resulting in formation of layer an amorphous Sb. The SEM image of the grown ICL with AlGaAsSb claddings is displayed in Figure 5.1.2.2 (a). The layers of the ICL and the Sb layer on top are labelled in the Figure. The layer was visible on the HR-XRD scan by the broad side peak indicated in Figure 5.1.2.2. (b) (left). Once treated with water, the layer of Sb dissolved, and the side peak vanished as shown in the Figure 5.1.1.2.2 (b) (right). The measurement of the doping levels in the ICL with AlGaAsSb claddings was performed by SIMS. Figure 5.1.2.3. displays the doping concentration throughout the layers (labelled). The measured densities correspond well to the designed values. The drop of the doping concentration after the buffer layer is caused by a sudden transition from low growth rate of GaSb (88 nm/h) to high growth rate of Al_{0.85}Ga_{0.15}As_{0.07}Sb_{0.93} (588 nm/h) at the same flux of Te ions. Doping by Si was applied only to active region.

Figure 5.1.2.2. (a) SEM image of the ICL with AlGaAsSb claddings with its layers labelled and with the layer of amorphous Sb on top of the surface (left) and with the Sb layer half-removed by water (right). (b) X-ray diffractogram of the ICL with AlGaAsSb bulk claddings, with (left) and without (right) amorphous Sb layer on top.

Figure 5.1.2.3. Densities of Te ions in the growth direction of the ICL with AlGaAsSb claddings. Doping density of InAs wells in claddings are linearly increasing from SCLs towards outside. First and the last 10 nm of each SCL is doped higher than the middle of SCL. The doping density in the electron injector QWs is averaged over the active region.

Following the growth, deep etched BA devices were fabricated as described in subchapter 4.3.6.

The laser bar with processed ridges was placed on the copper heat sink for the characterisation. The measurement was performed in pulsed mode at a repetition rate of 1 kHz and the pulse width of 500 ns, to minimize Joule heating. Electro-optical characteristics of the BA ICLs operated at RT (25 °C) are displayed in Figure 5.1.2.4. (a).

Figure 5.1.2.4. (a) Pulsed light power-current and voltage-current curves at RT for a 2 mm long and 100 μm wide BA ICL with SL and AlGaAsSb bulk claddings. (b) Voltage characteristics of the BA ICLs with SL

and AlGaAsSb claddings with linear fits of their leakage components and labelled leakage currents at respective threshold voltages.

The ICL with SL claddings showed threshold current density of $J_{th} = 521 \text{ A/cm}^2$, the threshold power density of $P_{th} = 2.03 \text{ kW/cm}^2$, threshold voltage of $V_{th} = 3.9 \text{ V}$ and a voltage efficiency of $\eta_V = 38.1 \%$ while for the ICL with bulk AlGaAsSb claddings, the obtained values for the same figures of merit are $J_{th} = 396 \text{ A/cm}^2$, $P_{th} = 2.65 \text{ kW/cm}^2$, $V_{th} = 6.7 \text{ V}$ and $\eta_V = 22.2 \%$. Apparently, there is a presence of leakage current in both ICLs in the voltage range of 3.0-3.6 V. Under assumption of ohmic behaviour of the ridge sidewalls that lead to a leakage, voltage-current characteristics could be extrapolated to higher voltages. The electrical characteristics of the ICLs were linearly fitted as shown in Figure 5.1.2.4. (b). Leakage currents of the ICL with SL and bulk claddings at respective threshold voltages are labelled in blue are 154 and 168 A/cm^2 . As the leakage current components are approximately the same, they are highly unlikely responsible for the difference in threshold current densities of the two ICLs. An additional method to cross-check this conclusion is measurement of threshold currents or ridges of different perimeter-to-area (P/A) ratios. Ridges of four different cavity lengths, 1.4 mm, 1.6 mm, 1.8 mm and 2.0 mm and the same width of 100 μm , were cleaved and characterized. In Figure 5.2.1.5, their threshold current densities are presented for their respective P/A ratios. The slope of the ICL with AlGaAsSb claddings $J_{th}/(P/A) = 487 \text{ A/mm}$, is smaller than of the ICL with SL claddings (1072 A/mm). The threshold current densities at (hypothetical) zero P/A ratio of the ICL with SL and AlGaAsSb claddings are then extrapolated to 5631 A/cm^2 and 2721 A/cm^2 , implying the superior performance of the ICL with AlGaAsSb claddings at zero sidewall leakage. Apart from the leakage current, the VISA also plays an important role in increasing threshold current density as shown in [76], [77].

Figure 5.1.2.5. Dependence of threshold current densities of ICLs with SL and AlGaAsSb claddings on perimeter-to-area (P/A) ratio, corresponding to 100 μm wide BA ridges of four different cavity lengths: 1.4 mm, 1.6 mm, 1.8 mm and 2.0 mm.

The suboptimal thickness of the hole, $\text{Ga}_{0.6}\text{In}_{0.4}\text{Sb}$ QW in the recombination region should be taken to account, considering the optimal thickness at emission wavelength of 5 μm was reported to be 3.0 nm [76], [77]. However, the high leakage currents resulted in threshold current densities above reported at similar wavelengths ($\approx 300 \text{ A/cm}^2$) [79], [116], [117], [118], [119], above state-of-the-art threshold voltages ($\approx 2 \text{ V}$) and threshold power densities ($\approx 0.8 - 1.5 \text{ kW/cm}^2$) [31], [120]. The lower threshold current density of ICL with AlGaAsSb claddings

implies that a higher confinement of the optical mode in the active region has a bigger influence than FCA losses. The measured voltage efficiencies were significantly lower than reported values at similar wavelengths of $\eta_V = 63\%$ [118] and $\eta_V = 80\%$ [119], due to high threshold current densities. The AlGaAsSb/GaSb TLs in ICL with AlGaAsSb claddings are thicker than AlSb/InAs TLs in the ICL with SL claddings, what lead to a higher parasitic voltage drop and consequently to lower voltage efficiency. The series resistance of the ICL with SL claddings of $2\ \Omega$ reasonably matches the typical $1\text{-}2\ \Omega$ [77], [88], [121], however the value of $5.4\ \Omega$ measured for the ICL with AlGaAsSb claddings is influenced by low doping of cap and GaSb layers of the TLs. Considering the 15% fraction ratio of Ga in the AlGaAsSb quaternary, the contrast between the growth rates of the alternating $\text{Al}_{0.85}\text{Ga}_{0.15}\text{As}_{0.07}\text{Sb}_{0.93}$ and GaSb layers is high, hence, to avoid overdoping GaSb layers, doping levels of AlGaAsSb layers in the transition layers are quite low. Substantially higher series resistance in ICL with AlGaAsSb claddings contributes to its higher threshold voltage, further leading to higher threshold power, despite lower threshold current density. In addition to RT, a temperature series of electro-optical characterisation of the two ICLs was performed. In Figure 5.1.2.6 (a) and (b), the light power-current characteristics of the ICLs with SL and bulk claddings at different temperatures are presented respectively.

Figure 5.1.2.6. (a) Pulsed light-current curve at RT for a 2 mm long and 100 μm wide BA ICL with SL claddings at different J_{th} temperatures. (b) Pulsed light power-current curve at RT for a 2 mm long and 100 μm wide BA ICL with bulk AlGaAsSb claddings at different temperatures. (c) Temperature dependencies of the threshold current densities and characteristic temperatures of ICLs with SL claddings, $T_0 = 38.0\ \text{K}$. and AlGaAsSb bulk claddings, $T_0 = 39.5\ \text{K}$.

The characteristics of the ICL with bulk claddings suggest a lower external differential quantum efficiency (EDQE). Figure 5.1.2.6 (c) depicts temperature dependencies of threshold current densities and the extracted characteristic temperatures. The obtained values compare well

with the previously reported at similar wavelengths [50], [77], [79], [118]. The measured figures of merit at RT, with number of cascade stages (N) are listed in Table 5.1.2.1. As mentioned before, a series of BA ridges of various cavity lengths was characterized. The cavity length dependent measurement can also be used to estimate the absorption losses in the ICLs. Figure 5.1.2.7. (a) and (b) display optical power-current density characteristics of BA ICLs with SL and bulk claddings in sequence. At the same current density, the output power becomes higher with longer cavity. The corresponding EDQEs are presented in the subplots. As slopes of the optical power-current characteristics were approximated to be linear in the range of 0 – 1200 A/cm², EDQEs remain constant once reaching the threshold.

	ICL with SL cladd.	ICL with bulk cladd.	Literature
J_{th} (A/cm ²)	521	396	247-500
P_{th} (kW/cm ²)	2.03	2.65	0.8-1.5
V_{th} (V)	3.9	6.7	≈2
N	6	6	5-12
Substrate type	n-GaSb	n-GaSb	n-GaSb/InAs
T_{max} (°C)	65	65	≤106
T_0 (K)	38.0	39.5	35-57

Table 5.1.2.1. Figures of merit of the ICLs with SL and AlGaAsSb claddings with values reported in the literature for ICLs at RT and wavelengths of approximately 5 μm. The literature values are based on references [30], [31], [77], [80], [119].

Figure 5.1.2.7. (a) Pulsed light power-current characteristics at RT for 1.4 mm, 1.6 mm, 1.8 mm and 2.0 mm long and 100 μm wide BA ICLs with SL claddings. In the subplot, the corresponding external

differential quantum efficiencies (EDQEs) are shown. (b) Pulsed light-current characteristics at RT for 1.4 mm, 1.6 mm, 1.8 mm and 2.0 mm long and 100 μm wide BA ICLs with AlGaAsSb claddings. In the subplot, the corresponding EDQEs are shown. (c) Dependences of inverse EDQEs of the ICLs with SL and AlGaAsSb claddings on the cavity lengths.

The reciprocal values of EDQEs at a current density of 1000 A/cm² are depicted in Figure 5.1.2.7 (c) for different cavity lengths. Facet reflectivity for the average refractive index of the active region $n_{rAR} \approx 3.5$ is $R = 0.31$. Taking to account the measured EDQEs, the total absorption losses and internal quantum efficiency (IQE) can be extracted from the following equation [122]

$$\frac{1}{EDQE} = \frac{1}{\eta_i} \left(1 + \frac{\alpha_w L}{\ln \frac{1}{R}} \right) \quad (5.1.2.1)$$

The obtained IQE of the ICL with SL and bulk claddings were $\eta_{iSL} = 0.177$ and $\eta_{iBulk} = 0.203$, whereas their respective absorption losses were $FCA_{SL} = 4.8 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $FCA_{SL} = 7.3 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The IQEs of the two ICLs are similar but notably below values of state-of-the-art [31], [122] due to high threshold current densities. On contrary, the difference between absorption losses is evident, although slightly lower than calculated (5.6 cm^{-1} and 8.0 cm^{-1}). The values are reasonably close, nevertheless small deviations could be caused by fitting approximations of electro-optical characteristics and reliability of the theoretical values of electron mobilities.

Figures 5.1.2.8 (a) and (b) present the temperature series of emission spectra of the ICLs with SL and bulk AlGaAsSb claddings respectively. The central wavelengths were $\lambda_{SL} = 4.93 \mu\text{m}$ and $\lambda_{Bulk} = 5.04 \mu\text{m}$ and the temperature gradient of the wavelength is $2.25 \text{ nm}/^\circ\text{C}$ for both ICLs.

Figure 5.1.2.8. Spectra at 25, 35 and 45 °C of BA (2mm x 100 μm) devices for ICL with SL claddings [in (a)] and the ICL with bulk AlGaAsSb claddings [in (b)]. The central wavelengths at RT are 4.93 and 5.04 μm , respectively.

The slightly longer wavelength of the ICL with bulk claddings additionally but marginally increases the FCA that would be higher than in ICL with SL claddings even if the wavelengths were exactly the same. Despite that, the ICL with bulk claddings have shown a superior

threshold current density. A direct comparison of the two ICLs with the same active region design and two different cladding materials was made. Theoretically, the ICL with bulk claddings has a higher optical confinement in the active region, but also FCA losses. Experimentally, the ICL has shown lower threshold current density and slightly higher characteristic temperature, but on a contrary, higher threshold power density and lower voltage efficiency. As mentioned before, it is likely a consequence of high leakage currents coming from unpassivised sidewalls and of high series resistance coming from the suboptimal design of TLs and doping of the cap layer. AlGaAsSb/GaSb TLs could be replaced with AlSb/InAs SLs to avoid need for unevenness of the doping levels between two adjacent GaSb-containing layers. Alternatively, the problem could be resolved by using an MBE system with two Ga cells. Further optimization of the active region and growth conditions along with replacing the GaSb cap layer with highly doped InAs could lead to a significant improvement of all figures of merit. Although the ultimate superiority of one design cannot be resolved at this point, this study has shown both advantages and disadvantages of the two species of claddings for an arbitrary ICL emitting at 5 μm .

5.2. ICLs with hybrid superlattice plasmon-enhanced claddings

In this subchapter, an impact of bulk, plasmon-enhanced InAs(Sb) claddings on performance of the ICLs is discussed. In the first section, the features of plasmon-enhanced InAs(Sb) materials are analyzed in respect to doping concentration. In the second section, the theoretical comparison between ICLs with the analog active region and hybrid cladding structure but different substrates, and hence different plasmon-enhanced materials, was made in terms of the optical confinement. In the third section, a high-performance GaSb-based ICL with hybrid cladding architecture is presented. The results shown on figure 5.2.1.1 (a) and 5.2.5.2 are obtained from energy dispersion in k-space obtained by 8 k·p calculation in nextnano³. The results depicted in figures 5.2.2.2, 5.2.2.3, 5.2.3.1 (a), 5.2.3.1 (b), 5.2.3.2 (a), 5.2.3.2 (b), 5.2.3.3 (a), 5.2.3.3. (b) and 5.2.5.1 were obtained from solving the real and imaginary parts of the Lorentz-Drude equation. The results shown in figures 5.2.1.1. (b), 5.2.1.1. (c), 5.2.1.2, 5.2.2.4, 5.2.3.1 (c), 5.2.3.1 (d), 5.2.3.2 (c), 5.2.3.2 (d), 5.2.3.3 (c), 5.2.3.3 (d) are obtained by solving the Lorentz-Drude equation. The results presented in figures 5.2.4.1, 5.2.4.2, 5.2.4.3, 5.2.4.4, 5.2.4.5, 5.2.4.6, 5.2.5.3, 5.2.5.4, 5.2.5.5, 5.2.5.6 and 5.2.5.7 are experimental.

5.2.1. Plasmon-enhanced claddings for ICLs

As shown in the previous subchapter, the state-of-the-art InAs/AlSb could be successfully substituted by bulk claddings. At longer wavelengths, the need for higher optical confinement increases for various reasons. For once, the gain reduces due to lower carrier confinement in QWs of the recombination region, whereas the FCA losses increase quadratically with wavelength. In addition, linewidth of the optical mode becomes broader, hence the mode leakage to the claddings and the substrate becomes higher. For this reason, longer claddings are needed to minimize absorption losses caused by the portion of the mode that leaks into the n-type doped substrate. In last decade, remarkable improvements of the laser performance and wavelength range have been achieved by introducing heavily doped plasmon-enhanced

claddings on InAs substrates [117], [118], [119], [123], [124], [125], [126]. The highly doped bulk InAs inherits a metallic property from its high n-type doping. At high electron density, the electron cloud can partially or completely screen the electromagnetic field of the emitted light of sufficiently long wavelength. At this point, the highly doped waveguide provides a strong internal reflection as the refractive index significantly reduces. Due to its high doping and consequently FCA, monolithic plasmon-enhanced claddings were not possible to implement. Instead, a portion of the cladding closer to the active region was kept the same as the state-of-the-art, to separate the area of a high optical mode confinement from lossy plasmon-enhanced claddings. Use of plasmon-enhanced claddings in combination with 22 cascade stages of the active region, extended the range of RT operation of ICLs to $\approx 7 \mu\text{m}$ [123]. At cryogenic temperatures, plasmon-enhanced claddings enabled the emission for wavelength as long as $11.1 \mu\text{m}$ in 2015 [124] (at 130 K). A combination of plasmon-enhanced InAs with inner InAs/AlSb claddings in ICLs extended emission range to $13.2 \mu\text{m}$ in 2022 [125] (at 115 K). An additional improvement of the electron confinement has been made by introduction of additional pair of InAsP barriers in the active region, which further extended the window of emission wavelength to $14.4 \mu\text{m}$ in 2023 [126] (at 120 K). Besides for extending the wavelength range, InAs hybrid claddings were implemented to ICLs with shorter emission wavelengths ($\sim 5.1 - 5.3 \mu\text{m}$) [118], [119], [127], ($\sim 4.6 \mu\text{m}$) [128] and ($\sim 3.7 \mu\text{m}$) [129] to increase their maximum operation temperature or to reduce the threshold current density. Although implementation of hybrid claddings to ICLs has shown an outstanding progress, high performance ICLs in terms of low threshold or maximum emitted wavelength are demonstrated only for InAs-based ICLs. By introducing 8.5 % portion of Sb in InAsSb, thick bulk claddings can be grown lattice-matched on GaSb substrates. Figure 5.2.1.1. (a) depicts the energy dispersions of the ground states in bulk InAs and InAsSb, calculated by k-p model in software nextnano³. The bandgap of n^+ -InAsSb lower than InAs and it becomes transparent for wavelength range $\lambda \geq 4.3 \mu\text{m}$, whereas pure InAs is transparent for $\lambda \geq 3.5 \mu\text{m}$. In this chapter, the chosen wavelength is $4.6 \mu\text{m}$ as just long enough to fit in atmospheric transparency windows of both InAs and InAsSb, and as a spectral line of a poisonous gas, carbon-oxide (CO). The refractive index dispersions calculated from Lorentz-Drude model presented in Figure 5.2.1.1.(b) for different doping concentrations. Refractive index reaches zero at wavelengths longer or equal to the plasmonic (cut-off) wavelength. At longer emission wavelengths (smaller photon energies), free electrons completely screen the electromagnetic field of the light. Due to the higher convexity of the dispersion and hence the lower effective mass (m_e^*), at the same wavelength, the refractive index of InAsSb is lower than of InAs. Complementarily, the same refractive index can be achieved in InAsSb at lower doping concentration than in InAs at a fixed wavelength. Assuming a doping concentration of $1 \cdot 10^{19} \text{cm}^{-3}$ the refractive indices of InAs and n^+ -InAsSb are $n_{r\text{InAs}} = 3.10$ and $n_{r\text{InAsSb}} = 2.88$. The Figure 5.2.1.1. (c) shows the differences between their refractive indices at different doping concentrations. The difference between refractive indices is positive for the wavelength up to the cut-off wavelength of InAs, whereas its maximum coincides with the cut-off wavelength of $\text{InAs}_{0.915}\text{Sb}_{0.085}$. Aside from the refractive index, FCA of the claddings plays an important role in laser performance. Figure 5.2.1.2. displays refractive indices and FCAs of InAs and $\text{InAs}_{0.915}\text{Sb}_{0.085}$ for different charge carrier densities at the desired wavelength.

Figure 5.2.1.1. (a) Band dispersion of InAs and $\text{InAs}_{0.915}\text{Sb}_{0.085}$ (b) Dispersion of refractive indices for different doping concentrations of n^+ -InAs and n^+ -InAsSb (c) Differences between refractive indices of n^+ -InAs and n^+ -InAsSb for different doping concentrations.

Figure 5.2.1.2. Charge carrier density dependence of refractive index of InAs and $\text{InAs}_{0.915}\text{Sb}_{0.085}$ and their corresponding FCA losses.

Refractive indices decrease linearly with increasing carrier concentration. FCA of the two materials at different charge carrier densities are obtained by taking into account a non-linear dependence of carrier mobility (μ_e) on charge carrier density (N) expressed by modified Hilsum formula [111], introduced for highly doped InAs by A. Baranov [110],

$$\mu_e = \frac{3 \cdot 10^4 \text{ cm}^2/\text{Vs}}{1 + \left(\frac{N}{8 \cdot 10^{17}}\right)^{0.75}}. \quad (5.2.1)$$

From the carrier mobility, the FCA losses are determined by equation 3.1.2.1.7.

FCA losses demonstrated an exponential increase for increasing carrier density in InAs and InAs_{0.915}Sb_{0.085}. A notably higher loss in InAs_{0.915}Sb_{0.085} is a consequence of its lower effective mass. These results will later enable calculations of FCA in plasmon-enhanced claddings incorporated in the ICL.

5.2.2. Model comparison of InAs-based and GaSb-based ICLs

Due to its lower refractive index, highly doped InAs_{0.915}Sb_{0.085} is a promising candidate for an outer cladding of GaSb-based ICL. To validate its advantage, a comparison between the analogous InAs and GaSb-based ICL structures must be made. The analysed cladding structure of the ICL from Ref. [128] performed with threshold current density below 300 A/cm². Figure 5.2.2.1. (a) displays its cladding design. Figure 5.2.2.1. (b) presents a design with the same geometry, but InAs_{0.915}Sb_{0.085} outer claddings, and GaSb-based SCLs, for ICL grown on GaSb substrate. The total thickness of the hybrid claddings is 1.7 μm , consisting of $\approx 1 \mu\text{m}$ inner InAs/AlSb SL (211 periods of 2.43 nm InAs/2.3 nm AlSb), and 0.7 μm thick outer plasmon-enhanced claddings. The doping level in InAs layers of the SL claddings is linearly decreasing from $1 \cdot 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ to $1 \cdot 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, while the outer plasmon-enhanced claddings are doped with $1 \cdot 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. The two analog ICL structures are compared in terms of optical mode confinement factors in the active region and the total FCA losses. Figure 5.2.2.2. (a) contrasts refractive index

Figure 5.2.2.1. Layouts of ICL structures with hybrid claddings: (a) InAs-based ICL with inner InAs/AlSb SL and outer highly doped n^+ -InAs (b) GaSb-based ICL with inner InAs/AlSb SL and outer highly doped n^+ -InAsSb claddings.

(n_r) profiles and respective relative mode intensities (R. I.) of the InAs-based and GaSb-based ICL with hybrid claddings. The optical mode in GaSb-based ICLs is narrower and more strongly confined in the active region. Figures 5.2.2.2 (b) and (c) display distribution of the confinement factors in different layers species of both ICLs along the growth direction. The confinement factor in the active region of the GaSb-based ICL is 3.8 % higher than in the active region of the InAs-based ICL. This is not only a consequence of a lower refractive index of highly n-type doped n^+ -InAsSb of $n_r = 2.88$ than of equally doped n^+ -InAs outer claddings ($n_r = 3.10$) but also of a higher refractive index of GaSb SCLs. For the sake of distinguishing individual contributions to the overall improvement, the InAs-based ICL structure has been contrasted to a hypothetical InAs-based ICL of the same geometry and GaSb SCLs. Although such structure is not possible to be successfully grown due to compressive strain of bulk GaSb layers, its optical mode profile is simulated and presented in Figure 5.2.2.3.

Figure 5.2.2.2. (a) Refractive index profiles and optical mode intensities along the growth direction of two ICLs with the same active region design but different claddings and SCLs: InAs-based ICL, with hybrid InAs/AISb – InAs plasmon-enhanced claddings and InAs SCLs (green) and GaSb-based ICL, with hybrid InAs/AISb – InAsSb plasmon-enhanced claddings with GaSb SCLs (red) (b) Optical mode confinement distribution along the growth direction of the InAs-based ICL (c) Optical mode confinement distribution along the growth direction of the GaSb-based ICL.

The confinement factor in the active region shows an improvement of 1.9 % in comparison to the original InAs-based structure, suggesting an equal contribution between low index n^+ -InAsSb and high index GaSb SCLs. Taking to account optical confinement factors (Γ), effective masses [52], [110], mobilities [110], [112], [114], [130] and doping concentrations listed in Table 5.2.2.1,

the total FCA losses can be calculated as sum of individual losses in SL claddings, plasmon-enhanced claddings, SCLs and the active region. As the doping concentration is linearly dependent on the growth direction coordinate (x) in SL claddings and constant in the remaining layer species, the overall FCA losses can be calculated as follows from equation 5.1.1 of subchapter 5.1.1:

$$FCA_{\text{total}} = \int \alpha_{SL}(x) d\Gamma_{SL}(x) + \alpha_{InAs(Sb)+} \Gamma_{InAs(Sb)+} + \alpha_{SCL} \Gamma_{SCL} + \alpha_{AR} \Gamma_{AR} \quad (5.2.2.1)$$

Figure 5.2.2.3. Optical mode confinement distribution along the growth direction of a hypothetical GaSb-based ICL structure with outer n^+ -InAs plasmon-enhanced claddings.

The obtained FCA of InAs-based ICL is $\alpha = 5.0 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which is 15.3 % lower than of GaSb-based ICL, $\alpha = 5.9 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Figure 5.2.2.4 shows the FCA losses in the corresponding layer species of both ICLs.

	InAs SCLs	GaSb SCLs	SL cladd.	InAs+	InAsSb+	AR
$N \text{ (cm}^{-3}\text{)}$	6E16	6E16	1E17- 1E18	1E19	1E19	4E18
n_r	3.49	3.71	3.39	3.10	2.88	3.55
$m_e^* (m_0)$	0.026	0.039	0.081	0.072	0.049	0.062
$\mu_e \text{ (cm}^2\text{/Vs)}$	26200	2900	10000	3920	4010	7900
$FCA_{InAs} \text{ (cm}^{-1}\text{)}$	0.405	/	0.83	1.13	/	2.66
$FCA_{GaSb} \text{ (cm}^{-1}\text{)}$	/	1.69	0.564	/	0.84	2.76

Table 5.2.2.1. Doping levels, refractive indices, effective masses, mobilities and FCA losses in the SCLs, SL claddings, outer plasmon-enhanced claddings and the active region of the ICLs.

As presented, FCA losses in GaSb SCLs are approximately 4 times higher than in InAs SCLs. This is a consequence of a higher confinement factor and approximately 9 times lower mobility than in InAs. Although mobilities of n^+ -InAs and n^+ -InAsSb are almost equal ($\mu \approx 4000 \text{ cm}^2/\text{Vs}$), FCA in n^+ -InAsSb is higher because of its lower effective mass. However, as the confinement factor in outer n^+ -InAs claddings is 3 times higher than in n^+ -InAsSb, FCA loss in outer claddings of the GaSb-based ICL are slightly lower than in InAs-based ICL. The GaSb-based ICL shows a lower loss in SL claddings, because of the lower confinement factor. Both ICLs have the same active region designed to emit at wavelength of $4.6 \mu\text{m}$. As discussed before in the chapter, the minimum VISA in the recombination region [76], [77] for similar wavelength, was obtained for the thickness of the hole $\text{Ga}_{0.6}\text{In}_{0.4}\text{Sb}$ hole QW of 2.50 nm, out of three values: 2.50, 3.00 and 3.50 nm.

Figure 5.2.2.4. Distribution of FCA losses over different species of layers in InAs-based and GaSb-based ICLs.

For this reason, this thickness was chosen and implemented. The refractive index, carrier density and mobility of the active region were averaged over the containing layers. The FCA losses in the active region of both ICLs are approximately equal. By putting the obtained aggregate FCA losses and optical confinement factors of the active region into the equation, the corresponding gain thresholds can be obtained from sums of facet losses (α_f) and respective FCA losses (α_{FCA}) as:

$$\Gamma_{InAs} g_{th_{InAs}} = \alpha_f + \alpha_{FCA-InAs} = \frac{1}{2L} \ln\left(\frac{1}{R^2}\right) + \alpha_{FCA-InAs}$$

$$\Gamma_{GaSb} g_{th_{GaSb}} = \alpha_f + \alpha_{FCA-GaSb} = \frac{1}{2L} \ln\left(\frac{1}{R^2}\right) + \alpha_{FCA-GaSb}$$

(5.2.2.2)

Considering $L = 2 \text{ mm}$ long cavities, the obtained threshold gains of the two ICLs are equal, $g_{th_{InAs}} = g_{th_{GaSb}} = 36 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The equal threshold gain suggest that the higher optical confinement gets compensated by higher FCA losses and vice-versa.

5.2.3. Cladding design variation of GaSb-based ICL

In this section, influence of individual cladding parameters of the ICL on the optical confinement factors is studied theoretically. Room for possible improvements of cladding design of the GaSb-based ICL could be investigated by analysing changes of the confinement factor and FCA for variation of individual layer species in the cladding structure.

Figures 5.2.3.1. (a) and (b) present the distribution of optical confinement factors for varying thickness of the outer n^+ -InAsSb, for a constant overall thickness of claddings.

Figure 5.2.3.1. (a), (b) Dependence of optical mode confinement factors in GaSb-based hybrid cladding ICL on the thickness of n^+ -InAsSb outer claddings for overall cladding thickness of 1.7 μm (c)

Dependences of FCA losses in claddings, SCLs and active region of GaSb-based n^+ -InAsSb hybrid cladding ICL on the thickness of n^+ -InAsSb outer claddings for overall cladding thickness of 1.7 μm (d) Dependence of the total FCA losses in the GaSb-based hybrid cladding ICL on the thickness of outer claddings for overall cladding thickness of 1.7 μm .

The simulation was carried out for outer cladding thicknesses corresponding to 20/30/40/50/60/70/80 % of the total cladding thickness. With n^+ -InAsSb claddings, the respective optical confinement factor exponentially increases, while for inner SL claddings it parabolically decreases. The increase of confinement factor of the active region and SCLs with increasing thickness of n^+ -InAsSb are almost linear. From Figures 5.2.3.1. (c) and (d) that depict distribution of the FCA losses in different layer species and the total FCA losses respectively, there is a trade-off between high optical confinement factor and low FCA losses. As shown in Figure 5.2.3.1. (c), individual FCA losses in active region, inner SL and outer n^+ -InAsSb claddings increase linearly with thickness of n^+ -InAsSb, whereas the loss in n^+ -InAsSb claddings increase as its confinement factor. For thickness lower than 1020 nm, the FCA losses are highest in the active region, while at longer n^+ -InAsSb claddings, the losses in them become dominant. From the Figure 5.2.3.1. (d), the total FCA losses are exponentially increasing with InAsSb thickness. A pronounced increase of the slope is observed for InAsSb thicker than 850 nm (50 %). There is a trade-off between higher optical mode and lower FCA in the range from 340 nm (20 %) to 850 nm (50 %), as therefore an ideal thickness of n^+ -InAsSb cannot be identified. The thickness of 340 nm provides 24.3 % lower FCA losses than 850 nm, but also a 4.9 % lower optical confinement factor in the active region.

As demonstrated in previous subchapter, design of SCLs is also significant for the optical confinement in the active region. Figure 5.2.3.2. (a) and (b) display distribution of optical confinement factors in different layer species of the ICL for various thicknesses of SCLs. For thicknesses increasing in range 50 nm to 150 nm, the optical confinement factor in the active region increases, reaches its peak at 150 nm. For SCL thicker than 150 nm, the confinement starts decreasing parabolically. In the SCLs, confinement sub-linearly increases, whereas in the n^+ -InAsSb claddings and inner SL claddings it exponentially decreases. In Figure 5.2.3.2. (c), distribution of the respective FCA losses is shown. For SCLs shorter than 150 nm, losses dominantly originate from the outer n^+ -InAsSb as they get closer to the active region. At longer SCLs, the losses in the active region become dominant. FCA in the SCLs, inner SL claddings and the active region resemble trends of the respective confinement factors. With longer SCLs, the optical mode redistributes from claddings towards SCLs and the active region. Despite 7.4 % lower confinement in the active region than maximum value, achieved at 150 nm, thickness of 400 nm provides 26.3 % lower FCA losses. In addition, at 400 nm thickness, the (tail) mode intensity in the vicinity of the high loss GaSb substrate is in the same range of values as in state-of-the-art ICLs with SL claddings, whereas for 150 nm, it is an order of magnitude higher. A higher penetration of the optical mode to the substrate, reduces overall mode intensity which suggests that 400 nm thick SCLs is a more promising choice. Number of the cascade stages in the active region directly determines its thickness, thus also its confinement factor. The ideal number of cascade stages, however, is not only a result of the trade-off between optical confinement and FCA losses. It is dominantly influenced by the emission wavelength considering the rule of thumb for the threshold voltage of 2 V. Following that criterion, for the wavelength of 4.6 μm , the optimal number of stages would be 7. With every additional stage, an additional

photon per injected electron would be generated, but it would also increase the threshold voltage and threshold power density.

Figure 5.2.3.2 (a) (b) Dependence of optical mode confinement factors in different layers of GaSb-based hybrid cladding ICL on the thickness of SCLs (c) Dependence of FCA losses in claddings, SCLs and the active region on the thickness of GaSb SCLs (d) Dependence of the total FCA losses in claddings, SCLs on the active region on the thickness of GaSb SCLs.

In Figures 5.2.3.3. (a) and (b), the optical mode confinements are presented for different number of cascade stages. By adding more stages, the confinement in outer n^+ -InAsSb claddings, inner SL claddings and SCLs almost linearly decreases, whereas in the active region it increases because of its widening. Figure 5.2.3.3. (c) depicts distribution of FCA in outer InAsSb claddings, inner SL claddings, SCLs and the active region over the number of stages. FCA losses in outer n^+ -InAsSb claddings, inner SL claddings and SCLs are decreasing, while the losses in the active

region increase. In ICLs with less than 7 stages, FCA losses from the SCLs are dominant, while with more stages, losses originate mainly from the active region. The loss in the SL claddings is approximately constant for varying number of stages.

Figure 5.2.3.3. (a), (b) Optical mode confinement factors in different parts of the GaSb-based hybrid claddings ICL for different number of cascade stages in the active region (c) Dependence of FCA losses in claddings, SCLs and the active region on the number of cascade stages (d) Total FCA losses in claddings, SCLs and the active region of GaSb-based hybrid cladding ICL for different number of cascade stages.

Figure 5.2.3.3 (d) present the aggregate FCA losses of the ICL with increasing number of stages. The trend of the losses is following the dominant losses from the active region. By a direct comparison between 12 stages design of an ICL reported in [119], with the design with 7 stages, there is a higher mode confinement by 44.7 %, but higher FCA losses by 8.4 % as well. Based purely on optical confinement, 15 stages design is even superior, as every additional cascade stage is beneficial for the threshold current density. Nevertheless, taking to account that useful voltage would be higher than double in comparison to 7, this would cause a significant increase

in threshold power density. The 12 stages design was, therefore, taken as a reasonable compromise between 7 and 15 stages.

5.2.4. Performance comparison of InAs-based and GaSb-based ICLs

The growth of the InAs and GaSb-based ICLs is explained in detail in Appendix B of this dissertation. Similarly to the previous sections, the primary characterization was carried out. The doping profiles of the two ICLs, measured by SIMS are presented in Figures 5.2.4.1 (a) and (b). The figure shows reasonable matching of doping concentrations in the corresponding cladding layers of the two ICLs, that are labelled. Figure 5.2.4.2. displays HR-XRD scans of the grown ICLs that indicate lattice mismatches of inner SL claddings of 330 ppm (InAs-based ICL) and -185 ppm (GaSb-based ICL), indicating good compensation of internal strain.

Figure 5.2.4.1. Densities of Si ions of InAs-based ICL (a) and Si and Te ions of GaSb-based ICL (b) in the growth direction of an ICL. Doping density of InAs wells in claddings are linearly increasing from SCLs towards outside. First and the last 10 nm of each SCL is doped higher than the middle of SCL. The SCLs are doped by Si in InAs-based and by Te in GaSb-based ICL. The doping density in the electron injector QWs is averaged over the active region.

The mismatch of n^+ -InAsSb claddings of GaSb-based ICL was -560 ppm. Period thicknesses of the active region and claddings of both InAs and GaSb-based ICL show high precision of up to 3 % error margin. After the growth, 2 mm long and 100 μm BA devices were fabricated by photolithography, for pulsed mode characterization. The power-voltage-current measurements were performed at a repetition rate of 1 kHz and the pulse width of 500 ns. In Figures 5.2.4.3. (a) and (b) electro-optical characteristics of BA InAs-based and GaSb-based ICLs at various temperatures, are depicted. The voltage-current density and output power-current density characteristics are displayed on the corresponding axes as labelled. At the same current, the voltage decreases at higher temperatures because of temperature induced reduction of the band gap, hence also the reduced overall voltage. RT threshold current density of InAs-based ICL was $J_{th} = 424 \text{ A/cm}^2$, whereas of GaSb-based ICL was $J_{th} = 359 \text{ A/cm}^2$.

Figure 5.2.4.2. X-ray diffractogram of the (a) InAs-based ICL (b) GaSb-based ICL with inner SL claddings and outer plasmon-enhanced claddings indicating almost strain-compensated growth.

These thresholds are higher than state-of-the-art ICLs of similar wavelengths, as some of previously reported values are approximately 300 A/cm^2 . The lowest threshold current densities of ICLs with wavelengths in $4.3 \text{ }\mu\text{m} - 4.8 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ window of 247 A/cm^2 (at $4.38 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$) [76], 247 A/cm^2 (at $4.6 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$) [128], and 220 A/cm^2 (at $4.77 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$) [78] are substantially lower than obtained in this study. Reported maximum operating temperatures in literature were also higher: $T_{max} = 96 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [118] and $T_{max} = 106 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [119]. This could suggest suboptimal growth conditions, predominantly flux ratio of group III/group V elements. Although there is room for improvement in terms of design and growth conditions, it is not crucial for this general comparison. Reaching record low threshold current densities requires optimal combination of parameters. This, however, might not be reproducible and sustainable over one growth campaign to calibrate all the parameters for growth on two different substrates. The obtained differential resistance of the InAs-based ICL of $2.8 \text{ }\Omega$ and GaSb-based ICL of $2.3 \text{ }\Omega$ are slightly higher than the usual $1\text{-}2 \text{ }\Omega$, which could be caused by too low doping of the SCLs. Threshold voltages of InAs-based ICL of $V_{th} = 5.53 \text{ V}$ and Ga-Sb based ICL of $V_{th} = 6.24 \text{ V}$ are higher than reported values at similar wavelengths [79], [119] which results in lower voltage efficiencies of $\eta_V = 59.0 \text{ }\%$ and $\eta_V = 49.6 \text{ }\%$ respectively. Higher threshold voltage (lower voltage efficiency) of GaSb-based ICL is a consequence of the larger conduction band offsets between SCLs and their adjacent layers [117]. Due to the lower threshold voltage, threshold power densities of InAs-based ICL of $P_{th} = 2.4 \text{ kW/cm}^2$ is comparable to the threshold power density of the GaSb-based ICL of $P_{th} = 2.4 \text{ kW/cm}^2$. The slope efficiency of InAs-based ICL drops from 167 to 59 mW/A , while for GaSb-based it varies from 236 to 84 mW/A . The reason for $15.3 \text{ }\%$ lower threshold current density of the GaSb-based ICL might be the higher optical mode confinement in the active region but could also originate from the leakage current as there was no sidewall passivation involved in the BA ridge processing. Considering non-ideal voltage-current diode characteristics of InAs-based and GaSb-based ICL at RT displayed in Figure 5.2.4.3. (c), there is a presence of a leakage currents.

Figure 5.2.4.3. Pulsed light-current and light-voltage characteristic at different temperatures for 2 mm long and 100 μm wide BA lasers: (a) InAs-based ICL (b) GaSb-based ICL displayed at respective axes as labelled. (c) Voltage characteristics of the BA ICLs with linear fits of their leakage components and labelled leakage currents at respective threshold voltages (d) Temperature dependences of threshold current densities of InAs-based ICL and GaSb-based ICL and extracted characteristic temperatures T_0 .

The ohmic behaviour of leakage currents is approximated by linear slopes of the respective voltage-current density characteristics. The leakage currents are corresponding to the respective threshold voltages. As it is shown in Figure 5.2.4.3. (c) there is a higher leakage current in InAs-based ICL. The linear fits of electrical characteristics of the ICL are made at zero voltage to roughly estimate leakage components of currents. The leakage current components can be read out for corresponding threshold voltages. The 35 A/cm^2 higher leakage current density of the InAs-based ICL effectively reduces the difference in measured threshold to approximately 30 A/cm^2 which could be attributed to a possible fluctuation of the growth

parameters. Figure 5.2.4.3. (d) depicts the respective temperature dependencies of threshold current densities of the two ICLs with extracted characteristic temperatures of $T_0 = 34.4$ K (InAs-based ICL) and $T_0 = 43.7$ K (GaSb-based ICL). The higher characteristic temperature of GaSb-based ICL indicates a higher thermal stability, however this could be mitigated by assuming presence of leakage currents. Its value is in the range of reported characteristic temperatures at similar wavelengths [76], [79], [118], [119], [128]. The obtained values of the discussed figures of merit as well as the corresponding reported values in literature are listed in the table 5.2.4.1.

	J_{th} (A/cm ²)	P_{th} (kW/cm ²)	V_{th} (V)	Stages	T_0 (K)	T_{max} (°C)	λ (μm)
InAs-based	434	2.40	5.53	12	34.4	55	4.55
GaSb-based	359	2.24	6.24	12	43.7	55	4.81
Ref. [79]	220	0.78	3.54	8	43	102	4.77
Ref. [127]	247			10-15	46-57	104	4.6
Ref. [76]	247			6	50.4		4.38
Ref. [117]	306			10	49	96	5.17
Ref. [118]	252	≈0.9	≈3.6	10		106	4.63

Table 5.2.4.1. Figures of merit of the InAs and GaSb-based ICL and literature values at similar wavelengths.

The Figure 5.2.4.4. presents measured threshold current densities of an ensemble of BA ridges of both ICLs. The threshold current densities of 8 laser bars of GaSb-based ICL and 9 laser bars of InAs-based ICL are depicted.

Figure 5.2.4.4. Threshold current densities at pulsed operation of different 2 mm long and 100 μm wide BA devices: InAs-based ICL (green) and GaSb-based ICL (red).

The average threshold current density of the GaSb-based ICL is lower than of InAs-based ICLs by 14.5 % which is approximately matching to the relative difference of the lowest threshold current densities of the respective ICLs. To estimate the FCA absorption of the measured BA devices, and to validate the previous calculations, two series of laser bars of lengths 1.4 mm, 1.7 mm and 2.0 mm were cleaved and measured in pulsed mode. Figures 5.2.4.5 (a) and (b) the current density-optical power characteristics of InAs-based and GaSb-based ICL are depicted. At the constant threshold current density, the power-current density slope increases with cavity length as the contact area increases. Assuming linear slopes of the power-current density, EDQEs were extracted, and they remain constant after reaching the thresholds. According to equation 5.1.2.1, EDQE decreases with cavity length as depicted in the subplots of Figures 5.2.4.5 (a) and (b).

Figure 5.2.4.5. Pulsed light-current density characteristics of 1.4 mm, 1.7 mm and 2.0 mm long ridges of the (a) InAs-based ICL, (b) GaSb-based ICL. In the subplots, the corresponding EDQEs are shown. (c) Dependences of the inverse EDQE in InAs and GaSb-based ICL on the length of the laser cavity.

Figure 5.2.4.5. (c) shows linear dependencies of inverse EDQEs on reciprocal values of the laser cavity. Considering the average refractive index of the active region of $n_r = 3.5$, hence assuming facet reflectivity of $R \approx 0.31$, FCA losses and internal quantum efficiencies (IQEs) can be extracted from the slope and cut on y-axis respectively. The FCA loss of the GaSb-based ICL of 5.8 cm^{-1} matches well to the calculated value (5.9 cm^{-1}), while the FCA of the InAs-based ICL of 4.6 cm^{-1} is slightly lower than calculated (5.0 cm^{-1}). Additionally, IQE of the two ICLs are approximately

equal, 11.4 % for InAs-based ICL and 11.2 % for GaSb based ICL. The values of IQEs were substantially below the reported values in literature [118], [119] which can be attributed to above average threshold current densities and the leakage currents. Figure 5.2.4.6 presents lasing spectra at different temperatures of the InAs-based ICL (a) and GaSb-based ICL (b). The GaSb-based ICL showed the central wavelength at RT of 4.81 μm , which is slightly longer than measured for InAs-based ICL, 4.55 μm . This is caused by either fluctuation of growth rates or the tensile strain-induced reduction of bandgap in InAs layers of W-shaped QW. The temperature induced shift for GaSb-based ICL was 3.95 $\text{nm}/^\circ\text{C}$, whereas for InAs-based ICL was 4.42 $\text{nm}/^\circ\text{C}$. Considering the measured central wavelengths, the corrected FCAs of the actual devices are then 6.4 cm^{-1} for the GaSb-based ICL, and 4.9 cm^{-1} for the InAs-based ICL, which are still slightly higher than measured values (5.8 cm^{-1} and 4.6 cm^{-1} respectively).

Figure 5.2.4.6. Spectra at 10 $^\circ\text{C}$, 20 $^\circ\text{C}$ and 30 $^\circ\text{C}$ of BA (2 mm x 100 μm) devices: (a) InAs-based ICL, the central wavelength at RT is 4.55 μm and the temperature shift is 3.95 $\text{nm}/^\circ\text{C}$ (b) GaSb-based ICL, the central wavelength at RT is 4.81 μm and the temperature shift is 4.42 $\text{nm}/^\circ\text{C}$.

In summary, the ICL structures grown on InAs and GaSb substrates were compared both theoretically and experimentally. Because of the lower refractive index of outer plasmon-enhanced claddings and higher refractive index of the SCLs, GaSb-based ICL shows a higher confinement of the optical mode in the active region. On contrary, InAs-based ICLs shows lower overall FCA losses. The calculations have shown that advantages of both designs lead to the approximately same threshold gain. Experimentally, however, GaSb-based ICL has performed with a lower threshold current density, however while taking leakage currents to account, threshold current densities of the two ICLs are comparable.

5.2.5. Low threshold GaSb-based ICL

In the previous chapter a comparative analysis between InAs and GaSb-based ICL has been made. Though a superior modal optical overlap was obtained for GaSb-based ICL, a high-performance hybrid cladding ICLs has not yet been demonstrated. The lowest threshold current density ($J_{th} = 98 \text{ A}/\text{cm}^2$) of an ICL, at “sweet spot” wavelength was obtained for a regular SL cladding design, by increasing number of stages to 10 [56]. In addition, it was shown that the characteristic temperature becomes higher with number of cascade stages, which is a consequence of lowering threshold current. Nevertheless, due to the high refractive index ($n_r =$

3.39) of AlSb/InAs SL, no RT emission of GaSb-based ICLs without plasmon-enhanced claddings was reported at wavelengths longer than 6.8 μm [131]. Since a spectral line of nitrous oxide (NO), the byproduct of fossil fuels, shows absorption at 5.2 μm , this wavelength is of a particular interest for controlling the air pollution. The first cw operation of a distributed feedback (DFB) laser at 5.2 μm was demonstrated in 2014 [132]. Previously reported threshold current densities in pulsed operation at RT for 10 stages [127] and 5 stages [82] ICLs were 1.3 kA/cm^2 and 650 A/cm^2 , respectively. A major improvement was reported in 2015 [116], [117] for 5 stages ICLs, as the lowest reported threshold current density at such wavelength was 280 A/cm^2 . Considering a low refractive index of n^+ -InAsSb even at shorter wavelengths as shown in Figure 5.2.1.1, high-performance ICLs with hybrid cladding design appears promising. Particularly at 5.2 μm the refractive index of highly doped InAsSb is as low as 2.70. However, the advantage of hybrid cladding design over the SL cladding in ICLs is not yet validated. In this study, the same cladding design is applied to ICL with 7 stage active region with emission wavelength of 5.2 μm . The claddings composed of 0.7 μm long n^+ -InAsSb claddings and 1 μm long AlSb/InAs SL claddings were combined with 500 nm thick GaSb SCLs. To verify benefits of such claddings over the common SL claddings (3.3 μm and 2.0 μm long), their optical mode profiles are compared. In Figure 5.2.5.1. (a) the profiles of refractive indices (n_r) and relative mode intensities (R. I.) of the two ICLs with the same active region but different cladding structure, are presented. Similarly to comparison between with AlGaAsSb claddings, the mode in ICL with SL claddings is broader and less confined to the central part of the ICL, SCLs and the active region. Figure 5.2.5.1. (b) displays distribution of confinement factors in the ICL with hybrid claddings along the growth direction. It shows the same order of magnitude of the tail intensity as in the state-of-the-art ICLs, but there is 11.2 % higher optical confinement in the active region due to lower refractive indices of n^+ -InAsSb.

Figure 5.2.5.1. (a) Refractive index profiles and optical mode intensities along the growth direction of two ICLs with the same SCLs and active region design, but different cladding designs: standard InAs/AlSb

SL claddings (green) and hybrid AlSb/InAs – InAsSb plasmon-enhanced claddings (red) (b) Optical mode confinement distribution along the growth direction of the ICL with hybrid cladding designs.

From a comparison of the optical mode, it can also be concluded that the lower refractive index of n^+ -InAsSb allows reduction of cladding thickness. In addition, substituting a part of the AlSb/InAs SL of low thermal conductivity ($\kappa \approx 3$ W/m K) [109] with bulk n^+ -InAsSb of a higher thermal conductivity ($\kappa \approx 15$ W/m K) [109] in a hybrid cladding-based ICL is likely to improve heat dissipation. Conversely, based on the confinement factors as well as doping levels, effective masses [52], [110] and mobilities [110], [112], [114] and [130], the overall FCA in claddings and SCLs of the hybrid architecture ($\alpha = 5.9$ cm⁻¹) is higher than in ICL with SL claddings ($\alpha = 4.5$ cm⁻¹) This is caused by a higher mode confinement in SCLs and high optical losses in plasmon-enhanced claddings. The active region, designed for 5.2 μ m emission is composed InAs/Ga_{0.6}In_{0.4}Sb/InAs (2.12 nm/3.0 nm/1.98 nm) W-shaped QWs. As discussed in previous chapters, to mitigate absorption losses in the valence band, thickness of the hole, Ga_{0.6}In_{0.4}Sb QW needs to be chosen accordingly. As the study [76] has shown that in wavelength range of 4.8-5.4 μ m, the optimal thickness is 3.0 nm, this is the value implemented in the 5.2 μ m design. Thicknesses of InAs QWs were determined by the optimal wavefunction overlap. Thicknesses of both InAs and Ga_{0.6}In_{0.4}Sb were swept in the single band calculation of the band structure, by using finite difference method of the software nextnano³. The band parameters were taken from the Ref. [52]. Figure 5.2.5.2. (a) depicts the lasing wavelength vs variations of the GaInSb hole QW and InAs electron QW. In Figure 5.2.5.2. (b), the corresponding wavefunction overlap is presented for the same range of parameters. The emission wavelength increases with thicknesses of InAs, whereas it is significantly less sensitive to change of GaInSb QW due to higher effective mass of holes, and hence higher confinement. The wavefunction overlap decreases with increasing both InAs and GaInSb thicknesses, but again, it decreases more with variation of InAs wells. According to the calculation, it can further be noted that for a fixed wavelength the overlap integral is almost constant for various thicknesses of GaInSb, assuring that there is no sacrifice from pre-selecting its value (3.0 nm). Figure 5.2.5.3 (a) depicts the structure layout of the ICL.

Figure 5.2.5.2. (a) Dependence of the emission wavelength (a) and the corresponding wavefunction overlap (b) for a variation of the electron (InAs) and hole (Ga_{0.6}In_{0.4}Sb) QW widths. For a fixed wavelength, the wavefunction overlap remains constant and almost independent of the hole QW. The chosen design is labeled by the purple dot.

The laser was grown on n-type GaSb substrate (10^{18} cm^{-3}). The growth was carried out in the same order and substrate temperatures as the GaSb-based ICL from the previous subchapter. The active region of the ICL was composed of 8 stages of $\text{AlSb}/\text{InAs}/\text{GaInSb}/\text{InAs}/\text{AlSb}/\text{GaSb}/\text{AlSb}/\text{GaSb}/\text{AlSb}/\text{InAs}/\text{AlSb}/\text{InAs}/\text{AlSb}/\text{InAs}/\text{AlSb}/\text{InAs}$ (2.5/2.12/3.00/1.98/1.0/2.8/1.0/4.8/2.5/4.4/1.2/3.2/1.2/2.5/1.2/2.05) nm. For the sake of carrier rebalancing, the last three InAs wells were n-type doped by Si ($4 \cdot 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$). Like in previous subchapters, the number of stages was chosen based on “rule of thumb” of 2 V open circuit voltage. Adding more stages would increase the useful voltage and reduce the threshold current density. Consequently, the ohmic parasitic voltages would decrease and hence the voltage efficiency would increase. Nevertheless, increasing overall voltage would increase the threshold power as well. In Figure 5.2.5.3 (b) the HR-XRD diffractogram is shown. Period thicknesses of the active region and claddings show precision of 98.8 % and 98.3 % respectively. GaSb substrate and outer n^+ -InAsSb cladding peaks show an excellent lattice matching with a spacing of only 0.046° (mismatch of 720 ppm). Satellite peaks of the SL claddings are also labeled in Figure 5.2.5.3. The zeroth order SL reflex precisely coincides with the peak of GaSb substrate indicating that strain of the SL is fully compensated. The crystal quality of the grown ICL was excellent as fringes originating from the active region are visible up to approximately the 20th order on the low-angle side of the substrate peak, while on the high-angle side, they are clearly discernible up to the 14th order. The asymmetry in fringe visibility is commonly observed and results from factors such as differential damping of interference fringes at higher diffraction angles.

Figure 5.2.5.3. (a) Detail layout overview of the ICL structure with hybrid cladding design (b) HR-XRD diffractogram of the ICL indicating lattice matching and strain-compensated growth of the high-quality cladding layers.

The doping profiles of Si and Te concentrations measured by SIMS are presented in Figure 5.2.5.4. The layer species are labelled. The doping concentration in outer, bulk layers is matching the design (10^{19} cm^{-3}), however it is less visible in SL claddings and the active region where the averaging of doping levels over different layers needs to be taken to account. The ICL sample was processed by a standard photolithography as defined in subchapter 4.3.6. The ICL was

characterized in pulsed mode as described in subchapter 4.3.7. The emission was observed for different temperatures up to 55 °C. Figure 5.2.5.5 (a) presents the corresponding power-current-voltage characteristics.

5.2.5.4. Densities of Si and Te ions in the growth direction of an ICL. Doping density of InAs wells in claddings are linearly increasing from SCLs towards outside. First and the last 10 nm of each SCL is doped higher than the middle of SCL. The doping density in the electron injector QWs is averaged over the active region.

Figure 5.2.5.5. (a) Pulsed light-current and voltage-current curves at different temperatures for a 2 mm long and 100 μm wide BA device (b) Temperature dependence of the threshold current density and extracted characteristic temperature $T_0 = 38$ K.

At the same current, the voltage decreases at higher temperatures due to the bandgap reduction caused by temperature shift. At RT, the ICL exhibits threshold current density of $J_{th} = 242 \text{ A/cm}^2$. The threshold was hence lower than previously reported record low value [116], [117] at the same wavelength (280 A/cm^2). The measured differential resistance of 3Ω was larger than the typical $1\text{-}2 \Omega$, which might be caused by slightly insufficient doping of SCLs and/or cap layer. Nevertheless, the threshold power density of 840 W/cm^2 was excellent as it is matching well with lowest reported values. The voltage efficiency of 55.4% is comparable to previously reported values [76], [79], though it could be improved by reducing the differential resistance. In the voltage range of $0\text{-}2 \text{ V}$ there is a presence of leakage current caused by low sidewall resistance as no passivation was applied to the BA ridges. For the displayed temperature range ($15\text{-}55 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) the slope efficiency drops from 144 mW/A to 66 mW/A . The extracted characteristic temperature of $T_0 = 38 \text{ K}$ displayed in Figure 5.2.5.5. (b) matches well with the reported values at similar wavelengths [76], [78], [118], [124].

Figure 5.2.5.6. displays the emission spectra of the ICL at different temperatures. The wavelength shift induced by temperature is $4.4 \text{ nm}/^\circ\text{C}$.

Figure 5.2.5.6. (a) Spectra at $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $45 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (b) and $65 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (c) of a BA ($2 \text{ mm} \times 100 \mu\text{m}$) device. The spectral wavelength at RT is $5.16 \mu\text{m}$ and the measured temperature shift is $4.4 \text{ nm}/^\circ\text{C}$.

For the sake of cw operation, RWG devices were fabricated. As a difference from BA devices, the waveguides were patterned by e-beam lithography and processed by reactive ion etching. The contact materials were the same as used for the BA devices. An additional $11 \mu\text{m}$ thick layer of gold was electroplated on the top contact. The facets were coated by with a high-reflective metal layer on the backside insulated by SiO_2 and Al_2O_3 . The $6.4 \mu\text{m}$ wide RWG ICLs were cleaved into 0.9 mm long laser bars. The Fabry-Pérot lasers were mounted epi-side up on a copper heat

sink. Figure 5.2.5.7 (a) presents electro-optical characteristics of the RWG ICL, operated in cw mode, at different temperatures. The maximum operational temperature was 41 °C which is approximately the same as previously reported values in that wavelength range [78], [82], [118]. The threshold current at RT cw operation of 49.6 mA corresponding to the threshold current density of 861 A/cm² is higher than reported values [82], [118], [124]. This could be a consequence of leakage currents present due to imperfection of the RWG fabrication process. The maximum measured output power at RT was 6.1 mW resulting in the wall plug efficiency of 1.4 %, what is in the range of state-of-the-art. Figure 5.2.5.7 (b) temperature-induced wavelength shift of a single Fabry-Pérot mode emitting in pulsed operation of a RWG ICL is presented. In Figure 5.2.5.7. (c), the difference between the input and output powers of a RWG laser is shown at the same temperature of the heat sink, for different wavelengths of a single Fabry-Pérot mode emitting in a cw operation, at different currents. The wavelength shift is a consequence of ohmic heating from the cw operation. From the ratio of obtained gradients of temperature (Figure 5.2.5.7 (b)) and power (Figure 5.2.5.7 (c)), the thermal resistance of the RWG ICL is $R_{th} = 62 \text{ K/W}$ ($R_{thA} = 3.6 \text{ K/ (kW/cm}^2\text{)}$).

Figure 5.2.5.7. (a) Continuous wave (CW) operation light-current and voltage-current curves at different temperatures for a 0.9 mm long and 6.4 μm wide ridge waveguide (RWG) device (b) Temperature-induced shift of a single Fabry-Pérot mode at pulsed operation of RWG laser (c) Difference between the input and output powers of the RWG laser for wavelength shift of a single Fabry-Pérot mode induced by sweeping of current at a cw operation.

This thermal resistance is significantly lower than reported values (100 – 150 K/W) for epi-side up RWG ICLs of similar cavity lengths [90]. This is indicating an enhanced heat dissipation of the

claddings which is in agreement with high thermal conductivity of plasmon-enhanced claddings in the literature [109].

In summary, the 5.2 μm emitting ICL has demonstrated not only the lowest threshold current density in the pulsed mode for wavelengths longer than 5 μm , but also a low thermal resistance suggesting a good thermal management. Therefore, plasmon-enhanced claddings can successfully be implemented in ICLs even for shorter emission wavelengths (4-6 μm) and perform with excellent figures of merit.

6. Triple V-shaped quantum wells for long wavelength ICL

In this chapter, the V-shaped design of QWs is proposed for long wavelength ICLs due to the larger wavefunction overlap and hence the optical gain. The structure of V-shaped QWs and optimization of their wavefunction overlap and VISA are discussed. The optimized parameters are then contrasted to the respective parameters of the W-shaped QWs commonly used as the recombination region of the ICL. The higher wavefunction overlap and a smaller VISA are desirable, especially at long wavelengths.

6.1. Triple V-shaped quantum wells design

Emission of ICLs commonly cover the wavelength range 3-7 μm , however absorption lines of more complex gases lay outside of this spectral range. Particularly, around wavelength of 7.5 μm , presence of TNT (7.3 μm), SO_2 (7.2 μm), H_2S_2 (7.3 μm), H_2O_2 (7.8 μm) and H_2SO_4 (7.9 μm) could be detected. Sensing TNT is crucial for explosive detection, whereas detection and suppression of sulfur-based oxides and acids is important as they are poisonous, odorless and highly toxic for inhaling. The neighbouring wavelengths of interest are 6.2 μm , the absorption line of NO_2 and 9.0 μm , the absorption line of glucose and ethanol. The longest wavelength reported at RT by GaSb-based ICL was 6.8 μm [123], whereas the limit for InAs-based ICL of 7.0 μm [131] has recently been extended to 7.7 μm [51]. To achieve the RT emission at 7.0 μm , the number of cascade stages was significantly increased at the expense of threshold voltage, whereas the number of electron injector wells was reduced to mitigate FCA losses. The wavelength limit was extended to 7.7 μm by implementing two-stage InAsP-AlAsSb barriers in the recombination region, similar to what was done in earlier reports for longer wavelengths [126], [129].

RT emission at longer wavelengths is limited by the oscillator strength. Potential improvement of wavefunction overlap was demonstrated in [133] at “sweet spot” wavelength of 3.5 μm , by introducing an additional pair of $\text{Ga}_{0.6}\text{In}_{0.4}\text{Sb}/\text{InAs}$ wells to the state-of-the-art $\text{InAs}/\text{Ga}_{0.6}\text{In}_{0.4}\text{Sb}/\text{InAs}$ W-shaped QW. Thicknesses of $\text{Ga}_{0.6}\text{In}_{0.4}\text{Sb}$ and InAs of the added pair were the same as in the original structure. As the triple V-shaped structure is longer than W-shaped QW, the emission wavelength is red-shifted. Nevertheless, hole confinement in the recombination region becomes higher due to an additional well, hence the overlap of electron and hole wavefunction increases. This way, unlike for W-shaped QW, emission at longer wavelength could be obtained not only without sacrificing, but with increasing the wavefunction overlap up to 20-30 %. Experimentally, it was validated by photoreflectance (PR) measurement. The integrated spectral feature intensity that corresponds to the wavefunction overlap has shown 80-90% improvement. Difference in magnitude of the improvement was due to possible misalignment of the setup or intermixing at the layer interfaces. It was shown that adding more QW pairs, red shifts the emission wavelength further, however it reaches a saturation. In this chapter, V-shaped QWs are compared to W-shaped QWs for wavelengths of 6.2 μm , 7.5 μm and 9.0 μm , as a potential way to improve their performance and to extend the RT emission range of GaSb-based ICLs.

6.2. Optimization of the wavefunction overlap

In order to contrast the triple V-shaped to the commonly employed W-shaped QW design at it is necessary to optimize the design parameters of both structures. The optimization of wavefunction overlap is shown for wavelength of 7.5 μm . The band structures of the two designs with maximal wavefunction overlap are presented in Figure 6.2.1. for the W-shaped and for the triple V-shaped QW in (a) and (b), respectively. The electronic band structure was obtained from k-p calculation, including the strain effects. The simulations were performed with the finite difference method provided by the software nextnano³. All material parameters were taken from Reference [52]. The W-shaped QW has the layer sequence **AISb/InAs/Ga_{0.6}In_{0.4}Sb/InAs/AISb** with thicknesses (2.50/2.65/2.30/2.65/1.50) nm. In the triple V-shaped QW the layer sequence is **AISb/InAs/Ga_{0.6}In_{0.4}Sb/InAs_{0.85}Sb_{0.15}/Ga_{0.6}In_{0.4}Sb/InAs/AISb** and the maximum wavefunction overlap was obtained for the thicknesses (2.5/2.4/1.8/3.1/1.8/2.4/1.5) nm and the arsenic mole fraction ratio for the middle InAs_{0.85}Sb_{0.15} QW. The V-shaped QW design shows a 19 % higher wavefunction overlap ($\langle\psi_e|\psi_h\rangle = 0.642$) compared to the W-shaped QW ($\langle\psi_e|\psi_h\rangle = 0.540$).

Figure 6.2.1. (a) Band structure of the W-shaped QW: Design A: **AISb/InAs/Ga_{0.6}In_{0.4}Sb/InAs/AISb**, (2.50/2.65/2.30/2.65/1.50) nm. (b) Band structure of the triple V-shaped QW: Design B: **AISb/InAs/Ga_{0.6}In_{0.4}Sb/InAs_{0.85}Sb_{0.15}/Ga_{0.6}In_{0.4}Sb/InAs/AISb**, (2.5/2.4/1.8/3.1/1.8/2.4/1.5) nm.

In Figure 6.2.2 (a) the wavefunction overlap is shown for different thicknesses of the electron InAs and the hole Ga_{0.6}In_{0.4}Sb layers. Due to higher confinement and larger effective mass of holes, the wavelength dependence on the width of InAs QW is significantly higher compared to the width of the Ga_{0.6}In_{0.4}Sb QW. At a wavelength of approximately 7.5 μm (labelled in the figure), the wavefunction overlap varies from 0.516 to the maximum value of 0.540. At longer wavelengths, the wavefunction overlap is further reduced. Due to the wider QWs, the optimal wavefunction overlap is significantly below the value for the state-of-the-art 3.5 μm emission wavelength with $\langle\psi_e|\psi_h\rangle = 0.640$. Along with 7.5 μm , designs of wavelengths 6.2 μm and 9.0 μm are marked with green and purple contour. Maxima of wavefunction overlaps at 6.2 μm and 9.0 μm are 0.573 and 0.510, respectively. Figure 6.2.2. (b) depicts dependencies of wavelength and wavefunction overlap on the thickness of the InAs layers for a fixed 2.3 nm wide Ga_{0.6}In_{0.4}Sb

QW. The figure shows that the wavelength increases, while wavefunction overlap decreases with InAs thickness. Similarly, Figure 6.2.2. (c) presents wavelength and wavefunction overlap dependencies on the thickness of the $\text{Ga}_{0.6}\text{In}_{0.4}\text{Sb}$ QW for fixed 2.65 nm wide InAs QWs. The wavelength increases parabolically with the maximum wavelength at around $8.15 \mu\text{m}$ for a 3.5 nm thick QW. The wavelength shift is approximately 6 times smaller compared to varying InAs QW thickness by the same thickness variation of 1.5 nm. For both cuts, the wavefunction overlap decreases almost linearly with layer thickness. However, there is a more prominent decrease for varying the thickness of the InAs QW layers.

Figure 6.2.2. (a) Dependence of the wavefunction overlap in a W-shaped QW for a variation of the electron (InAs) and hole ($\text{Ga}_{0.6}\text{In}_{0.4}\text{Sb}$) QW thicknesses. The region corresponding to the wavelength of $\approx 7.5 \mu\text{m}$ is marked with the solid, blue contour. Design A of the highest wavefunction overlap is labelled with the grey dot. The regions corresponding to wavelengths of $6.2 \mu\text{m}$ and $9.0 \mu\text{m}$ are marked with solid green and purple line respectively. Their corresponding designs with maximal wavefunction overlaps are labelled by green and purple dot (b) Dependence of the wavelength and wavefunction overlap on the thickness of InAs layers at fixed 2.3 nm wide $\text{Ga}_{0.6}\text{In}_{0.4}\text{Sb}$ QW. Design A is labelled with the blue and red dot. (c) Dependence of the wavelength and wavefunction overlap on thickness of $\text{Ga}_{0.6}\text{In}_{0.4}\text{Sb}$ layer at fixed 2.65 nm wide InAs QWs. Design A is labeled with the blue and red dot.

In contrast to the W-shaped design, the design of triple V-shaped QWs has four degrees of freedom: thicknesses of InAs, $\text{Ga}_{0.6}\text{In}_{0.4}\text{Sb}$, $\text{InAs}_x\text{Sb}_{1-x}$ and arsenic mole fraction ratio x . Maximal wavefunction overlaps of triple V-shaped QW designs for the wavelengths $6.2 \mu\text{m}$, $7.5 \mu\text{m}$ and $9.0 \mu\text{m}$ are listed in the Table 6.2.1. The maximal wavefunction overlaps at $6.2 \mu\text{m}$, $7.5 \mu\text{m}$ and $9.0 \mu\text{m}$ are 0.681, 0.642 and 0.608, which is 18.8 %, 18. 9% and 19.2 % higher than values for their respective W-shaped designs.

λ	InAs	Ga _{0.6} In _{0.4} Sb	InAs _x Sb _{1-x}	x
6.2 μm	2.2 nm	1.6 nm	2.8 nm	0.85
7.5 μm	2.4 nm	1.8 nm	3.1 nm	0.85
9.0 μm	2.6 nm	1.8 nm	3.4 nm	0.90

Table 6.2.1. Layer structure of V-shaped QW composed of **AlSb/InAs/Ga_{0.6}In_{0.4}Sb/InAs_xSb_{1-x}/Ga_{0.6}In_{0.4}Sb/InAs/AlSb** at wavelengths 6.2 μm , 7.5 μm and 9.0 μm .

Due to high dimensionality of the design space of V-shaped design, the focus is on optimization of wavefunction overlap for wavelength of 7.5 μm . The optimization procedure for the wavelengths of 6.2 μm and 9.0 μm are carried out analogically. Figure 6.2.3. (a) displays the wavefunction overlap at fixed 3.1 nm width of the middle InAs_{0.85}Sb_{0.15} electron QW, under same varying parameters: width of InAs electron QWs and Ga_{0.6}In_{0.4}Sb hole QWs.

Figure 6.2.3. (a) Dependence of the wavefunction overlap in a triple V-shaped QW for a variation of the electron InAs and hole Ga_{0.6}In_{0.4}Sb QWs widths at fixed 3.1 nm thickness of middle InAs_xSb_{1-x} electron QW and the Arsenic fraction of $x = 0.85$. The region corresponding to the wavelength of 7.5 μm is marked with solid, blue contour. The design with the highest wavefunction overlap is marked with a grey dot and dashed line (design B). (b) Dependence of the wavelength and wavefunction overlap on widths of InAs QWs at fixed 1.8 nm thick Ga_{0.6}In_{0.4}Sb. Design B is labelled with blue and red dot. (c) Dependence of the wavelength and wavefunction overlap on the width of Ga_{0.6}In_{0.4}Sb QWs at fixed 2.4 nm wide InAs QWs. Design B is labelled with blue and red dots.

Designs of emission wavelength of $\approx 7.5 \mu\text{m}$ are labelled by the blue contour. The wavefunction overlap in the wavelength range $7.4\text{-}7.6 \mu\text{m}$ varies from 0.518 to 0.642. The design with the highest wavefunction overlap is highlighted by the grey dot. Its wavefunction overlap is comparable to the wavefunction overlap of a standard $3.5 \mu\text{m}$ W-shaped QW. Hence, the design compensates the reduction introduced by the longer wavelength. Figures 6.2.3 (b) and (c) present cuts of the wavefunction and wavelength dependencies at fixed thickness of 1.8 nm $\text{Ga}_{0.6}\text{In}_{0.4}\text{Sb}$ and 2.4 nm InAs respectively. In Figure 6.2.3. (b) and for a fixed 1.8 nm thick $\text{Ga}_{0.6}\text{In}_{0.4}\text{Sb}$, the wavelength parabolically increases with InAs QW thickness as the effective bandgap reduces. In the first segment of the curve, wavefunction overlap slightly increases with thickness of InAs QWs. Eigenstates in thin InAs wells are significantly above the state in the middle $\text{InAs}_{0.85}\text{Sb}_{0.15}$ QW, hence due to lack of wavefunction coupling, the electron confinement is dominantly concentrated in the middle $\text{InAs}_{0.85}\text{Sb}_{0.15}$ QW. With wider InAs QWs, the coupling of wavefunctions establishes and the confinement redistributes from $\text{InAs}_{0.85}\text{Sb}_{0.15}$ towards the outer layers. Then in the second segment of the curve, for further widening InAs QWs, the wavefunction overlap parabolically decreases as the confinement in side wells become bigger. Analogously, as presented in Figure 6.2.3. (c), at fixed thickness of InAs layers, the wavelength parabolically increases with thickness of $\text{Ga}_{0.6}\text{In}_{0.4}\text{Sb}$ layers. However, it reaches a maximum at 3 nm , as the shift of the hole eigenstate in $\text{Ga}_{0.6}\text{In}_{0.4}\text{Sb}$ becomes negligible. Unlike for the previous cut, the wavefunction overlap is monotonously decreasing with wider $\text{Ga}_{0.6}\text{In}_{0.4}\text{Sb}$ wells as confinement in every separate electron QWs increases. As a difference between the W-shaped QW design, it is notable that variation of thickness of electron and hole wells comparably contribute to change of the wavelength and wavefunction overlap, which increases their tunability. Figure 6.2.4 displays band structures of triple V-shaped QWs of the same $7.5 \mu\text{m}$ emission wavelength and middle 3.1 nm wide $\text{InAs}_{0.85}\text{Sb}_{0.15}$ QW, but with different thicknesses of InAs and $\text{Ga}_{0.6}\text{In}_{0.4}\text{Sb}$ layers. The evolution of wavefunction coupling with respective wavefunction overlaps, for increasing width of InAs wells (d_1) and decreasing width of $\text{Ga}_{0.6}\text{In}_{0.4}\text{Sb}$ wells (d_2) is displayed in sequence $d_1 = 1.0 \text{ nm}$, $d_2 = 3.8 \text{ nm}$ (a), $d_1 = 2.4 \text{ nm}$, $d_2 = 1.8 \text{ nm}$ (b) and $d_1 = 3.7 \text{ nm}$, $d_2 = 1.1 \text{ nm}$ (c).

Figure 6.2.4. Band structures of triple V-shaped QWs of designed emission wavelength $7.5 \mu\text{m}$, with the following combinations of thicknesses of InAs (d_1), $\text{Ga}_{0.6}\text{In}_{0.4}\text{Sb}$ (d_2) and $\text{InAs}_{0.85}\text{Sb}_{0.15}$ (d_3): (a) (d_1, d_2, d_3) = ($1.0, 3.8, 3.1$) nm (b) (d_1, d_2, d_3) = ($2.4, 1.8, 3.1$) nm (c) (d_1, d_2, d_3) = ($3.7, 1.1, 3.1$) nm. The structure in (a) has a lower wavefunction overlap than optimal structure (b) due to both, the shorter InAs and the

thicker $\text{Ga}_{0.6}\text{In}_{0.4}\text{Sb}$ layers. The structure in (c) has a lower overlap than optimal structure (b) due to the thicker InAs layers, despite shorter $\text{Ga}_{0.6}\text{In}_{0.4}\text{Sb}$ layers.

Figure 6.2.5 (a) shows the wavefunction overlap at fixed thicknesses of 2.4 nm for the InAs electron QW and 1.8 nm for the $\text{Ga}_{0.6}\text{In}_{0.4}\text{Sb}$ hole QWs for varying thickness of the middle $\text{InAs}_x\text{Sb}_{1-x}$ electron QW and its arsenic fraction ratio (x). Similarly to the previous figures, the design with the highest wavefunction overlap is labelled as a grey dot on a blue contour indicating designs at an emission wavelength of $7.5\ \mu\text{m}$. Figures 6.2.5 (b) and (c) display cuts of the wavefunction and wavelength dependencies at fixed thickness of 3.1 nm of $\text{InAs}_x\text{Sb}_{1-x}$ QW and fixed arsenic fraction ratio of $x = 0.85$ respectively.

Figure 6.2.5. (a) Dependence of the wavefunction overlap in a triple V-shaped QW for a variation of the electron $\text{InAs}_x\text{Sb}_{1-x}$ QW width and its arsenic fraction ratio (x) at fixed thicknesses of 2.4 nm of InAs electron QW and 1.8 nm $\text{Ga}_{0.6}\text{In}_{0.4}\text{Sb}$ hole QW. The region corresponding to wavelength of $7.5\ \mu\text{m}$ is marked with the solid, blue contour. The design with the highest wavefunction overlap is marked with the gray dot and the dashed line (design B). (b) Dependence of the wavelength and wavefunction overlap on arsenic fraction ratio (x) in 3.1 nm $\text{InAs}_x\text{Sb}_{1-x}$ QW at fixed thicknesses of 2.4 nm of InAs electron QW and 1.8 nm $\text{Ga}_{0.6}\text{In}_{0.4}\text{Sb}$ hole QW. Design B is labeled with blue and red dots. (c) Dependence of the wavelength and wavefunction overlap on thickness of $\text{InAs}_{0.85}\text{Sb}_{0.15}$ at fixed thickness of 2.4 nm of InAs electron QWs and 1.8 nm $\text{Ga}_{0.6}\text{In}_{0.4}\text{Sb}$ hole QW. Design B is labeled with blue and red dots.

Figure 6.2.5. (b) shows that both wavelength and wavefunction overlap almost parabolically change with the increase of the arsenic fraction ratio in $\text{InAs}_x\text{Sb}_{1-x}$. At arsenic fraction ratio of $x < 0.12$, the valence band edge of $\text{InAs}_x\text{Sb}_{1-x}$ is energetically above the $\text{Ga}_{0.6}\text{In}_{0.4}\text{Sb}$, and hence

$\text{InAs}_x\text{Sb}_{1-x}$ is not a barrier anymore and now acts as a QW for holes. Therefore, the wavefunction overlap is low as hole confinement is concentrated dominantly in the middle layer. For $x > 0.12$, $\text{InAs}_x\text{Sb}_{1-x}$ becomes a hole barrier, thus hole confinement redistributes from $\text{InAs}_x\text{Sb}_{1-x}$ to $\text{Ga}_{0.6}\text{In}_{0.4}\text{Sb}$ layers resulting in an increase of the wavefunction overlap. Additionally, the coupling of the electron wavefunction in $\text{InAs}_x\text{Sb}_{1-x}$ with the wavefunctions of InAs wells is increasing and reaches its maximum at $x \approx 0.4$. With further increasing the arsenic content, the barriers for electron in the $\text{InAs}_x\text{Sb}_{1-x}$ QW become higher, thus due to larger confinement, the coupling between the electron wavefunctions reduces, resulting in decrease of wavefunction overlap. As discussed before, for $x < 0.12$, the two $\text{Ga}_{0.6}\text{In}_{0.4}\text{Sb}$ and $\text{InAs}_x\text{Sb}_{1-x}$ form one joint hole QW. Once arsenic ratio becomes higher than 0.12, $\text{InAs}_x\text{Sb}_{1-x}$ converts from hole QW to hole barrier. Then the confinement redistributes fully to $\text{Ga}_{0.6}\text{In}_{0.4}\text{Sb}$ QWs that are significantly thinner than the previous joint QW. For this reason, their hole eigenstates are becoming lower than in the joint QW, leading to slight increase of transition energy. Then at $x = 0.35$ the wavelength reaches its minimum, and starts increasing again, for $x > 0.35$. The reason for this is energy drop of the electron eigenstate in the $\text{InAs}_x\text{Sb}_{1-x}$ QW caused by shift of the conduction band edge. In Figure 6.2.5. (c), the first segment of the wavefunction overlap shows an increase with the thickness of $\text{InAs}_{0.85}\text{Sb}_{0.15}$. In short $\text{InAs}_{0.85}\text{Sb}_{0.15}$ QW, the electron eigenstate is higher than in the InAs QWs, hence only the wavefunction in the first and the third electron QW are coupled, which reflects on low wavefunction overlap. With longer $\text{InAs}_{0.85}\text{Sb}_{0.15}$ QW, the wavefunction overlap becomes higher and reaches its maximum at $\text{InAs}_{0.85}\text{Sb}_{0.15}$ thickness of $d_3 \approx 2\text{nm}$ As the majority of wavefunction overlap originates from areas of $\text{Ga}_{0.6}\text{In}_{0.4}\text{Sb}$, with further widening the middle QW, the width fraction of $\text{Ga}_{0.6}\text{In}_{0.4}\text{Sb}$ over the total width is getting lower, leading to decrease of the wavefunction overlap. In contrast, the wavelength is monotonously increasing with increasing thickness of $\text{InAs}_{0.85}\text{Sb}_{0.15}$ layer, similarly to trend for varying the InAs wells. Figure 6.2.6. presents the wavefunction profiles and the respective wavefunction overlaps of the $7.5\ \mu\text{m}$ V-shaped QWs for increasing the thickness of $\text{InAs}_x\text{Sb}_{1-x}$: $d_3 = 1.4\ \text{nm}$, $x = 0.1$ (a), $d_3 = 3.1\ \text{nm}$, $x = 0.85$ (b), $d_3 = 4.0\ \text{nm}$, $x = 0.65$ (c). Figure 6.2.6 (a) depicts the band structure where $\text{InAs}_x\text{Sb}_{1-x}$ is a hole QW, whereas in figures 6.2.6 (b) and 6.2.6 (c), $\text{InAs}_x\text{Sb}_{1-x}$ is a hole barrier. Figure 6.2.6 (b) displays the structure with the highest wavefunction overlap, while 6.2.6 (c) shows suboptimal wavefunction overlap due to thicker $\text{InAs}_x\text{Sb}_{1-x}$.

Figure 6.2.6. Band structures of triple V-shaped QWs of designed emission wavelength $7.5\ \mu\text{m}$, with fixed thicknesses of InAs ($d_1 = 2.4\ \text{nm}$) and $\text{Ga}_{0.6}\text{In}_{0.4}\text{Sb}$ layers ($d_2 = 1.8\ \text{nm}$), and the following combinations of arsenic fraction ratio (x) and thickness of $\text{InAs}_x\text{Sb}_{1-x}$ (d_3): (a) (x, d_3) = (0.1, 1.4 nm) (b) (x, d_3) = (0.85, 3.1 nm) (c) (x, d_3) = (0.65, 4.0 nm). The structure in (a) has a lower wavefunction overlap than optimal structure (b) due to both lower x and thinner $\text{InAs}_x\text{Sb}_{1-x}$ layers. The structure in (c) has a lower wavefunction overlap than optimal structure (b) due to thicker $\text{InAs}_x\text{Sb}_{1-x}$ layers, despite lower x .

6.3. Wavefunction overlap and VISA under bias

In support to the overview of the comparison between the W-shaped and V-shaped QW designs, along with the wavefunction overlap, the VISA was calculated for TE polarized light according to equation 3.1.2.2, by using the QuantCAD's software CADtronics [134]. To have a fair insight to applicability of the V-shaped design on the actual device, the two structures were simulated under bias. Due to Stark shift, the ground states in the InAs electron wells and hole $\text{Ga}_{0.6}\text{In}_{0.4}\text{Sb}$ wells tend to decouple; hence the well thicknesses are slightly adjusted so that the structure become asymmetric. As in the V-shaped design, hole $\text{Ga}_{0.6}\text{In}_{0.4}\text{Sb}$ QWs are significantly narrower than InAs QWs, a sensitivity of their ground states to external field is higher, thus the second well is made slightly wider (2.0 nm). In the W-shaped QW design, the first well is made slightly wider (2.7 nm) and the second slightly narrower (2.6 nm).

The wavefunction overlaps at different applied electric fields are listed in the table 6.3. It is notable that the W-shaped QW is almost insensitive to applied electric field ($\langle\psi_e|\psi_h\rangle \approx 0.54$) regardless of what symmetrical or asymmetrical variant of the design is considered. Nevertheless, the wavefunction overlap of V-shaped QW is drastically changing for varying the field. As a result of decoupling hole wavefunctions of the two $\text{Ga}_{0.6}\text{In}_{0.4}\text{Sb}$ wells, one of the two hole wavefunction peaks is effectively lost, therefore the wavefunction overlap drops abruptly. Unlike for the symmetrical design considered in the previous subchapter, the asymmetrical V-shaped well has the hole wavefunctions decoupled at zero bias. However, at field of $F = 37$ kV/cm the coupling reestablishes, and the wavefunction overlap considerably increases to $\langle\psi_e|\psi_h\rangle = 0.605$. With higher fields the wavefunction overlap decreases, similar to the case of symmetrical design. The coupling effect does not necessarily happen exactly at certain fields, as the dispersion and thermal energy also play a prominent role.

	WQW	WQW	VQW	VQW
$F = 0$	0.540	0.538	0.642	0.438
$F = 37$ kV/cm				0.605
$F = 50$ kV/cm	0.538	0.539	0.422	0.437
$F = 100$ kV/cm	0.532	0.537	0.385	0.393

Table 6.3. Wavefunction overlaps in symmetrical and asymmetrical W-shaped QWs (WQWs) and triple V-shaped QWs (VQWs) under different external fields F . The fields in red color are the fields at which the coupling of wavefunctions occurs within the V-shaped QW. The structures of the four QWs are the following: symmetrical W-shaped QW (2.5 nm **AlSb**/2.65 nm *InAs*/2.30 nm $\text{Ga}_{0.6}\text{In}_{0.4}\text{Sb}$ /2.65 nm *InAs*/1.5 nm **AlSb**), asymmetrical W-shaped QW (2.5 nm **AlSb**/2.70 nm *InAs*/2.30 nm $\text{Ga}_{0.6}\text{In}_{0.4}\text{Sb}$ /2.60 nm *InAs*/1.5 nm **AlSb**), symmetrical V-shaped QW (2.5 nm **AlSb**/2.4 nm *InAs*/1.8 nm $\text{Ga}_{0.6}\text{In}_{0.4}\text{Sb}$ /3.1 nm *InAs*_{0.85}*Sb*_{0.15}/1.8 nm $\text{Ga}_{0.6}\text{In}_{0.4}\text{Sb}$ /2.4 nm *InAs*/1.5 nm **AlSb**), asymmetrical V-shaped QW (2.5 nm **AlSb**/2.4 nm *InAs*/1.8 nm $\text{Ga}_{0.6}\text{In}_{0.4}\text{Sb}$ /3.1 nm *InAs*_{0.85}*Sb*_{0.15}/2.0 nm $\text{Ga}_{0.6}\text{In}_{0.4}\text{Sb}$ /2.4 nm *InAs*/1.5 nm **AlSb**).

Figure 6.3.1 displays the band structure of V-shaped QW at different electric fields. As reported in Ref. [133], for this reason implementation of such V-shaped QW in the ICL active region can be challenging. Nevertheless, as it is shown that V-shaped QW can still provide a higher wavefunction overlap than W-shaped QW. When the threshold voltage is known, well widths can be further adjusted to the corresponding field intensity.

Figure 6.3.1. Calculated band structures of V-shaped QW under three different electric fields: (a) $F = 0$ kV/cm, (b) $F = 37$ kV/cm, (c) $F = 100$ kV/cm. At $F = 37$ kV/cm, the hole states are coupled, and the wavefunction overlap integral is maximal. At field higher or lower than 37 kV/cm the ground hole states are decoupled. However, experimentally, the states could be coupled even for slightly different fields due to energy dispersion and thermal energy.

In Figure 6.3.2, the calculated VISA spectra of Designs A and B is displayed.

Figure 6.3.2. Spectral dependence of VISA of the (symmetrical) W-shaped and V-shaped QW with the optimal wavefunction overlaps.

In the 6-9 μm range, the V-shaped QW has a lower VISA than the W-shaped design. The highest difference is achieved at wavelength of 7.05 μm . At 6.2 μm , the VISA for W-shaped and V-shaped is approximately equal. However, at 7.5 μm , VISA of the W-shaped QW is $\alpha_{VISA} = 4.65$ cm^{-1} while the V-shaped QW shows a significantly lower absorption of $\alpha_{VISA} = 2.0$ cm^{-1} . Figure 6.3.3 presents the VISA in the slightly asymmetrical W-shaped and V-shaped QW structures under three different electrical fields: 0, 50 kV/cm, and 100 kV/cm. As presented in both

subfigures, at wavelength of $7.5 \mu\text{m}$, the VISA is equal for all the electric fields. The VISA in the W-shaped QW is $\alpha_{VISA} = 4.50 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, whereas of V-shaped QW is $\alpha_{VISA} = 2.65 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, therefore, the suppression of VISA for the V-shaped design remains present.

Figure 6.3.3. Spectral dependence of VISA of the asymmetrical (a) W-shaped (b) V-shaped QW with the optimal wavefunction overlap under three different external electric fields: 0, 50 kV/cm and 100 kV/cm.

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Appendix A

In this section, the overview of the active region and growth of the ICLs with SL and bulk claddings from subchapter 5.1.2. is provided. The substrate temperature is monitored by a pyrometer. Prior to growth, an oxide desorption was performed under exposure to Sb flux at 560 °C for 3 min. Firstly, a 200 nm thick n-type doped GaSb:Te buffer layer ($1 \cdot 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) was grown at a substrate temperature of 500 °C. For the ICL with SL claddings, during the growth of the bottom cladding, the temperature was ramped down to 450 °C. The superlattice was grown as described in the subchapter 3.3.4. Following the bottom cladding, the substrate temperature was increased back to 500 °C for the growth of the bottom SCL. For the ICL with bulk $\text{Al}_{0.85}\text{Ga}_{0.15}\text{As}_{0.07}\text{Sb}_{0.93}$ claddings, the temperature was kept at 500 °C throughout the growth of the bottom cladding at the bottom SCL. The AlGaAsSb layers are n-type doped by Te in the same fashion as the ICL with SL claddings. Subsequently, the substrate temperature was reduced to 450 °C for the growth of the six-stages active region for both ICLs. Once the active region was grown, the substrate temperature remained constant at 450 °C. The SCLs in both ICLs were 430 nm thick and lightly n-type doped with Te ($6 \cdot 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}$). The active region is composed of **AISb/InAs/Ga_{0.6}In_{0.4}Sb/InAs/AISb** (W-shaped QW), GaSb/**AISb**/GaSb (hole injector), **AISb/InAs/AISb/InAs/AISb/InAs/AISb/InAs** (electron injector) with thicknesses listed in the Table A.

	AISb	InAs	GaInSb	InAs	AISb
W-QW	2.5 nm	2.23 nm	2.55 nm	1.75 nm	1.0 nm

A1. Layer structure of the recombination W-QW region.

	GaSb	AISb	GaSb
h-injector	2.8 nm	1.0 nm	4.8 nm

A2. Layer structure of the hole injector.

	AISb	InAs	AISb	InAs	AISb	InAs	AISb	InAs
e-injector	2.5 nm	4.6 nm	1.2 nm	3.4 nm	1.2 nm	2.6 nm	1.2 nm	2.1 nm

A3. Layer structure of the electron injector.

Table A: Layer thicknesses of the recombination region (A1), layer thicknesses of the hole injector (A2) and layer thicknesses of the electron injector (A3) of the ICLs with SL and bulk claddings.

The last three InAs wells of the electron injectors were n-type doped to $4 \cdot 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$.

As mentioned before, for the ICL with quaternary claddings, 50 nm wide LDGs composed of AlGaAsSb/GaSb were grown as TLs from GaSb to AlGaAsSb and vice-versa. In the last 12 min of the GaSb buffer growth, the growth rate of GaSb was reduced from 480 nm/h to 88 nm/h to match the desired 15% molar fraction ratio in the $\text{Al}_{0.85}\text{Ga}_{0.15}\text{As}_{0.07}\text{Sb}_{0.93}$ bottom cladding. In parallel, the temperature of the Te cell was ramped down to maintain the doping level constant

($1 \cdot 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$). Due to a significantly higher growth rate of the AlGaAsSb layers (588 nm/h), for a doping level of GaSb layers of $1 \cdot 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, the doping level in AlGaAsSb layers of TL is significantly lower. Once the growth of the transition layer ends, temperature of the Te cell is increased rapidly to match the doping level of in the AlGaAsSb claddings. Rapid ramp up of the temperature of the Te cell at the beginning of the cladding, could be avoided by a gradual raise during the growth of the TL. However, the containing GaSb layers would be grown overdoped and AlGaAsSb layers underdoped anyway. The ICL with SL claddings was capped by InAs, n-type doped by Si to $2 \cdot 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. The ICL with AlGaAsSb claddings was capped by GaSb, n-type doped by Te to $3 \cdot 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. The GaSb cap was used instead of the InAs to reduce the conduction band offset between the bulk layer and the cap material.

Appendix B

In this section, an insight to the active region structure and the growth details of the InAs-based ICL and GaSb-based ICLs from the subchapter 5.2.4. is given. The two ICLs were grown on n-type doped InAs and GaSb substrates ($1 \cdot 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$). Prior to the growth, a 3-minute oxide desorption process was carried out under arsenic flux at 540 °C for InAs-based ICL and under Sb flux at 560 °C for GaSb-based ICL. The growth of InAs-based ICL begins with 200 nm InAs buffer, n-type doped by Si ($1 \cdot 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$), followed by n-type doped 700 nm n^+ -InAs claddings ($1 \cdot 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$). Subsequently, 1 μm thick InAs/AlSb SL cladding was grown. After every AlSb layer of the SL, surface was exposed to 3 s arsenic soak to balance the compressive strain in AlSb layers on InAs substrate, by forcing AlAs-like interfaces. The doping concentration of Si in n-type doped InAs layers of the SL cladding, was linearly decreasing towards the active region from $1 \cdot 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ to $1 \cdot 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. The substrate temperature was monitored by a pyrometer and maintained at 450 °C from the beginning of buffer until the end of the growth run. The growth of GaSb-based ICL starts with 200 nm GaSb buffer layer, n-type doped by Te ($1 \cdot 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$). During the growth of the buffer, the substrate temperature was 500 °C. Then, the temperature got ramped down to 450 °C for the growth of the 700 nm n^+ -InAsSb ($1 \cdot 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) and 1 μm AlSb/InAs SL ($1 \cdot 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ - $1 \cdot 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) bottom claddings. The SL claddings was grown without soaking by group V material as on the GaSb substrate, AlSb and InAs are countering the strain of each other. Once the growth of the bottom cladding is finished, the substrate temperature was raised to 500 °C for the growth of the bottom 400 nm GaSb SCL and then ramped back down to 450 °C for the growth of the active region. The rest of the structure was grown at the same temperature. Throughout both ICL structures, AlSb/InAs TL were implemented between active region, SCLs and cladding layers for purpose of matching the band offsets.

The active region is composed of **AlSb/InAs/Ga_{0.6}In_{0.4}Sb/InAs/AlSb** (W-shaped QW), GaSb/**AlSb**/GaSb (hole injector), **AlSb/InAs/AlSb/InAs/AlSb/InAs/AlSb/InAs** (electron injector) with thicknesses listed in the Table B.

	AlSb	InAs	GaInSb	InAs	AlSb
W-QW	2.5 nm	2.12 nm	2.50 nm	1.67 nm	1.0 nm

B1. Layer structure of the recombination W-QW region.

	GaSb	AlSb	GaSb
h-injector	2.8 nm	1.0 nm	4.8 nm

B2. Layer structure of the hole injector.

	AlSb	InAs	AlSb	InAs	AlSb	InAs	AlSb	InAs
e-injector	2.5 nm	4.4 nm	1.2 nm	3.2 nm	1.2 nm	2.5 nm	1.2 nm	2.0 nm

B3. Layer structure of the electron injector.

Table B: Layer thicknesses of the recombination region (A1), layer thicknesses of the hole injector (A2) and layer thicknesses of the electron injector (A3) of the ICLs with SL and bulk claddings.

The last three InAs wells of the electron injectors were doped n-type doped to $4 \cdot 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. In order to reduce the contact resistance, InAs-based and GaSb-based ICLs were capped with 25 nm thick layer of highly doped ($2 \cdot 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) InAs and InAsSb respectively.

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B. Petrović, A. Bader, J. Nauschütz, T. Sato, S. Birner, S. Estevam, R. Weih, F. Hartmann and S. Höfling, "Comparison between InAs-based and GaSb-based interband cascade lasers with hybrid superlattice plasmon-enhanced claddings," *Opt. Mat. Express* **14**, 12, 2912-2928 (2024).

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